

**The Influence of Social Media Marketing in
achieving profitability in SME's**

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ABSTRACT

The research study has been carried out to evaluate the influence of social media technology use in the performance of the firm through the perspective of the business owners. With the help of the use of social media technology, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) could easily communicate the information as well as respond with the minimum possible cost. The capability to share information and access the information could influence the performance of SMEs, whereas little research has been carried on the perspective of social media technology use and performance of firm from the perspective of the owner. Compared to big organizations most SMEs finds it hard in executing effective marketing strategies into their business tasks due to its cost, complex strategy and some firms finds it risky to practice new marketing techniques. Online media is somewhat a new phenomena particularly in developing countries, the absence of understanding of its latent capacity, we accept that the social media marketing is an issue that needs studying, particularly its capability of advertisement for SMEs. The objective of the paper is to present a survey quantitatively to explore the mediation effect of marketing capabilities, customer orientation, and brand equity among social media technology use and firm performance in SMEs of Pakistan. (Yadav, 2017)

The research study conducted makes use of a multi-purpose framework where the impact of social media technology use on firm performance and the mediating role of marketing capabilities, customer orientation, and brand equity has been covered. A survey questionnaire has been used to collect the data from the sample of SMEs operating in Pakistan. Data from 224 respondents has been collected and analysed. From the research, it has been found that social media technology use has a positive impact on firm performance. In addition to this, it has been found that marketing capabilities and customer orientation as mediators impact positively the performance of a firm with the use of social media technology. No impact has been found whereas of brand equity as a mediator between social media technology use and firm performance. Implications of the research area for the SMEs.

Keywords: Social media technology use (STU), Firm performance (FP), Brand equity (BE), Marketing capabilities (MC), Customer orientation (CO).

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CHAPTER 1

1. Introduction

Social media marketing has gained popularity and has become essential for SMEs due to its lower marketing costs and the significant number of benefits it can bring. Social media applications are not only used for communication purposes, but also help to engage consumers with brands (Hanna et al., 2011). Jurgens et al. (2016) assert that the use of social media tools has been increased to enhance interactive communication between consumers and businesses. These social networking tools are sufficient to create brand-related discussion at a lower cost and within a limited time. Based on customers' reviews related to products or brands, businesses can modify the products and enhance the level of service quality according to these customers' needs, wants, and demands (Paniagua and Sapena, 2014). Compared to other SMEs, retail clothing businesses have more opportunities to grow through social media, new marketing tactics, and greater awareness about the trends and fashions across the world.

All of the digital, mobile and social media platforms (in view of Web 2.0 standards) have changed market and business elements by creating organizations' competitive positions (Porter, 2001) and expanding customer power. In the midst of this dangerous development of social media innovations, firms are seeing ways to leverage user-generated content (UGC) and produce solid firm-generated content (FGC) for buyer commitment in social media. There is evidence that online media can be utilized to build and oversee brands, and to improve and support clients' relationship with firms, and consequently can bring advantages to organizations around the world, further resulting in organisational success (Arora and Sanni, 2018).

Zhu and Chen (2015) argued that customers are making purchasing decisions based on the information available on different social media platforms. Therefore, SMEs are exploiting these tools by investing in credible sources and opinion leaders, who can use marketing tools to create the right word of mouth among targeted customers.

Compared to developed countries, the levels of education, customer awareness, technology usage and internet facilities, and the numbers of skilled and trained employees for social media marketing, are not up-to-the-mark in less developed countries (Tiago and Veríssimo, 2014). Therefore, even though social media as a marketing tool is helpful to promote socialization and

information sharing about products, services, and customers, there is still a lack of understanding on how social media influences the sustainability and profitability of SMEs, especially in the context of developing countries where there are more restrictions and lower levels of awareness about the usage of social media applications. Many countries have imposed certain restrictions on the usage of WhatsApp, Skype, and Facebook: in Nyairo's (2016) study, such restrictions were present in 12 of the 65 countries examined. Furthermore, Telegram, Facebook, Messenger, Line, Viber, Google handouts, and IMO are also frequently blocked in most of the developing countries. In some countries, restrictions still exist. Facebook is banned in China, while Nigeria has banned Twitter. It has been calculated that social media is blocked in 180 countries from 2015 to the present day. (Surfshark, 2021). However, most of the previous studies have been conducted on SMEs in western countries where there are minimal restrictions on the use of social media tools compared to Asian countries (Öztamur and Karakadılar, 2014; Eggers et al., 2017).

Social media help small businesses to increase brand awareness, build a customer base and continuously engage with customers through interactive content in the form of text, pictures, or videos (Weinberg and Pehlivan, 2011). Social media have become highly significant over the past decade and continue to grow at an exceptional rate (Kietzmann et al., 2011). Internet usage will continue to grow along with the world's population, and so will social media (Paniagua and Sapena, 2014).

According to Jurgens et al. (2016), social media marketing is the 'next big thing' Nearly three billion people on the planet use at least one form of social media. Williams (2017) states that around 40% of the world's population are social media users (with active social media profiles on any of the social media platforms). Such massive usage of social media platforms allows small and medium businesses to exploit the opportunity to reach out to their target customers cost-effectively and with greater precision (Lee, 2018). However, social media have turned the tables, and now such platforms are used to increase website traffic. Social media are now primarily used by small and medium enterprises due to their cost-effectiveness and targeted approach (Khera, 2018).

This research aims to evaluate the influence of social media technology use on the performance of businesses. The businesses on which this research will focus are companies in the retail clothing sector that are operating in Pakistan. The research is primary and is focused on collecting feedback/responses from business owners regarding variables such as business

performance, brand equity, marketing capabilities, customer orientation, and social media technology use. The researcher collected data using an online survey questionnaire and applied statistical data analysis techniques to drive the results. The results of this research are highly likely to benefit micro-enterprises and small and medium enterprises (SMEs), who could use the practical tools and social media strategies to promote their businesses, as the four large retailers in Pakistan are doing.

Paniagua and Sapena (2014) argue that countries need to focus on the SME sector to achieve increased employment and economic prosperity. The SME sector supports the economy of a country by bringing employment and innovation activities to the market. SMEs play a vital role in the economic, social, and modern development of a nation (Prenaj, 2016). SMEs' commitment towards GDP growth and their ability to increase the standard of living have gained the attention of the underdeveloped countries. As described by Keskgñ et al. (2018), SMEs have gained importance in developing economies due to their rapid adaption of technology.

In Pakistan, SMEs broadly consider government policies and processes as problems and challenges for their growth rather than as sources of support and positive reforms fostering their economic activity (Papachristodoulou et al., 2017). It is vital for Pakistan to focus on economic development through strengthening the SME sector by offering rebates and a conducive environment for business activities (Zafar and Mustafa, 2017).

The usage of social media tools has increased more in the private sector compared to the public sector. A previous study highlighted that most investors are interested in investing in the private sector because of its long-term sustainability, attractive profitability, and high success rate (Syed et al., 2012). Other studies suggested finding the impact of social media marketing efforts on the sustainability and profitability of SMEs, with the purpose of determining how much investment, time and effort are needed to achieve the financial and non-financial targets (Öztamur and Karakadılar, 2014). On the other hand, it is also stated that the failure of the private sector could become the reason why many members of the workforce are unemployed, as well as causing a significant decrease in economic growth (Ahmad, 2018). Researchers, marketing managers, and business leaders are currently searching for inventive ways to take advantage of social networking tools for the sustainability and profitability of businesses. They are using social media for relationship management with customers. Some researchers also suggest that social media marketing is suitable for small businesses, as it provides them with a

cost-effective way of conveying their message before an audience (Durkin *et al.*, 2014). They can spread the message about products and services within limited resources to a broader audience, which is readily available in respect to traditional media (Mejía-Trejo, 2017). Social media marketing in the context of SMEs is an important phenomenon that needs exploration and further understanding.

Social media networks and Pakistani SMEs have been the prime focus of this research. Business models are also changing with the rise of social networks. Social networking websites are shaping the markets, as the concept of e-retailers is also emerging, and consumers are increasingly interacting with businesses online on social media platforms (Chen, and Leteney, 2000). Businesses these days are not merely seeking to establish only a physical presence or an online presence; instead, they are looking to establish themselves both online and physically, as it is becoming apparent that this is necessary in order to be successful (Wang *et al.*, 2016), using the so-called ‘bricks and clicks’ business model. Such businesses operate physical stores and buildings (the ‘bricks’ aspect), while the ‘clicks’ aspect represents their online or e-commerce activities (Ofek *et al.*, 2011).

1.1. Background of the study

Marketing communication using social networking tools such as Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, and WhatsApp have been attracting increasing attention from many fashion brands, service providers, and consumers (Ha and Lee, 2018; Richter and Koch, 2008). According to Valos *et al.* (2016), some companies are using 30% of their budgets to promote interactive communication by using digital marketing tools. With the advent and rise of social media, marketing staff and customers have shifted from old-fashioned (i.e., single-way) communication to interactive two-way direct communication. Social networking tools have become important because of their interactive nature and useful role to facilitate information exchange between service providers and consumers (Ha and Lee, 2018). Many fashion designers, such as Chanel, Ralph Lauren, Gucci, and Donna Karan, have taken the services of Apple to create iPhone applications to enhance their interactive communication, sales, and profitability (Kim and Ko, 2012).

The number of users of such websites and applications is increasing with time in Pakistan. There are over 44 million social media accounts in Pakistan alone, out of which Facebook users comprise 14 million, while Twitter users account for 2.5 million (Husian, 2017). Social media users can create their virtual profile online, whereby they can upload their pictures, share

videos, write messages, and so on. People from all over the world are spending a considerable amount of time on social media. There are over two billion users of social media across the globe, of whom over a billion are active on social media each day (Zulqarnain and Hassan, 2017). Moreover, Husian (2017) indicated that “Pakistan is one of Asia’s fastest-growing internet markets”. Companies are increasingly promoting their services and products with the help of social media. Therefore, it will be useful to highlight the ways in which social media marketing strategies can help small businesses to promote their products and services.

The technological advances in recent times have shifted the focus of marketing to online platforms (Shaltoni, 2017). Computer-based platforms are revolutionizing the ways businesses have been carried out, such as user-generated content, Web 2.0, and social networking applications (Cheng *et al.*, 2016). These advances have enabled businesses to gain consumer-oriented input and user data and maintain two-way communications, while allowing consumers to share content with businesses and collaborate openly and freely (Whiting *et al.*, 2017). The rise of social media platforms has allowed small businesses to reach out to various customers simultaneously, regardless of the geographical boundaries. For this reason, small businesses have attracted customers by adopting social media marketing strategies (McCann and Barlow, 2015). There are also disparities in existing studies concerning small businesses’ social media marketing, with inconclusive findings that reflect contextual differences (Ungerma, and Myslivcová, 2014). Therefore, further research must be conducted in this area. There is also little evidence of the practical and successful utility of social media marketing from the aspect of SMEs (Cheng *et al.*, 2016; Kalkan and Bozkurt, 2017), or concerning social media marketing and small businesses in terms of their financial performance.

1.1.1 Background of SMEs in Pakistan

SMEs are now mainly using social media platforms to reach out to their target customers. Social media are used for selling, brand building, and consumer engagement; however, before these platforms emerged, companies, including SMEs, used traditional marketing techniques. But as argued by Li *et al.* (2018), the quantum of marketing activities used by small businesses were not the same. The globalization era and now the digital age, including social media, have allowed businesses to reach out to clients that are beyond their physical geographical boundaries. Social media marketing is expected to grow in the future, especially by small business; however, to predict the future, it is also essential to understand how things have

evolved and how marketing forms have changed and adapted to modern technology, changing business forms and consumers' trends/behaviours (Saridakis *et al.*, 2019).

The world of technology and our relationship with it have seen drastic advancements, and marketing strategies have had to cope with these changes. Similarly, the sales function of businesses had to deal with the invention of the telephone, which was followed by the popularity of the television. With the invention of personal computers, the industry of the Marketing Company Era experienced the most significant leap in its history. This invention enabled mass adoption of the internet daily (Saridakis *et al.*, 2019).

With further increase in usage, the web continued its development and usability. Different features came into existence, such as Electronic Mail (email) and search engines like Yahoo! and Google. Similarly, people gradually began to realize that this virtual social organization could also be used to conduct business and other financial transactions. Telephone, television, print media, and radio were already in place to be used, and were then joined by email as a new tool of outbound marketing. As search engines grew popular on massive scales, early marketers used advanced techniques at the time to generate high rankings (Weinberg and Pehlivan, 2011).

In the early 1990s, the internet set foot in Pakistan, and the first email services were developed by Digicom Pakistan Limited during the same period. The same company provided the first internet service in the mid-1990s (Baloch, 2016). Similarly, using a nationwide call dialup network, the state-owned company called Pakistan Telecommunications Company Ltd (PTCL) started offering access. To boost the country's appetite for economic modernization using the web and the development of an export-oriented software market, Pakistan has been making advanced and aggressive Information Technology (IT) policies (Aurora 2017). As a result of such fruitful policies, the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) industry in Pakistan is growing at a notably healthy pace. Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMAX) technology is also being provided to be adopted at a mass level (Aurora, 2017).

Increasing use of the internet has also allowed small businesses to develop their virtual presence (mostly in the form of websites) to connect with online users using search engine optimization (SEO) techniques. The internet sector that gained the most attention was IT (including software houses and other IT-related service providers). SMEs in various sectors marketed their products on a regional basis, and due to lack of funds and low marketing budgets, they restricted their marketing/advertising campaigns to the regional level. Of course,

this restricted the ability of SMEs to reach out to a broader audience due to the high costs associated with marketing campaigns. Social media has changed the dynamics of businesses, especially SMEs; however, this does not mean that traditional marketing activities are not feasible or suitable. They are still very influential and are necessary for long-term sustainable profitability (Zafar and Mustafa, 2017).

Mass marketing campaigns were not affordable (and still are not), and therefore SMEs used to work with traditional mindsets, namely doing businesses with routine clients in an orthodox manner. SME owners would visit different regions to make business contacts through personal meetings and establish their foothold in different local and international markets (Ahmad, 2018).

With the advancement of modern technology, customers are now more than ever influenced by online E-WOM (electronic word of mouth). Previous research has shown that while traditional media channels can disseminate information to dozens of people at one point in time, social media can instantly deliver information to thousands of users at a time (Stewart, 2016). Businesses value reviews from early adopters of their products or services since the position of their companies and their reputation are at stake. This research involves an active investigation conducted with many marketing scholars discussing the effects of E-WOM, and mainly focusing on the quantitative aspects of reviews. It ignores textual reviews, as these are very unstructured. The most effective social media acts as a platform that facilitates mutual communication between business and users. It has significantly altered the nature of interactions and communication between businesses and users.

1.2. Research Problem

At present, social media networking applications are gaining increasing popularity in the context of SMEs. SMEs are increasingly using various social networking applications as social media marketing strategies. Many companies rely on more than one form of social media for marketing purposes (Wearesocial, 2018).

Moreover, Ali and Yousaf (2017) argued that social media is a factor of crucial significance for small businesses to gain success. Social media generate many of the sales for small businesses in Pakistan, such as OLX, which is one the primary websites providing an online platform for SMEs to sell their products online (Chong et al., 2018). However, many small businesses are still unaware of the relevance and significance of social media marketing. The general problem of business is that while social media marketing strategies may be chalked

out, the implementation of such strategies can be a gruelling task. The lack of social media marketing specialists, time, resources, and appropriate social media marketing strategies can add to problems for small businesses (Gutierrez-Leefmans *et al.*, 2016), and this can affect their competitiveness. As indicated by Stokes (2000), SMEs mostly undertake marketing for immediate necessities and pay little consideration to strategies and techniques. To survive in the market, SMEs guide their focus toward sales. The responsibility falls to SME owners for operations and performance inside an association, like recruitment, advertising, sales, marketing and purchasing. They frequently choose which marketing strategies to utilize on the ground because it is rare to have marketing experts as representatives in the marketing department. On the other hand, large organisations are huge enough to have advertising departments that allow the outline of activities and operations. This distinction can be ascribed to specific constraints faced by small firms with restricted resources in terms of money, time, and marketing purposes (Petrevska, 2016).

The specific business problem explored in the current research is that owners of small retail businesses need to overcome the barriers that are preventing them from applying social media marketing. Many SMEs in Pakistan lack the resources to compete against large businesses in the market. Compared to big organizations, most SMEs finds it hard to integrate IT into their business tasks, as this is a costly initiative with various other barriers. Having as a main priority that online media is a somewhat new phenomenon, particularly in developing countries, and there is thus a lack of understanding of its latent capacity, it can be accepted that the social media marketing is an issue that needs to be studied, particularly its capability of advertisement for SMEs (Yadav, 2017).

However, social media is increasingly becoming popular among Pakistani people, as they are using it as a strategic platform for communication. As a result, social media adoption and usage presents an exciting feature that can help SMEs to maintain their competitiveness in the market. Therefore, the present study will examine the social media marketing practices and advantages for the growth of small businesses in Pakistan. The research is based on a multiple case study approach to determine the role of social media marketing actives to enhance the sustainability and profitability of SMEs in the context of Pakistan.

In SMEs, the study will be focused on retail clothing businesses that are more frequently using various social media applications to enhance profits. The research will explore the SME

owners' experiences, meanings, and usage of social media as a marketing tool in the development of their businesses.

1.3. Research Gaps

Due to the rise of social media for businesses, small businesses can lose customers if they do not adequately follow social media marketing strategies. Efficient and effective marketing strategies enable small businesses to compete with large businesses (Brink, 2017; Durkin *et al.*, 2014). However, small businesses have not yet developed full awareness about the marketing strategies which are helpful to achieve their business targets (Nobre and Silva, 2014). It is also important to note that the exact numbers of barriers faced by small businesses are not yet fully known, especially in developing countries that have a shortage of financial, human, technological, and other resources. There are also barriers faced by small businesses concerning the implementation of social media strategies (Eggers *et al.*, 2017; Bocconcelli *et al.*, 2017). It is important to note that there has been limited research carried out concerning the social media marketing utilized by small businesses to improve their business sustainability and profitability (Gholston *et al.*, 2016; Pérez-González *et al.*, 2017; Wiścicka-Fernando, 2018). The subject area of marketing is frequently in need of exploration of the marketing efforts that small businesses undertake on social media to promote their brands (Kriechbaumer and Christodoulidou, 2014). Moreover, Scuotto *et al.* (2017) argued that small businesses from developing countries are not likely to adopt the latest technology quickly, particularly in relation to e-commerce. Many small businesses, however, are exploring the opportunities on social media from a marketing perspective in developing countries as well as developed ones (Kalafsky, 2017). The limited literature available related to the influence of social media marketing in the context of sustainability and profitability of SMEs is mainly in the context of developing countries.

There is scant research literature available on the effective utilization of social media marketing in the context of marketing (Guha *et al.*, 2018; Wiścicka-Fernando, 2018). Although many other topics have been extensively analysed, such as electronic commerce concerning businesses, there is little literature on social media marketing for small businesses, especially in the context of developing countries. The focus in this research on small businesses from the aspect of social media marketing and its connection with sustainability and profitability of SMEs is also minimal. Therefore, this research aims to investigate the relative social media marketing practices to improve SMEs' sustainability and profitability, especially in the context

and culture of Pakistan. The level of education, usage of technologies, business methods, marketing strategies, offerings, advertisements, languages, fashions, designs, customs, and business tactics in developing countries vary compared to developed countries (Rehman *et al.*, 2016; Brown, 2017). Therefore, it is essential to find the influence of social marketing practices that are more beneficial to increase the sustainability and profitability of SMEs from the perspective of Pakistan.

1.4. Research Objectives

The following are the research objectives of the present study.

1. To evaluate the role of social media technology use in the performance of SMEs in Pakistan;
2. To evaluate the impact of social media technology use on customer orientation, marketing capabilities, and brand equity of SMEs in Pakistan;
3. To evaluate the impact of customer orientation, marketing capabilities, and brand equity on firm performance of SMEs in Pakistan;
4. To investigate how customer orientation, marketing capabilities, and brand equity mediate the relationship between social media technology use and firm performance for SMEs in Pakistan.

1.5. Scope of the Research

The impact of social media and firms' financial performance has been very well documented, whereas the impact of the use of social media technology on the performance of firms with the mediation of marketing capabilities, customer orientation, and brand equity has not yet been studied very thoroughly. The aim of the present study is to report on the impact of such mediation on the use of social media technology and firm performance.

The scope of the study is limited to a sample of 224 respondents to a survey questionnaire, drawn from the population of 2.9m SMEs in Pakistan. A survey questionnaire was prepared and filled in by the sample. Reliability tests were performed on the data collected from the respondents. In addition to this, correlation analysis was performed on the data collected. Regression analysis was also carried out, taking into consideration the assumptions of such analysis, to test the hypotheses developed for the study. Baron and Kenny's (1986) mediation steps were used in this analysis.

1.6. Research Significance

The present study provides a new perspective on the impact of social media technology use on the performance of SMEs. The significance of the study is that it investigates the influence of social media technology use on firm performance with the mediating role of marketing capabilities, customer orientation, and brand equity. Prior researchers have focused only on social media usage, whereas the current research is focused on social media technology use instead. Moreover, performance is not measured based on financial figures, but rather from the employer's point of view. Similarly, the mediating role of brand equity has not been measured from the customers' point of view, but rather has been taken into consideration from the perspective of employers, and how they feel about the equity of their brand. Also, before this research, this relationship had been investigated using qualitative methodology, but it has never before been investigated using quantitative methods. The research is significant to single owners and private companies, as it is based on extensive investigation into SMEs in Pakistan.

1.7. Dissertation Structure (thesis outline)

This thesis includes six chapters.

Chapter	Title	Content Summary
1	Introduction	This chapter includes an introduction to the research, including the research background and gap, research problem, significance and objectives.
2	Literature Review	This chapter reviews the literature related to social media, social media theories, types of social media platforms, social media technology use, marketing capabilities, customer orientation and brand equity.
3	Proposed research model	This chapter develops the research model for the thesis and provides a visual presentation of the framework. For the purpose of the research, ten hypotheses have been developed and the relationships between these proposed hypotheses are explained
4	Methodology	This chapter sets out the methodology of the research, including components of the study based on the research onion, the data collection process, ethics of the research, and explanations of the techniques of data analysis

5	Findings, Analysis and Discussion	This chapter provides a discussion and analysis of data obtained through the research performed. It includes the respondents' profiles, reliability testing, descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis, testing of the hypotheses, and a discussion of the results.
6	Conclusion, Implications and Future Research	Chapter Six is the last chapter of the research and presents the conclusion, implications of the research, both practical and theoretical, as well as research limitations and future implications.

1.8. Chapter Summary

The purpose of the current study is to find the influence of social media marketing in the context of sustainability and profitability of SMEs in Pakistan. This study intends to find the influence of social media marketing in the retail clothing industry in Pakistan. The E-commerce boom has increased the importance of social media marketing, as social media presence is now considered very important for any form of business (Zhu and Chen, 2015).

In Pakistan, being a developing country, many small businesses are still unaware of the relevance and significance of social media marketing. The general problem is that while social media marketing strategies are present, small business owners are hesitant to implement such strategies because the lack of social media marketing specialists, time, resources, and appropriate sets of social media marketing strategies can add to the problems faced by small businesses (Gutierrez-Leefmans *et al.*, 2016) and affect their competitiveness. The specific business problem explored in the current research is the barriers that need to be overcome by owners of small retail businesses, as such barriers are preventing them from applying social media marketing.

The research is primary and focused on collecting feedback/responses from business owners regarding research variables such as business performance, brand equity, marketing capabilities, customer orientation, and social media technology use. The researcher will collect data using an online survey questionnaire and apply statistical data analysis techniques to derive the results.

CHAPTER 2

2. Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

The previous chapter has been given a brief detail regarding background, justifications, research gap, scope, aims, and objectives. The first chapter has highlighted how this study provides a real contribution to current knowledge in the context of social media marketing and perceived sustainability and profitability of SMEs. The purpose of this chapter is to provide a critical literature review that constructs a baseline of knowledge about the role of social media marketing in the perspective of perceived sustainability and profitability of SMEs. The concept of social media marketing is introduced before the synthesis of social media marketing's importance to improve the sustainability and profitability of SMEs. This chapter has brief details regarding the following perspectives: the concept of social media and its importance for business, the concept of social media marketing and its significance for SMEs, justifications for creating the link between social media marketing and sustainability and profitability of SMEs, and summary of critical literature review.

2.2. Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is considered an umbrella term for all sorts of marketing over digital platforms (Saravanakumar and SuganthaLakshmi, 2012). Digital marketing can be categorized into various sections such as online digital marketing, offline digital marketing, and search marketing. However, there are various sorts of definitions of digital marketing, but the basic idea is to promote the product or service over digital platforms. According to Hanssens and Pauwels, (2016), digital marketing is the use of mobile devices, social media, display advertising, social media, the internet, and other digital channels to reach out to customers. Corporations are now focusing on having 'digital relationships' with customers (Lamberton and Stephen, 2016). It implies that reaching out to customers using digital platforms is increasing, and the trend continues to grow in the coming years. Digital marketing is primarily used to attract consumers towards e-commerce (or online shopping). The trend is on the rise in developed countries like the US and UK and many other underdeveloped countries (Tiago and Veríssimo, 2014). Hence, the increase in e-commerce would also increase in digital marketing initiatives (Saravanakumar and SuganthaLakshmi, 2012).

Wylie, (2014) asserts that digital marketing includes activities, processes, and institutions that facilitate the use of digital technologies effectively to deliver value to the customers by communication. Zhu and Chen, (2015) argue that digital technologies such as smartphones, smart mobile devices, internet-of-things (IoT), and Artificial Intelligence would continue to change the lives of people globally and would surely change the marketing landscape.

The term ‘digital marketing’ has evolved over many years from a specific term describing to use of digital platforms for products and services to an umbrella term describing the process where digital technologies are applied to reach out to the target audience (Papachristodoulou, Koutsaki and Kirkos, 2017).

2.3. Social Media Part of Digital Marketing

Social media is one part of an overall digital marketing strategy. Social media is one form of digital platform that is used by people to engage, interact and share content in the form of images, voice, and videos (Tuten, 2008). Digital marketing has one branch of internet marketing under which all the technologies using the internet are considered or targeted to market the product and service messages. Social media is one part of internet marketing and hence, comes under digital marketing. However, as per Levy, (2013), social media is now becoming one of the largest and most influential mediums over digital platforms and therefore, needs special attention and understanding by markets to influence the consumers for the purchase of products and services (Ngai *et al.*, 2015).

2.4. Defining Social Media

Tuten, 2008: Web 2.0 is the second stage of the development of the internet that is mainly known for its development of static to interactive web pages. Social media platforms use web 2.0 technology enabling the users or members of an online social community to interact, share content and engage in a dialogue using several options .

Basille 2009: Defined social media as the democratization of information hence, converting the public from receivers to publishers. This definition focuses on the capability of content created by the members of the social medium. As per Basille , term social means respecting others, like people, and communicating with them to have a functional and constructive relationship. The other part is ‘media’, which usually means any communication medium. Hence, ‘social media’ means socializing with people through a communication medium.

Kaplan and Haenlein 2010: They used two concepts in defining social media (i) USG (user-generated content); and (ii) Web 2.0. USG can be a form of content that is created for the public by individuals, and Web 2.0 is a technology providing platform for the websites or applications to run over World Wide Web. , Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) asserted that social media is a collection of internet-based applications that are built on the foundation of Web 2.0 and allow users to generate and exchange user-generated content

Campbell *et al.*, 2011: Social media is considered as one of the critical inventions since, the automobiles that make people mobile.

Zinnbauer and Honer ,2011: Social media development is directly related to technological advancements

Kietzmann *et al.*, 2011: Social media is run on web platforms that are used to enable content creation, exchange, and collaboration among participants. They argue that social media is a mixture of technology and sociology that is dependent upon the transformation of information flow that turns from a monologue into a dialogue.

Saravanakumar and SuganthaLakshmi 2012: Social media news can become viral in no time as people are free to share with as many people they want.

Peters *et al.*, 2013: Various social media platforms use web 2.0 technology such as Facebook, Twitter, Myspace, and LinkedIn, etc. many social media platforms are run based on users generated content such as YouTube, Wikipedia, Helium, etc.

Wylie 2014: defined social media as a tool or platform where users can get information or content from each other rather than from traditional institutions such as companies and newspapers etc.

Zhu and Chen 2015: Traditional media follows the broadcasting concept of disseminating information to the specific target audience; however, social media uses the flow of information from many-to-many where active communication among members of online communication is conducted .

Felix et al., 2017: Asserts that due to the sheer quality of social media where users generate content, it is also challenging to control. Social media is also referred to as consumer-generated

media since consumers generate the content for other members that generates engagement with each other.

Page *et al.*, 2018: there is no constant definition of social media due to its reason for continuous evolution since its inception

2.5. Social Media Theories

Media research extensively works on concerns about whether media exposure can influence individual behaviors and attitudes (Constantinides, 2014). Certain conditions specific to the individual may lead to media selection or specific media content, which then leads to reinforcing behavioral and attitude changes. Various theories are used by experts to elaborate on social media's impact on behaviours and attitudes of the users. Theories such as the Theory of Social Presence, Social Cognitive Theory, and Media Richness Theory are some essential and widely used by the researchers while researching social media influences on human behaviours. It requires a little innovativeness to perceive how you can tailor your message to fit these theories.

2.5.1. Social Presence Theory

Social Presence Theory was developed by social psychologists John Short, Ederyn Williams, and Bruce Christie, co-authors of the 1976 book *The Social Psychology of Telecommunications*. Lombard and Ditton, in 1997, translated Social Presence Theory as a multi-dimensional and adaptable idea that arranges media as indicated by how well social media pass on closeness and warmth among internet users by their capacity to make a bond between users.

Social presence comprises of psychological processes like social direction, motivating skills and what rouses the sensation of being together, even through a screen. An investigation led by Baozhou, Weiguo, and Zhou, in 2015, social presence assembles trust between people, which is critical to our collaborations face to face or in online platforms. Online correspondence and chat facility has ascended in recent years, Social Presence Theory has been adjusted to the new medium, to clarify how we depict ourselves, to make individual connections with others on the web (Kehrwald, 2008).

SOCIAL PRESENCE THEORY:

2.5.2. *Social Cognitive Theory*

The field of mass communication research widely appraises the Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986). Bandura in his book argued that human behaviour is caused by personal, behavioural, and environmental influences (Bandura, 1986).

The theory explains the explicit capability of human behaviours shaped by observational learning. Social Cognitive Theory is widely applied to social media’s effect on user behaviours. This theory suggests a causal model explaining the human behaviours under the reciprocal interaction among people (including affective, cognitive, and biological events), environmental and behavioural factors (Kaplan and Mazurek, 2018). The theory explains that individuals are encouraged or discouraged in adapting other persons’ values or behaviours, based on perceived consequences, i.e., rewards or punishments (Page et al. 2018).

SOCIAL COGNITIVE THEORY

2.5.3. Media Richness Theory

MEDIA RICHNESS THEORY

Media Richness theory suggested by Daft and Lengel, (1986) assumes that any type of communication purpose is to reduce uncertainty and resolve ambiguity (Hanna et al., 2011). MRT is used to rank and evaluate the richness of certain communication media, such as phone calls, video conferencing, and email. For example, a phone call cannot reproduce visual social cues such as gestures which makes it a less rich communication media than video conferencing, which affords the transmission of gestures and body language.

The theory explains the richness of different types of media, which is mainly dependent upon (i) its ability to convey verbal and non-verbal signals; (ii) quality or ability of immediate feedback; (iii) presence of personal focus and (iv) use of natural language. Based on the above factors, some communication mediums are more effective, and that is more people use the reason. This theory is also applicable to marketing communication decisions and strategy formulation. Messages that are not rich or equivocal (i.e., memos or letters) do not require rich media, therefore, could be used lean media. Rich theory suggests that face-to-face communication contains high richness followed by telephone and then electronic email (Rayat *et al.*, 2017). This theory applied to social media could rank it below face-to-face communication (Rayat *et al.*, 2017), or some say it could be ranked above all due to its richness.

Along with the theories mentioned above related to social media influence on human behaviour, three laws are explaining the role of the human element on medium effectiveness. These laws are discussed and explained below.
Information Richness and Communication Channels

Figure redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at: <http://ashleerbrookens.blogspot.com/>.

Source: <http://ashleerbrookens.blogspot.com/>

2.5.4. Sarnoff's Law

Sarnoff Law was postulated by David Sarnoff, who is the pioneer in the broadcasting business and founded NBC (*National Broadcasting Company*) (Ngai, Tao and Moon, 2015). The law states that to make a one-to-one network worthwhile, it is essential the specific number of participants are there. However, the drawback of this law is that it can only be applied to the one-way communication medium.

2.5.5. Metcalf's Law (100)

Robert Metcalfe postulated this law in 1980, stating that for a two-way communication network, the value or worth of such network equals to square of the number of users in that community or network. It can be quantified and justified in a way that people can communicate in two directions and hence, more than one conversation takes place at one time. This law can only be applied to networks having two-way communication, such as emails and telephone (Ngai et al., 2015).

2.5.6. Reed's Law

David Reed postulated this law and is also referred to as 'The Law of the Pack', which explains the mathematical explanation of the power of a communication medium or network. This law argues that every member's entry into the network doubles its value (Bakić-Mirić, 2018). As per Evans, (2008), the value of a network is primarily increased by Reed's law compared to the previous two laws (i.e., Sarnoff's and Metcalf's). Reed's law can be applied to the social networking paradigm where every member's addition to the groups creates tremendous value and opens new dimensions of interactions and communication. A drawback of Reed's law is the absence of the human element in the mathematical calculation of the network evaluation.

2.6. Types of Social media platforms and current usage

Social media role will remain towards the creation of communities and hence, encourage members to engage in conversations (Zhu and Chen, 2015). Billions of people are using social media today, and as internet penetration is increasing the use of social media is also increasing. Currently, there are nearly 2.77 billion social media users globally, and the number is rising with every passing day (Rayat *et al.*, 2017). Some of the major social media platforms currently in use of the majority of the social media users are Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Myspace, WhatsApp, YouTube, and Flickr (Constantinides, 2014). As per Zhu and Chen, (2015), social media selection by the users is based upon its ability to allow diverse participation, interactive

conversation, friendly platform, and support collaboration (Felix *et al.*, 2017). Following are a few prominent examples of social media and their functionality types along with their current Monthly Average Users (MAUs).

Table 1: Social media platforms and functionality

Digital Platform	Functionality	MAUs
Facebook	Social Networking	2.23 billion
YouTube	Video Sharing	1.9 billion
WhatsApp	Instant Messaging/ content sharing	1.5 billion
FB Messenger	Instant Messaging/ content sharing	1.3 billion
WeChat	Instant Messaging/ content sharing	1.06 billion
Instagram	Social Networking	1 billion
Twitter	Micro Blogging	335 million
LinkedIn	Social Networking	294 million

Before using social media as a marketing tool, every aspect of social media must be understood table shows the monthly active users on different social media platforms. Table shows some of the main channels for marketing purpose in Pakistan which SMEs can target to advertise their products and services because of active users.

This table is adding value in the research for SMEs by describing the functionality of digital platforms so SMEs can take advantage by sharing the right content on proper channel to maximize their reach to the target audience. The primary thing you ought to research for marketing is that what social applications your audience is using. For most organizations, the best methodology is to handpick online media channels that suits well for the brand, as opposed to put efforts all over. Few out of every odd online media channel will function admirably for your industry. For example, visually driven enterprises like cosmetology and fashion industry incline toward Instagram, Facebook and Snapchat. These organizations depend more on visuals than text, so they're an extraordinary fit.

For using social media as a marketing tool, every aspect of social media must be understood. Web 2.0 technology and its functionality need to be adequately understood before making any marketing efforts on social media platforms. Web 2.0 provides a platform where continuous updating of content is required to keep the users engaged with the brand or the company (Zhu and Chen, 2015). As per Hanna *et al.*, (2011) it is much more about the people who are using

the technology rather than the technology itself. Users are now creating the content and consuming it; therefore, adding value to the websites that allow them to do so (Felix *et al.*, 2017). As mentioned in table 1 above, various social media platforms (all using Web 2.0) technology are used by millions across the world, and the number is continuously on the rise. It shows the importance and popularity of social media consumption across the world. As per Malthouse *et al.*, (2013), social media has now become the top trending items where news and information are shared among millions, and that makes the news viral.

2.7. Research Overview

Social media is increasingly being used in Pakistan by people for various reasons. It is primarily being used for socializing purposes, i.e., staying in touch with friends and family. It is also being used as a platform for debating and discussing various issues of political and social. In social issues, people are discussing the products and services that are required in their daily lives. Social media play a significant role in promoting brands and awareness related to brands. There are over 2 billion active users on Facebook, which shows a significant number of people in the world. Therefore, those businesses who are promoting their products and services on Facebook are targeting a pool of 2 billion potential customers (Ali and Yousaf, 2017).

For example, a clothing brand in Pakistan, **Furor**, took to social media for spreading its message before its Pakistani customers. However, the company has various rivals in the industry as it is new in the industry. However, the company maintained its competitiveness by agreeing with two famous Vloggers in the country. In no time, the number of fans increased for the brand. The content which the businesses share on social media is a source of attraction for people (Chong *et al.*, 2018). It increases the number of followers for the brand. These followers represent the potential customer base for the business. It shows that social media is not only a source of brand awareness for the business but also a source of attracting potential customers (Eggers *et al.*, 2017). Social media is also the most efficient and cheapest source of publicity for businesses. It provides a platform where people are discussing the latest trends and including the fashion retail brands (Bocconcelli *et al.*, 2017). There were times when word of mouth was the cheapest source of publicity. Social media has given rise to e-WOM, whereby people are spreading awareness about a brand on social media to each other. It is becoming an online source of word of mouth for the brands (Durkin *et al.*, 2014). A business must maintain a strong presence on social media to attract such customers. People now determine the standard

of a brand by considering the positive reviews the brand has on social media (Odoom *et al.*, 2017).

Each day, billions of people are spending their time on social media. Every person is creating various connections on social media. Social media does not necessarily represent a tool for exchanging information but that it can cast an influence on the decision making of the consumer. There is the influence of online messages from peers whereby such messages shape the behaviour of consumers, their purchasing trends, and awareness about the brand and its products (Franco *et al.*, 2014). A survey shows that 60% of the people present on social media are either writing a review or that they shared an existing review on their profile with friends and family (Cheng *et al.*, 2016). Consumers use reviews for sharing their experiences with other users. In this manner, social media has provided a platform to companies for sharing information about their products and services (Shaltoni, 2017). Social media has revolutionized the internet by making it not only an information source but also an influential source (Pérez-González *et al.*, 2017).

A little increase in Pakistan has been noticed in the number of broadband users. It has happened after 3G and 4G, and 4G LTE is launched in the country. The prominent reason behind the increase in several internet users is due to budget-friendly Smartphones in the country which can operate on 3G and 4G (Convex, 2018). There are over 50 million users of 3G and 4G internet in the country which shows a 24.5% increase from November 2017. The major contributors were mobile broadband which had 47 million 3G/4G subscribers as per the data on the PTA website. It represents 23% penetration. The total number of subscribers of the fixed local line has crossed 3 million (Zaheer, 2017). The number of 3G and 4G users in the country had reached 46 million in November 2017. The total number of users of broadband had increased to 48 million. There are over 144 million users of mobile phones in Pakistan. It is more than 142.5 million users in the country in October 2017 (BBC, 2018). Telecommunication has also increased in respect to mobile phones, i.e., it increases up to 70.83%. Soon the launch of 5G technology is planned by PTA in the country. It is estimated that by the year 2020, the 5G technology will be available in the country on a commercial basis (PTA, 2017). Initial tests for 5G technology are already underway after the approval from the cabinet has been received. Social media have shaped modern-day communication in the country Internet users in Pakistan seem to be sharply catching up with the modern-day communication methods (PTA, 2017).

There were over 44 million social media accounts in Pakistan as per the statistics from social media houses. The numbers have only increased ever since the country launched 3G and 4G technology (Husian, 2017). Facebook ranks first as compared to other social media websites in this regard as there are over 30 million active Facebook users in the country as per PTA statistics. There were over 7.1 million users of Line, 3.9 million users of Instagram (Sachtv, 2018). The total number of Twitter users comprised 3.1 million, and that of Snapchat comprised 0.4 million. There are diverse purposes for which social media is used in Pakistan, including socio-political discussions, e-commerce, political rallying, and social vigilantism (Appen, 2018). One of the reasons that social media users are increasing in number in the country is due to the success of 3G and 4G internet technology in the country. There are over 37 million subscribers of broadband in the country (Dody, 2017). It shows an excellent opportunity for SMEs to adopt effective social media marketing strategies to get the advantage of increasing social media trends in Pakistan.

Figure 1: E-commerce prospects in Pakistan

Source: Aurora (2017)

The complete media stats list in the country is shown below:

- As of 1st January 2017, there are over 0.4 million users of Snapchat
- There are over 7.1 million users of LINE Messenger as of 15th October 2016

- There are over 3.1 million users of Twitter as of July/August 2016
- There are over 30 million users of Facebook as of 15th November 2016
- There are over 3.9 million users of Instagram by 2018.

Social media is increasingly becoming the most common way of interaction among people from across the globe. Tremendous growth is observed in Pakistan in the social media users as compared to the rest of the world. There are over 44 million social media accounts in Pakistan. The statistics have been shown with the help of data collected from different companies of social media (Samma tv, 2017). There are over 30 million users of Facebook, according to the figures released by PTA. One of the chief reasons that social media has penetrated deeply in Pakistan's population is due to the rise of 3G and 4G internet technology. It has brought social media applications and websites within the ordinary reach of people. Due to this technology, people can access social media through their Smartphones at the convenience of wherever they are.

Further, it is also important to note that the figures mentioned above are from 2016 and 2017. It can be said that these figures might have increased in the year 2018, given the rising trend (PTA, 2017). As social media are increasing with time, the company's social media activities are increasing in Pakistan, as the below figure shows the top 20 brands on social media in Pakistan (Socialbakers, 2018).

Social media has brought changes in communication between retailers and consumers by providing advanced technology for communication and marketing tools at a cheaper cost. Customers are more trusting of the information they acquired through social media related to products and services than the information delivered by firms through traditional media. Consumers' purchasing decisions, learning, sharing, and exchanging information are more dependent on the way consumers receive and react based on received information through social media sites. Companies are regularly using social media to communicate with their clients using platforms like Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, and social flicker. Social media is associated with many benefits such as it provides a database with that of social networks of potential customers providing an opportunity to harness related and relevant information. The information obtained through social media platforms can achieve multiple objectives like new product development, market segmentation, customer feedback, etc. Social media marketing describes a situation where one consumer's shopping experience leads to an exchange of words on social media with other people converting others into consumers. SMEs businesses are

exploiting these tools by investing incredible sources and opinion leaders. Marketing management and practical online marketing tools are helpful in the prevention of failure on the part of small businesses which can lead to the strengthening of the economy.

Figure 2: Statistics of Top 20 brands on social media in Pakistan

Source: Socialbakers, (2018)

Figure 3: Top 5 Industries on Facebook

Source: Socialbakers, (2018)

Small businesses must increase their presence on social media to maintain their competitiveness in the market. Large firms are increasingly using social media to outsmart other companies for increasing their market share (Cheng *et al.*, 2016). These benefits involve increased effectiveness of marketing, increased level of customer satisfaction, reduced travel

costs, reduced marketing cost, and reduced cost of customer support (Shaltoni, 2017). If small business owners do not use social media, it may become impossible for them to compete with larger firms on the marketing end. They can easily reap the benefits of marketing through social media (Guha *et al.*, 2018). The business owners of small firms risk losing their business by being absent on social media. Some studies have been conducted outside Pakistan concerning small business owners. It is imperative to identify the barriers to adopting social media marketing so that marketing strategies can be devised (Dutot and Bergeron, 2016).

However, the reasons have clearly not been understood by researchers to the factors which are posing as barriers for small businesses from the aspect of social media. Therefore, there is a need to clearly understand the barriers of utilizing social media in Pakistan because it has been discussed above that there is an increasing trend of social media users at the same time the brands marketing activities are also increasing on social media platforms. There is also a need to understand the role played by social media marketing for enhancing the profitability of small businesses in Pakistan.

It shows that there is a lack of literature on social media marketing strategies in the context of Pakistani small businesses that would guide them to improve their sustainability and profitability through improving social media marketing strategies. When owners of small businesses in Pakistan identify barriers to change, they will be ready to address those barriers as well. Small businesses can better devise social media marketing strategies when they can identify the challenges and barriers faced by them to social media marketing. Small businesses can be competitive when they adopt a social media marketing strategy, thereby adding to the stability of small businesses (Ainin *et al.*, 2015). Social media can be a source of economic growth for small businesses, thereby increasing their overall financial performance.

2.8. Comparison between Traditional and social media marketing

The table below shows the basic comparisons between Traditional and Social media marketing.

Traditional marketing	Social media marketing
Attracts public with visual commercials.	Provides entertainment to users of social networking websites with information and special offers.
Traditional media can be costly from marketing aspect.	Social media on the other hand is less expensive.

Nothing is free of cost on traditional marketing.	Social media setting up free accounts on famous platforms such as facebook, Instagram and twitter etc.
The traditional media, fails in the provision of accurate methods to analyse the performance and success of their marketing efforts.	The advertising cost on Facebook is low, whereby the companies get the opportunity for distributing the advertisements to desired segments. With customers feedback and reviews company can analyse the success of their organisational marketing efforts.
The audience of traditional media is generally vast. It can cause the delivery of an advertisement to an irrelevant audience. It can also causes a lower ROI.	There is a highly responsive and active community on social media platforms.
Traditional media does not facilitate the customers in having communication platform with them.	Social media is also helpful for consumers as it provides the method of direct communication to the customers and contributes towards the development of the brand image.

Social media marketing is also referred to as inbound marketing as it is aimed at attracting users of social networking websites to provide entertainment, value, information, special offers, etc. The prime examples of social media marketing comprise search engine optimization, blogs, and social networks, even though many people still regard social media as comprising social networking marketing only. Traditional media can be quite costly from the aspect of marketing (Bruhn *et al.*, 2012; Stefanone *et al.*, 2010; Zhao *et al.*, 2011). The average cost of a time slot in 30 seconds during a broadcast is above \$1200. It can be a hefty cost to bear for marketing purposes for smaller firms, and it carries risk with it as well. Social media marketing, on the other hand, is less expensive than traditional media marketing (Bruhn *et al.*, 2012; Stefanone *et al.*, 2010; Zhao *et al.*, 2011). A firm only must pay a fraction of the price for reaching the same number of people they desire to reach.

The metric which is employed in the current research comprises Cost-Per-Thousand Impressions (CPM) (Stefanone *et al.*, 2010; Zhao *et al.*, 2011). The CPM in an instance involving social media is less than \$3, that of radio is around \$10, and that for television is staggering \$28. Another vital thing to note is that social media marketing involves setting up a free account on prominent platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter (Stefanone *et al.*, 2010; Zhao *et al.*, 2011). The advertising cost on Facebook is low, whereby the companies get the opportunity for distributing the advertisements to desired segments. The traditional

media, on the other hand, fails in the provision of accurate methods to analyse the performance and success of any effort of marketing.

In contrast, those organizations which are advertising online are reaping data-driven and actual benefits about how the marketing efforts can be planned (Bruhn *et al.*, 2012). The marketers can get rich data from Google about the performance of any online advertisement. There is a highly responsive and active community on social media platforms. There are over 890 million active users on Facebook every single day. It makes it easier for firms to choose their ideal target market. The audience of traditional media is generally vast. It can cause the delivery of an advertisement to an irrelevant audience. It also causes a lower ROI. However, social media, on the other hand, provides a method for advertisers for accurate targeting of a relevant audience.

Social media is also helpful for consumers as it provides the method of direct communication to the customers and contributes towards the development of the brand image. The social media users are likely to catch the message which the marketer is projecting through the social media marketing campaign. For example, if the intended group of target market comprises students, then the marketer can update the settings in advertisement settings and project the message with lucrative offers. They can also interact with the firm's representative online on social media and with other customers, and thus two-way communication is established (Stefanone *et al.*, 2010; Zhao *et al.*, 2011). This type of communication creates a buzz and is also helpful in generating insight for the company into the thoughts of the customers. Traditional media, on the other hand, involves highly complex organizing, allocating, and executing. To do this effectively, it is not only vital to have a generous budget but also that employees possess significant expertise. However, consumers also intend to welcome those campaigns in which they have the role to play as well. Traditional media does not facilitate the customers in this regard. It can be stated that social media projects the advertisement to consumers with laser precision. With the help of social media marketing, the content is created so that customers or users can be engaged as well. The focus of traditional marketing is on cultivating trust over a more extended period. Social media does the same in a relatively shorter period by giving customers quick engagement with the advertising firm (Stefanone *et al.*, 2010; Zhao *et al.*, 2011).

2.8.1. E-Tailing and its significance for SMEs

Various benefits are associated with this model for offering to business owners but integrating both such methods can also be challenging. Experts of marketing pointed out channel conflict, which can arise concerning utilizing bricks and clicks model of conducting business.

The SMEs are also increasing their business presence with the help of social media marketing. Social networking sites (SNS) are increasingly recognizing the need for small and medium-sized firms to project their message to the audience. These sites are facilitating the SMEs to target audiences at a global level within a shorter budget. Further, SMEs can connect and interact with their consumers free of cost by making a profile on SNS. The e-retailers are also increasing their presence on social networking sites as they have created business profiles and offer products on social media websites. Studies highlight the significant rise of e-retail that SNS will increase the business online and it will promote the connection and interaction between consumer and businesses (Chen, and Leteney, 2000; Harris, and Dennis, 2011; Öztamur and Karakadılar, 2014). The prospects are equally promising for businesses dealing with touch-and-feel products. The e-retail sector has revolutionized the business and marketing prospects for SMEs due to SNS. The advancement in information technologies has positively influenced the business sector, and the prospects are promising for SMEs. E-retailing is essential for online branding as well (Harris and Dennis, 2011; Öztamur and Karakadılar, 2014).

Currently, researchers, marketing managers, and business leaders are exploring for inventive ways to utilize online business models and e-business technologies for business purposes. These latest e-business models and technologies have changed the pace, speed, and way of communication. Practitioners and academics have reported that the advent and rise of brick and click business model has been brought a considerable shift in ways of doing business as well as business practices (Bertrandie and Zielke, 2017). The brick and click model addressed needs to every type of customers like a person who wants to see the quality of the product before purchase or the person who feels comfortable by shopping online and getting the order delivered when it suits him/her (Bertrandie and Zielke, 2017). However, experts of marketing pointed out that channel conflict can create challenges in utilizing bricks and clicks model of conducting business effectively. A study has been highlighted that 98% of internet users are dissatisfied with the internet speed and only 2-percent of internet users purchased online items in Pakistan (Ahmad, 2018). They also argued that 99-percent of people felt insecure by using

the e-transaction method during online shopping. A company (draz.pk) has launched an e-commerce business and introduced the concept of Black Friday (Friday is a holy day in Islam) in Pakistan, which was unsuccessful due to hurting religious beliefs and values. It is also found that some e-commerce businesses have a limited focus on customer service, video marketing, mobile-friendly interface, and personalization. Furthermore, these businesses are unable to understand the dynamics of online advertising work as well as over-obsession with SEO (Ahmad 2018; Majid and Yasir, 2017; Saeed and Sameer, 2015). On the other hand, customers have experienced many flaws in online shopping such as low level of quality of products, higher prices for a lower level of quality of products, dissatisfied customer service, risky and uncomfortable payment methods, and afraid of counterfeit products (Ahmad 2018; Chong *et al.*, 2018).

Customer tracking capabilities, low overhead, execution speed, IT infrastructure, and network commerce model. Customers are increasingly becoming smarter in employing e-tailer for comparison and convenience shopping. E-tailing comprises the subset of e-commerce that captures all commerce taking place through the internet (Harris and Dennis, 2011; Chen and Leteney, 2000). It represents that part of e-commerce which includes the sale of product merchandise and does not involve service sales such as airline tickets, railway tickets, job portals, etc. Internet retailing or e-tailing represents the new format of the store in retailing (Gera and Gu, 2004; Harris, and Dennis, 2011; Chen and Leteney, 2000). E-tailer can also be regarded as pure-play or bricks and clicks business. Bricks and clicks business has both physical and online presence in the market.

The pure e-tailer, on the other hand, only has an online presence for selling the goods. Pure e-tailing represents the most exciting opportunities for the future as they are all engaged in internet selling and do not have to bear the maintenance cost of maintaining the bricks store. The prominent features of e-tailing involve quick interaction with business and customers, speed, networking with suppliers, and link in the value chain (Gera and Gu, 2004; Harris and Dennis, 2011; Chen and Leteney, 2000). These e-trailers cover many niches, and their products are also increasingly innovative, which it is difficult to find replica elsewhere (Chen and Leteney, 2000; Delayco and Walcutt, 2010). The internet has brought the level playing field as SMEs can now compete in the global market against big firms by projecting their products and services to a broad audience across the borders through SNS (Chong *et al.*, 2018). The e-tail sector has also received pace in growth due to recession whereby businesses are focusing on increasing their presence but overcoming their cost of maintenance or cost of expansion. Tuten

Solomon, (2013) argued that over the next years the global online sales would continue to increase at least by 10% in each successive year.

More e-trailers mean that more competitive offerings will be brought in for customers. The benefits of e-tailing comprise ease of communication between consumer and company (Chen and Leteney, 2000). Other benefits of e-tailing comprise the fewer requirements concerning infrastructure, convenient setup, wider reach to the audience, and ease of access. It enables SMEs to grow their sales volume. E-tailing also provides consumers with convenient access to information related to different promotions, offerings, comparison with competitors' items, and a high level of anonymity and privacy. However, several issues are also arising in e-tailing. One of the significant operational issues is the extent of information to be projected to the customer (Chen and Leteney, 2000). Further, the shipping cost can also be higher for international deliveries, and that the distribution network and system should be highly efficient. The critical factor in this regard is the distribution efficiency as it overcomes the risk of shipment losses and fraudulent claims.

2.8.2. E-Service quality and its significance for SMEs

The concept of service quality is widely being researched in management and business literature and in-service marketing literature. There are two schools of thought related to service quality: the European school of thought and North American school of thought. Former is led by Christian Gronroos and later by Parasuraman and his colleagues. The commonality between both these is that they regard service quality as a multi-dimensional construct. However, Gronroos believes that there are two main dimensions of service quality as it comprises the technical dimension and a functional dimension. The technical dimension is related to outcomes, whereas the functional dimension is related to processes. The technical dimension involves the outcome which the customer gets when they interact with the business, whereas the functional dimension involves the perception among customers about the service they receive (Gronroos, 2000). (Parasuraman *et al.*, 1985), on the other hand, believed that service quality involved more than just the outcome. It also involves the manner of delivery of service.

Nevertheless, both schools of thought made an extensive focus on the process aspect of the quality of services. They accommodated the perception near customers about the quality of service to measure the dimension. (Parasuraman *et al.*, 1985) developed a scale for measuring

the service quality called SERVQUAL. This scale is employed across a wide range of service industries. But various researchers have also questioned the applicability of this generic instrument. It has been argued that the instrument employed in one market should not be employed for the other market.

Due to this reason, SERVQUAL has been modified and added into overtime by different researchers according to their research so that it can adjust to different settings (Hassan *et al.*, 2015). Even though the North American school of thought gained more attention in the literature of service marketing, there is still no consensus on whether which side has concrete evidence to the exclusion of the other. In literature, the evidence is abundant for the reconciliation of both concepts. McDougall and Levesque, (2000) differentiated between relational service quality and core service quality and in the context of four service types: dental services, restaurant services, auto services, and hairstylist services. Both quality dimensions were employed in the context of customer satisfaction. Service quality, as perceived by customers, is generally regarded as resulting from how okay expectations of customers are being met by actual performance and experiences. Social commerce has generally combined with e-commerce due to Web 2.0, which is also employed by social media websites. As of 2011, at least 83% of the Fortune 500 companies were relying on social media for one business reason or the other so that they can stay connected with their customers (Flanigan and Obermier, 2016). (Parasuraman *et al.* 2005) observed that two distinct scales could be employed to capture the service quality: E-S-QUAL and E-RecS-QUAL. E-S-QUAL scale comprises efficiency, system availability, fulfilment, and privacy. Later Wolfinbarger and Gilly (2003) employed SQ dimensions: fulfilment, website design, security, reliability, customer services, and privacy.

E-service quality may be described as an overall evaluation by a customer about the quality and excellence of the delivery of e-service in the virtual marketplace (Lee and Lin, 2005). There are five dimensions of e-service quality, as identified by Barnes and Vidgen (2002). These include design, usability, trust, information, and empathy. Usability is related to ease of use, appearance, and navigation, and the image developed by the consumer about the service. The design represents aesthetics and appearance. Information is related to the appropriateness of the information for the user. Trust represents the safe transactions; reputation and that the personal information of the user is safe and secure. Empathy represents the community, communication, and personalization. Santos (2003) highlighted various determinants of e-service quality. These comprise the appearance, ease of use, structure, linkage, content, layout,

efficiency, reliability, communication, support, incentive, and security. Raman *et al.*, (2008) recommended six dimensions of service quality such as appearance, ease of usage, customization, reliability, incentive, and communication.

Nowadays, SMEs are focused on outsourcing the IS functions to enhance the e-SQ. It is also found that e-SQ expectations are different from SMEs and other large organizations which are following the brick-and-mortar business model. It is also found that e-SQ has a statistically significant connection between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty (Chang *et al.*, 2010). Some researchers have also highlighted that e-SQ has become an essential factor in gaining high profitability and competitive advantages in SME businesses (Chang *et al.*, 2010). E-SQ is helpful to improve the products and services according to need, want, demand of customers especially in SMEs businesses (Chang *et al.*, 2010). A recent study has indicated that SME's performance and competitive advantages are enormously dependent on e-SQ SMEs need to enhance the quality of their products and services by using the latest technologies and achieve e-SQ reviews.

2.9. Social media technology use

At present, executives, researchers, consultants, and decision-makers are increasingly focusing on searching for new ways to harness social media tools for business purposes (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). Applications for social media have introduced new tools for the customer-centric approach that enables the business to make their customer able to interact with them and become the member of their social network (Kietzmann, Hermkens, McCarthy, and Silvestre, 2011). Here are some examples of social media applications and their use for CRM as discussion forums, blogs, user-generated content sites, and user-created communities. In specific, the list includes Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter and these critical applications have completely changed the approach for CRM from Customer-specific (a communication tool for peer-to-peer) to tools of customer-centric that has enabled the business to interact with their customers who are part of their online social network (Trainor, 2012). Agnihotri *et al.*, (2012) have stated that organizations can utilize the potential of these technologies to get access to the information of customer through direct interaction between customer and organization or an indirect interaction through customer-customer communication or interaction. This study is based on four functional blocks of social media technology use, and Kietzmann *et al.* describe these blocks., (2011) and it is specific to the use for CRM; conversations, sharing, groups and relationships.

Sharing block of social media technology has been referred to as a support for users to distribute, exchange, and receive related product/organization content (i.e., text, coupons, pins on Pinterest, images, and videos, and so on). This block is like the information reciprocity concept as it includes the processes and activities that boost customer encouragement for the company and personal information sharing and interaction with the company and other customers and it has a positive influence on the ability of a business to manage their customer relationships (Kirca *et al.*, 2005). Further, conversations block represents supporting social media technologies for an organization to develop an interactive dialogue with customers and between customers (i.e., status updates on Facebook, blogs, discussion forums, and Twitter) to gather information of customers from the dialogues. Moreover, relationships refer to social media technologies that enable organizations and customers to develop and build association networks with other users (i.e., LinkedIn, Facebook, Yammer, Ning, etc.) and allows to utilize the information for the network by organizations (Trainor, 2012).

Fourth fundamental block of social media technologies is ‘groups’ that supports online user community development catered on specific brands, topic, and products, i.e., idea force, Salesforce, and application software of Igloo’s customer community. Firms use these technologies to get access to valuable customer-related information including complaints, requirements, and experiences that are discussed between customers on applications of social networking, i.e., online communities, blogs, and discussion forums (Trainor, 2012). Additionally, these social media technology blocks develop online support communities that help organizations to develop a network of interaction with customers to solve problems for support encounter during service delivery and creating and distributing information of interaction to the concerned departments of business (Trainor, 2012). He discussed that effectiveness of the sales force of a business can be increased through efficient use of social media technologies as it provides understanding for the social networking between the company and its customers (Trainor, 2012).

Studies have found that there has been a significant role of information technology in customer relationship management (CRM) (Chang *et al.*, 2010; Kirca *et al.*, 2005; Trainor *et al.*, 2014). The literature on CRM has described that most of the information technology is aimed to automate the process of information among company staff within the internal staff like a salesperson and external stakeholders like customers, i.e., technologies like interactive voice response systems, e-mail, customer analytics system, automation of sales force and database marketing. Ahearne *et al.*, (2007) have explained that the technology used in CRM has been

described as a tool for marketing and sales of a business to improve and enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of employees. Further researchers have defined CRM technology as the level of usage of supporting IT by firms to manage the relationship with their customers (Chang *et al.*, 2010). Relevance has been identified in the definition with past studies even though past researchers did not examine the role of new technology to support social interaction and it is because that these technologies have been introduced in recent times in organizational settings (Trainor, 2012).

Most of the previous research is claiming the benefits of networking regarding business. In this era, small and medium-size organizations are called the economic engine. Roberts and Grover (2012) discussed the adoption of social media and its benefits, along with barriers for SMEs.

Nowadays, customers are gathering information from social media platforms related to brands so that they can make a purchase decision based on information from a neutral source (Michaelidou *et al.*, 2011). Information technology has empowered consumers to assume the role of active information generator from merely passive receivers. The companies continuously identify target consumers for selling their products using social media tools. Targeted consumer identification helps share information, creating positive word of mouth, and designing marketing strategies. Credit goes to social media because consumers can exercise control, accessing a high multitude of information and exhibiting control over consumption (Hoffman and Fodor, 2010). Companies are in constant use of social media to communicate their clients using platforms like Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, and social flicker. Such companies or organizations or private entities are using such platforms as sponsors for celebrities who can create positive word of mouth for the offered services and products.

Consumer reviews posted online are equivalent to a 'sales assistant' as they are engaging customers in a discussion about the pros and cons of different products and services which best match their needs. Such reviews have been utilized for forecasting sales. It found that online consumer reviews should be credible, and their credibility may be questioned as some websites use such reviews for remuneration purposes. Roberts (2015) pointed out the type of legal action taken by Amazon against those who posted feedback for money on the website. Certain features relate to the credibility of UGC. These include the comprehensiveness, length, quality of argument, valence, style of review, and relevance of content. The standard of the content was the most crucial element which influenced perceptions of products or services. The length of the review was also found to have positively influenced consumers. However, the personal

expertise of the customer did not add to the credibility of the review. The purchase intention of consumers is influenced by message valence amongst amateur consumers of cameras, but not amongst expert consumers. Consumers are empowered by social media to express their dissatisfaction with products or services. Some websites represent a step further and house those reviews which, instead of showing displeasure with a 'bad' product or service have taken an 'anti' step or boycott measures. However, such information might be influential for consumers who are about to arrive at a purchasing decision about a product or service. The credibility of the brand is enhanced because of pictures and videos which people share online and which the brand features on its website and social media channels. It enhances the credibility of the brand and influences other social media users to start using the services of the brand.

The increased significance associated with social media has done small businesses on active heels, but they need to follow professional lines to modernize their practices. In case they disarray, small businesses can face serious marketing threats (Michaelidou *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, with the influx of smartphones, the use of social media has undergone a tremendous rise that empowers users to watch and operate content on their respective smartphone sets. Moreover, the generation of videos, scripts, and picture content is possible through this. Subsequently, every user gets the capacity to generate content where he feels weak business side, for instance, low quality of hotel sanitation, unclean community swimming pool like bad business reputation can prove fatal for the small business. Internet exhibits such reviews as a big hit as Charlesworth, (2014) concluded that such users bear a good reputation and others show trust in their reviews. The research found that in many cases, it becomes imperative for the organizations that carry out online marketing to remain in touch with the online discussions. It is important that organizations can interact with the followers of their online discussion forums to develop 2-way communication and keep the process going (Ismail, 2017). The point is to mention that an organization can keep abreast with ethical as well as legal dimensions of communicating with customers (Chaffey, 2015; Ryan, 2014). There is another aspect that responding to each comment of the user can prove risky and culminating in igniting an uncontrollable debate (Ryan and Jones, 2010). It occurs at times when the organizations do not have the required expertise relating to social media-based marketing (Chaffey, 2015). The uncontrolled debates can result in reputational loss before customers. The Consumer Protection from Unfair Trading Regulations (2008) in the European Union protects the argumentation with online customers and takes it as an offence as enunciated in the above

regulations. It emphasizes competency development in the social media field of marketing that offers an experimental approach that can sufficiently block the generation of undesirable results (Charlesworth, 2014). Charlesworth (2014) forwards a compelling argument that social media not only connects but enables sharing experiences that already existed (Charlesworth, 2014). Because in any case of raising voice online and offline carry the same status on social media (Ryan, 2014). Due to social networking applications, consumers are more capable of providing their reviews related to brands so that brands can modify products or services according to the need, demand, and requirements of their consumers (Parkin, 2009).

2.10. Marketing Capabilities

Capability based perspective and the resource-based view serve the theoretical foundation in the research. The common thing is that both perspectives determine a firm power as its resources and effective use of resources which have the potential to positively impact the company's capabilities (Vorhies *et al.*, 2011). Krush *et al.*, (2015) claimed that a firm resource represents its assets and its knowledge as well as its business process. On the other hand, the capabilities of the organization are all about assembled and deployment of resources. The coordination of these skills, resources, and capabilities helps the organization to get a competitive edge (Lamberton and Stephen, 2016). Giannikas *et al.*, (2019) are considered the marketing pioneers and they also claimed that only resources are not sufficient for organizational success so for the significant organizational performance organizational resources need to transform in capabilities and competencies, so this combination helps to yield the organizational performance improvement. According to Pekovic and Rolland, (2016), organizational performance improved when distinctive capabilities are created through deployed technological resources and organizational resources.

2.10.1. Defining Marketing Capabilities

Organizations are focused on designing strategies that could help them improve their performance. Hence, the resource-based view mostly focuses on internal and external firm's capabilities that can generate a sustainable competitive advantage for the organizations. Marketing capabilities are effective techniques under the marketing business functions that can help support the achievement of desired organizational objectives. As per Hanssens and Pauwels, (2016) marketing capabilities consists of three broad-groups (i) outside-in capabilities, which is related to the channel bonding and market sensing, (ii) inside-out capabilities, which is related to logistics and development of technology, (iii) capabilities

approaching both the aspects such as product development and customer order fulfilment. Vorhies, Orr and Bush, (2011) have a view that marketing capabilities are strongly related to competitive advantage. Krush et al.,(2015) assert the fact that marketing capabilities have a positive influence on organizational performance.

2.10.2. Marketing Capabilities and Organizational Performance link

Researchers have emphasized capabilities over resources in terms of potential impact and relevance to the performance of the organization (Newbert, 2007). The only use of resources cannot bring required outcomes; these are the capabilities that enable to use of resources effectively. Further, studies have predominantly focused on marketing capabilities in terms of capabilities of customer linking and market sensing (Day, 1994). So, the literature on marketing capabilities has endorsed the importance and relevance of the topic for developing an understanding of the performance and strategy of the organization. In the seminal marketing strategy review, it has been proposed that there is a need to deploy marketing resources through significant capabilities to create a competitive advantage.

Additionally, the review of these researchers referred to intangible assets of marketing (capabilities) like customer and brand equity. Consecutive studies by Berthon et al., (2008) have given two critical suggestions to the organizations to move forward in marketing strategic planning implementation is the marketing capabilities that are referred to as the resource-based theory for strategic marketing. Secondly, marketing capabilities link with the performance. This insight provides a guide for the current study to develop a theoretical foundation that links support marketing capabilities to the marketing capabilities and then to the overall performance of marketing.

In terms of empirical outcomes of studies for marketing, capabilities that contribute to the overall organizational performance are limited. Past studies have described the marketing capabilities' role in two specific situations called horizontal acquisitions and economic crisis management (Capron and HULLAND, 1999). Further, studies have provided a more general view of marketing capabilities' contribution to the organizational performance that is categorized into two approaches. First, the early literature on the topic conceptualized the capabilities of marketing in terms of supporting strategies for processes of mid-level marketing and included the elements of the marketing mix, market management, and market research (Vorhies and Morgan, 2005). For this approach, studies found limitations that it does not include any higher-level assessment for integrative capabilities like innovation, brand management, and customer

relationship management that is the second approach (Vorhies and Morgan, 2005). These researchers have raised questions to be answered in future studies. In the same year, another study built preliminary work to provide an evaluation of different higher-level capabilities of marketing, including customer relationship marketing, brand reputation, and innovation.

A meta-analysis has been provided by Krasnikov and Jayachandran, (2008) to demonstrate the relationship between organizational performance and marketing capabilities. However, the reassurance of these findings in terms of the first approach of marketing capabilities is the sum of different activities of mid-level marketing. In terms of comparison of marketing capabilities there are limited research pieces of evidence since the evaluation of two higher-level capabilities of marketing comparison by Hooley *et al.*, (2005) has been done with a focus on capabilities of mid-level marketing (Krasnikov and Jayachandran, 2008; Vorhies and Morgan 2005).

Kaplan and Mazurek, (2018) designed two ways in terms of marketing ways that can help organizations to move forward first is emphasizing marketing capabilities which are usually referred to as marketing strategy through resource-based theory and the second way is to create a link in capabilities as well as marketing performance. Different research explored the contribution of marketing capabilities primarily studies done by Giannikas *et al.*, (2019) describe that marketing capabilities can play their role in two precise manners first is a horizontal acquisition which helps the organization to manage the economic crisis.

Wu *et al.*, (2010) stated that there is limited research are found on the marketing capabilities, especially those who evaluate or assess the higher-level marketing capabilities. In contrast, it is a very crucial factor to assess the organizational success in the perspective of marketing because in terms of resource-based view capabilities are crucial as compared to only resources. According to resource-based view literature most of the organizational capabilities can identify through core determinants of business performance, and these core determinants are more helpful to achieve a competitive edge in the market (Tiago and Veríssimo, 2014). At the same time, resource-based view theory suggests that technology, marketing, and other operational capabilities are some crucial capabilities of an organization that contribute a vital role in organizational success (Vorhies and Morgan, 2005). The existing literature is depicting that major decisive drivers of firm performance are marketing capabilities which are helping to enhance the financial position of the organization (Felix *et al.*, 2017). That is why, according to VRIO analysis, marketing capabilities are valuable, inimitable, rare, and non-substituted

(Malthouse *et al.*, 2013). Kamasak, (2017) suggested that firms with successful marketing capabilities can develop sustainable growth in the market through competitive advantage and an increase in organizational performance.

2.10.3. Branding Capability

Another critical capability of higher-level marketing is the potential to identify the performance of marketing and in the field of business to business, and studies have identified branding benefits (Kim *et al.*, 1998). Further, the in context of business to business, branding has been emphasized by Michell *et al.*, 2001, Bendixen *et al.*, 2004 and Van Riel *et al.*, 2005. Recent approaches have been developed for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) as in past branding was considered as an element of marketing strategies for only large businesses; therefore, there has been little research undertaken in the context of SME's branding. Research for the branding of SMEs is not older than the past two decades (Berthon *et al.*, 2008). These studies indicated the importance of branding for SMEs and the role of this marketing capability for the performance of small businesses.

It is essential to study and discuss the link between marketing capabilities and the performance of marketing. Still, there is also essential for the explanation of leading mechanism to create, develop and manage capabilities of marketing. It shows the importance of defined capabilities mix in terms of creating and developing marketing capabilities that are the process of creating capabilities from other capabilities. Perry *et al.*, (1993) have provided a useful exposition of link and inter-dependence of capabilities with each other. Firstly, they distinguished the core capabilities that directly create or enable a firm for building competitive advantage and secondly the support capabilities of value addition and these are the facilities for core capabilities. Thirdly there are essential capabilities that are not required to create an advantage and facilitate the activities that create competitive advantage but should be acquired by the firm to continue their business operations. In the context of this study, marketing capabilities are considered as core capabilities to identify the direct influence of capabilities on marketing performance.

2.10.4. Innovation Capability

Innovation is the result of organizational processes that are governed and directed by different leadership styles, transformational most likely; however, other leadership styles can also support innovation. In considerable organization management innovation is referred to the adoption and such processes and practices that are new to companies and break the status quo

(Hecker and Ganter, 2013). The change management experts argue that traditionally organizations were reluctant to adopt new forms and used to operate in their way for long. However, with the current wave of digitalization and the advent of new technology and business forms, innovation has now become the fundamental need for any organization (Nieves and Segarra-Cipres, 2015).

Hollen, Van Den Bosch and Volberda, (2013) argues that new process adoption affects organizational performance in terms of innovation productivity and enhances its competitiveness. The departure from traditional business processes, structures, and techniques can be achieved by adapting the risk-taking approach and adding innovation into organizational culture (Hecker and Ganter, 2013). Changes in the structures, working routines, processes, and techniques lead to attaining competitive advantage given the innovation is competitive, hard to imitate, and ambiguous plus complex (Nieves and Segarra-Cipres, 2015).

The innovation capability of management or leadership style is different from product innovation due to distinct characteristics. Management innovations are primarily aimed to enhance the operational efficiency and effectiveness of the organization, whereas the innovation of products and services improves the standard and quality of the products and is from the customers' perspective. However, Hollen *et al.*, (2013) argue that innovation capability in the management perspective leads to the innovation of the product. Adaption of new technology and business forms helps organizations to become robust and develop processes that are not replicated easily and hence. Organizational enjoys a competitive advantage that is sustainable and drives higher revenues and profits for the business.

Various variables can be considered as potential factors for consideration of capabilities of marketing support as the two specific support capabilities are named market management and orientation capabilities. The literature of the field has strongly supported the nexus between innovation and market orientation (Han *et al.*, 1998). More studies have found that there is a basis for the relationship between innovation and market orientation (Han *et al.*, 1998). These researchers have argued that it essential to have a market orientation in the context of business philosophy as it provides a culture that brings innovation through operationalization in related departments to have the required impact of these capabilities on performance. Ideal, market orientation culture has been aligned by innovation, and various studies have found the relationship between innovation and market orientation, and others did not find any proven link

between the two (Brooksbank and Taylor, 2002). These researchers have suggested for future researchers to find a link between market intelligence and more incredible innovation.

Managers of the organization play a vital role in the implementation and practice of management innovation. The non-technological characteristics of management innovation make it a hard sell for business management; however, it can be created and embedded in organizational culture by motivating and encouraging business managers to develop innovation capabilities that can be trickled down to the middle and lower tier of organizational employees (Hecker and Ganter, 2013).

Organizational structure plays an essential role in the dissemination of innovative thoughts and hence, generates capability among the employees (Nieves and Segarra-Cipres, 2015). As per Hecker and Ganter, (2013) mechanistic structures are more likely to foster administrative innovation. Wright et al., (2012) assert that the administrative intensity and size of the company serve as essential features for administrative innovation. Wu et al., (2010) noted that the size of the organization, the way assets are used, and the services in addition to employee qualifications influence management innovation. In the context of having innovation embedded culture, transactional and transformation leadership is highly valuable (Vaccaro *et al.*, 2012). Such leaders are prone to understand the technological advancements across the globe and are more likely to adopt change and lead their team to adapt to the change management processes. Therefore, these leadership styles are highly likely and associate with management innovation capability.

Small and medium-sized companies usually lack developed and established business processes and organizational structures (Vorhies *et al.*, 2011). As per Hollen *et al.*, (2013), the conceptual model of management innovation is challenging to find in small and micro companies as most of the business decisions are linked to the top-management approvals. In such a scenario, the role of leadership style is highly influential in management innovation capability. Similarly, the qualification of employees also serves an essential part in the adaption of innovation culture in the organization (Zafar and Mustafa, 2017). Highly qualified employees have strong intellectual and analytical capabilities with a broader knowledge base that supports the innovation processes and culture in the organization.

The way of thinking and intercepting information by the individual working for the organization results in management innovation (Ngai *et al.*, 2015). As per Papachristodoulou *et al.*, (2017) Small and medium enterprises, despite centralized power structures should focus

on hiring quality and qualified resource with a mind-set of ‘right person for the right job’, which will ultimately help the company to develop managerial innovation ability (Bourlakis *et al.*, 2009). Management innovation is a concept that should be evaluated as a product of collective wisdom and is not a product of a single individual. Therefore, in small and medium enterprises this concept is rare to find, however, can be adapted and implemented with the right leadership approach and choices to select a qualified resource (Hollen *et al.*, 2013).

2.11. Customer Orientation

2.11.1. Defining Customer Orientation

Customer orientation of a firm refers to the level of information obtained and used by a firm from their customers to develop the strategy to meet the needs of their customers, and strategy implementation would be by responding to the needs of customers (i.e., understanding of firm of its target customers; Hult *et al.*, 2007;). Therefore, a customer-oriented firm is considered an organization that has placed their customers on high priority based on the current and future needs, and for that abilities of the firm are being advanced to sense trends and events in the base of their customers (customer sending) and responding to the acquired information (responsiveness of customers). Customer orientation is a result of continuous improvement of the firm for sensing their customer and firm responsiveness capabilities, and this has been viewed as a strategic asset of an organization (Foley and Fahy, 2009). There are more possibilities of outperformance of a firm that has strong customer orientation than their rivals in terms of a better understanding of the needs of their customers, adjusting service and product and demand forecasts (Theoharakis and Hooley, 2008).

2.11.2. Dynamic capability view

A useful conceptual lens has been provided by the dynamic capability theory of organization for understanding business sources for gaining competitive advantage and resource building, the configuration of strategic integration to respond to the marketplace changes and challenges (Eisenhardt and Martin, 2000; Teece *et al.*, 1997). The primary use of the dynamic capability theory is that it explains the change in inter-firm performance by use of capabilities of the firm to acquire and distribute resources in the process of matching organization with the marketplace (Teece *et al.*, 1997). Use of these capabilities requires an intricate pattern of coordination of knowledge and skills that have become fixed as the routine of organizations (Grant, 1996), and are implemented well than their rivals (Eisenhardt and Martin, 2000; Teece *et al.*, 1997; Foley and Fahy, 2009), and continued through all times despite rival’ attempt to imitate the

capabilities (Teece et al., 1997). It means that strategic asset processing may be fair, but firms must distribute assets in ways that match with the coordination of the market to acquire value in the marketplace for the firm. Customer orientation modelling and orientation for supply within the aspect of facilitating specific approach as the emphasis is to identify necessarily required capabilities by the firm to accrue value (Foley and Fahy, 2009). So, the given customer orientation of firm in presumed heterogeneity of business and orientation of business for supply, configuration, and distribution of skills in a firm would underlie the capabilities of strategic assets that could lead to high performance than rivals and has a contribution for performance superiority i.e., cost reductions, innovation and customer responsiveness (White et al., 2003).

2.11.3. Customer sensing

Customer sensing and responding strategies are now becoming more popular among marketers to understand and answer the customer need effectively (Krush *et al.*, 2015). Customer sensing allows marketers to forecast or predict the possible consumer response to the marketing campaign or strategy. Marketers also focus on customer sense to find out the misalignment of marketing communication with a consumer base. There are certain benefits that an organization can generate through adapting customer sensing and response strategy. For instance, Page *et al.*, (2018) assert that customer sensing understanding can help to understand the exact needs of the target consumers and hence, organisations can alter their production and service delivery strategy following the desired needs.

Further, Kamasak, (2017) added that consumer sensing also helps companies to reduce the marketing expenditure or to maximize the outcome of the marketing budget. By having detailed knowledge of consumer sensing and possible response, marketers would develop strategies that are very close or exactly matching what consumer wants to see and attain from the brand. Vorhies *et al.*, (2011) assert that it is highly likely that companies achieve high customer satisfaction when the marketing efforts are directed towards the consumer sensory needs and matches with their perception.

Organizations must gather information about the preferences and needs of their customers because these vary from customer to customer and segment to segment. Therefore, the gathered customers' need information would help the organization in the understanding of concerns of the customers and preferences in future and forecasting future trends (Feng *et al.*, 2015). Such information generation depends on different mechanisms like discussions and meeting with

trade partners, customers, analyses of customer surveys and sales reports. Studies have stated that there is a need for accurate and frequent contact between business and their customers as this interaction gives input for efficiency improvement and information for capturing market effectively (Feng *et al.*, 2015).

Kamasak, (2017) also argued that gathering data about customer perception is not an easy thing to do. It requires immense research and in-depth knowledge of the market where the target audience is identified, and data is gathered against the desired variable. Market research effectiveness is only possible if the target audience is recruited in the right manner. Further, it carries an immense cost for the companies to gather data about consumer perceptions, sensing and their inner needs. For retail companies, the existing distribution setup can play a vital role in data collection regarding customer sense. The retail partners can be engaged through an effective and professional marketing strategy to gather the data. Companies with professional marketing research services are also available that can provide support to the manufacturing organizations to gather right data at the right time hence, aiding the manufacturers in their product development processes (Tiago and Veríssimo, 2014).

2.11.4. Customer responsiveness

Financial performance of any organization is more likely to be the assessment of the factors, which is outside of the organization (Papachristodoulou *et al.*, 2017). For instance, Giannikas *et al.*, (2019) discussed that conventional performance indicators such as return on investment (ROI), market share, net income, present value, operational efficiency and after-sales support are some key variables or factors that lead to the assessment of firm's performance reflecting its ability to generate profitability by effectively utilizing essential resources. Bourlakis *et al.*, (2009) discussed the time-based performance indicators as an assessment of a firm's value chain performance. The value chain is driven from raw material to the delivery of the final product to the customer (Levy, 2013). Key dimensions include the delivery time, product quality and new product development. However, customer responsiveness is another essential factor that has been discussed as the part of the firm's agility and is considered an essential part of a time-based performance of the firm (Olenski, 2015).

Customer responsiveness is discussed by Baird and Parasnis, (2011) and defined the concept as the ability of the firm of being fast and accurate. The notion of 'right time with the right product at the right place' is highly suitable to be applied to the concept of customer responsiveness (Peterson and Crittenden, 2018). Being right means the customer gets the

product or service in a way that meets the expectations. The concept comes under the more extensive portfolio of customer orientation that is primarily associated with knowing the customers in the best possible manner and serving them rightly as per their perceptions (Feng et al., 2015). Giannikas *et al.*, (2019) noted that organizations that were good in market sensing were not so good at performing at a high level for the customer. There is a missing link, which Peterson and Crittenden, (2018) called or referred to as customer responsiveness. Organizational beliefs and values that are positively associated with customer responses are innovation, entrepreneurship and risk-taking. Hence, the theorists and marketers talked about the importance of flexible teams that are highly efficient and responsive, and this characteristic of executive teams directly influence customer responsiveness.

A firm can generate customer information, but until unless their response to the information, it can state that little has achieved in terms of information gathering and generation. Responding to the information gathered from customers to meet their needs is the responsiveness of the firm to the information. For this purpose, firms are required to educate, plan and communicate with related functional departments that provide the basis for shared concentrated actions (Giannikas *et al.*, 2019), that install the profile of customer orientation (Feng et al. 2015). Researchers have found that interactions with the customer by inter-organizational teams and customer relationship programs would lead to select the market for targeting, design of the product and its offering to the target set of customers to cater the identified needs of these customers those have been delivered by the firm (Feng *et al.*, 2015). So, the firms with the superiority of customer orientation are more likely to achieve performance superiority than their rivals because they have met the needs of customers with better understanding and delivery of their required product or service.

2.12. Brand Equity

2.12.1. What is Brand

Different theorists have defined the brand in different ways. Still, collectively all means one statement, and that says the brand is a combination of name, design, a symbol of a product of a particular company that provides differentiated and substantial advantages over the products offered by competitors (Brodie et al., 2013). Further, the term has also been defined as a combination of mental associations that customers have towards the product by the organization based on the perceived value of offered service or the product (Rosenbaum-Elliott, et al., 2015). These associations should be unique, lively and robust in terms of providing best

possible solutions or moving needs and want of the customers even though the term has been defined formally, the informal statement by theorists' states that branding is required to build an image of the product by a particular company (Jones and Bonevac, 2013). The image is meant to improve perceived product worth that will eventually increase brand value for the customer and leads to high brand loyalty.

2.12.2. Importance and Role of Brand

Every consumer perceives brand as a name in his/her mind that is characterized based on a noticeable symbol and name that differentiates product or service from competitor's products (Rosenbaum-Elliott et al., 2015). Further, Jones and Bonevac (2013) stated the consumer's perspective for the brand as they perceive brand a product that is of high quality and highly reliable. Additionally, consumer-like to purchase and consume the product with recognized brand names as they view it a highlighter of their personality through and in different contexts of situations (Brodie et al., 2013). These days, consumers are well-aware, and they have a comprehensive list of brands available in the market to choose from.

Further, it has been identified by studies that the emotions of consumers are one of the key determinants that influence the purchase decision and buying behaviour of customers. According to researchers of consumer shopping habits, almost one-fourth of the consumers are likely to have the influence of others or a brand for buying accessories and clothed (Albert and Merunka, 2013). Consumers have their choices at the time of making purchase decisions, but they would choose based on their preferences those are developed following brand perception. Jones and Bonevac (2013) stated that successful branding of a product makes the consumer aware of their presence that would most likely increase the buying chances of product or services of a particular company.

2.12.3. Conceptualizing Brand Equity

Brand Equity term has been defined as the set of liabilities and assets associated with a brand, and the associations include symbol and name of the brand that could determine effects of product value (Buil et al., 2013). Further added to this point by (Zhang, 2015), brand equity enables the company to signify the differentiated marketing effects on the brand. Brand Equity's positive side concern happens when consumers want to pay more for similar product quality just because of the brand image and name of the product. However, the equity of the brand would be ruined if the brand manager fails to manage it properly (Heding et al., 2015). For example, low customer services of product quality would damage the brand image and would

lead to a decrease in overall sales of company' products. Luxton, Reid and Mavondo (2015) further argued this point, that brand equity is a multi-faced and complex concept like it requires capturing customers through a set of measures instead of using only one measure. The typical example quoted to stated brand as equity for a company is the imposition of law for implementing intellectual property rights.

States with highly established legislative system define brand value for both the producer and the consumer. To deal with piracy of product or brand, many countries have established laws to protect patent, trademarks, copyrights and patents of the product (Conley et al., 2013). Furthermore, brand equity allows the company to earn higher margins by applying a premium pricing strategy and less reliance on promotional activities. Owing to the image of the brand, customers would not focus on the short-term promotional activities of the firm but the whole brand. Concept of brand equity has been stated as a broader area that has been further divided into four categories or areas including name awareness, brand loyalty, brand association and perceived quality (Buil et al., 2013).

Additionally, the brand has also been defined as a tradable product that has financially measurable value and the selected measures been required to be aligned with the vision of the brand. It is identified that the instability of the stock market is likely to be affected because of the purchasing behaviour of consumers not depending upon the decline or growth of retail sales. The view of brand equity has supported this point as it depends on the number of regular purchasers of the brand (Heding et al., 2015).

2.12.4. Brand Awareness

It is one of the vital brand equities' determinants that refer to the consumers' ability to recognize and recall the brand and ability to link the brand with the corresponding product category (Huang and Sarigollu, 2012). Brand Awareness level lies in a continuum, with recognition of brand being the first name and lowest level brand with the highest level but unaided recall. Moreover, the key customers need to be aware of the product so it can become the first choice at the time of purchasing. It is because the product requires being first in the awareness set that would further lead to the consideration of customer purchasing decision. So, this has been viewed as an essential part because of the increase in demand for pirate products and brands because of lowest prices and relatively good product quality (Kapferer, 2009).

2.12.5. Perceived Quality

Another vital attribute is the perceived quality of the product that has been defined as the perception of the customer for the overall quality of the product or service (Severi and Ling, 2013). Since it is an intangible kind of the product and stated as overall feelings of customers towards the brand that is subject of nature and the customer knowledge of the actual product to satisfy their needs that correlates with the perceived quality (Baalbaki and Guzman, 2016). Perceived quality of a product or brand helps brand managers of a company to generate values for the customer by providing a reason to buy through product differentiation that is the brand position, motivating channel members to encourage customers and charging a premium price and brand would include further extensions for the categories (Heding et al., 2015). The same author further stated that appropriate branding would lead to higher sales for not only the promoted product but also the associated product of the brand. Albert and Merunka, (2013) discussed that the brand is a personality that helps the customer in identifying the services and design of the product (including term, name, symbol, sign and design or the combination of all) and how these elements related with the necessary constituencies like staff, customers, investors and partner. Further, some customers differentiate the brand based on the psychological aspect of the brand associated through feelings, thoughts, images, perceptions, attitudes, beliefs, experiences and other that linked to the brand and the experiential aspect of the brand (Buil et al., 2013). The experience of the brand of a consumer is his action to measure the accuracy of perception for the brand and how the brand would react that would lead to brand loyalty if it has performed as per the perceived quality of the brand.

2.12.6. *Consumer Preferences*

Preferences of the consumer for a product leads to the success of failure of any company because it is customers' choice to purchase a product or not. If they are purchasing, then the company can survive for years (Baalbaki and Guzman, 2016). However, if there are a few customers and they are quick to switch brand, then it can lead to failure of the company, and this is because consumer preferred to not buy from a particular seller. Albert and Merunka (2013) discussed that consumers are quick to develop stereotypes about a particular product, and it occurs sales. Hence, consumers can make choices of their preferences for buying a product based on the product quality or origin of the product manufacturing company (Brodie et al., 2013). Furthermore, the price has also been identified as a critical element influencing the preference of consumers as based on price most of the time quality of the product is perceived. Gneezy, Gneezy and Lauga, (2014) also identified price more relevant to create a

perception for the product quality that also shows the inability of a person to evaluate the product quality based on other directly relevant factors.

2.12.7. *Brand Loyalty*

Brand Loyalty is among the critical components of brand equity that is directly and positively affected by brand equity (Buil et al., 2013). Under the brand loyalty influences, customers continuously purchase the brand regardless of the prices, convenience and superior features owned by the competitor's product (Luxton et al., 2015). Studies have found that more loyal customers are the less vulnerable base of customer would be, and it has been argued by Romaniuk and Nenycz-Thiel, (2013) that lifestyle and physical quality has an impact on the level of brand loyalty that is further mediated by the satisfaction of the consumer. A definition further supported the point, and the definition states brand loyalty in two simple terms, including 'behaviour and attitude' (Heding et al., 2015). Based on the outcomes of the studies, repeat purchase of a brand by a customer shows brand loyalty (Baalbaki and Guzman, 2016). However, there are challenges and arguments by other researchers that this measure cannot be accurate as it has been argued that some people repurchase or repeatedly purchase a product because of their habit to use the brand as it is readily available.

2.12.8. *Brand Association*

The brand association has been stated as the last dimension of brand equity that is defined as the vital linkage between the brand and memory (Severi and Ling, 2013). Further, researchers described the concept as the brand equity is mostly supported by the association of customers towards the brand that contributes to their perception and image for the brand (Heding et al., 2015). Concept of brand association has been stated as the complicated mediator that connects one dimension of brand equity with other, consisting different ideas, examples, episodes and the facts that develop a network of brand knowledge (Buil et al., 2013). Additionally, the tangible product has characteristics of intangible quality are also stated as the brand association that consumer connects to perceive the whole brand as the quality of product and service (Gneezy et al., 2014). The brand association has further divided into three types, including attributes, benefits and attitudes (Heding et al., 2015).

2.13. Chapter Summary

The second chapter of the research is about the review of the literature. Literature reviews summaries the concept about digital marketing, the social media part of the digital marketing, defining of social media and theories of social media, different types of social media platforms and their current usage. The literature review also comprises of traditional marketing and social media marketing. The chapter also encompasses social media technology use, marketing capabilities and its details, customer orientation and its details, lastly, in the chapter the concept of brand equity is explained with details..

Social media is attracting SMEs for marketing purpose . The purpose of marketing is to generate revenue for the company by selling their products. To measure the performance of the firm there are some key factors (out of which some are discussed here) as marketing capabilities , customer orientation and brand equity. These factors are playing a mediating role between social media technology use and firm performance. Further in research will find out the importance of these mediators and which is directly related to a better performance of a firm. It will help SMEs executives to focus on the exact key performance indicators and how to improve marketing tactics. Next chapter of the research covers the development of hypotheses for research based on literature review.

CHAPTER 3

3. Proposed Research Model

3.1. Introduction

In this chapter a thesis statement will develop a visual research model and that model will propose some hypothesis development in order to clear relationships between two or more than two variables. Hypothesis is a prediction statement in writing that what a writer expect to happen in his study. In proposed framework , hypothesis can be proved or disproved. It is typically used in quantitative research and predicts the relationship between variables.

A hypothesis makes a testable expectation about the result of a particular report, while a hypothesis is the all-encompassing clarification for why and how certain results occur overall. That implies you can utilize the hypothesis to figure out what you hope to occur. Researchers for the most part base scientific hypothesis on past perceptions that can't agreeably be clarified with the present scientific theories. Despite the fact that the words "theory" and "hypothesis" are regularly utilized interchangeably.

3.2. Theoretical underpinning / Development

Different theoretical frameworks and perspectives about social media are viewed in the literature. According to Agnihotri, Kothandaraman, Kashyap and Singh, (2012), these different theories are basically about social media adoption either on an individual or organizational level. Different theories talk about this perspective, such as Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), Technology Accepted Model (TAM) and the third leading theory is Technology Organization Environment (TOE). Vorhies and Morgan, (2005) discussed the Theory of Planned Behaviour which describe the link in human believes and behaviours. According to Gligor *et al.*, (2019) **resource-based view** (RBV), competitive advantage for firms is necessary, and this theory is primarily used in recent era to a competitive edge in the market. This theory claimed that attainment of competitive edge in the market is reliant on the firm's resources that how the firm is using its productive resources (Vaccaro *et al.*, 2012). Agnihotri *et al.*, (2012) claimed that Resource-Based View theory is primarily based on the VRIO analysis which helps to find the organizational competencies by finding its capabilities are Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, as well as Distinctive. These four characteristics are primary

sources to get a competitive edge in the market and to get a superior market position. Kamasak, (2017) stated that in the firm its resources are considered the main drivers and textile industry is also based on the resources, for example, physical resources which are infrastructure, and facilities. Some other resources are human resources (managerial skills and whole staff) as well as organizational resources such as information technology, business strategies, and knowledge sharing etc. (Gligor *et al.*, 2019). These resources are helping and contributing their role in value creation for clothing-related firms (Wu *et al.*, 2010). At the same way, capabilities are considered those skills which are providing an advantage to the organization with the combination of organizational resources and assets (Lamberton and Stephen, 2016). Roberts and Grover, (2012) stated social media is the primary source to maximizing its information technology resources which ultimately providing the opportunity to increase company capabilities. The networking capabilities can also achieve through social media sources. Hollen *et al.*, (2013) argued that knowledge could be acquired through the firm’s networking activities which not only help to provide information but also help to promote the organizational performance of the company. Online social platforms are crucial in terms of information sharing about firm, its provided facilities and resources. Peterson and Crittenden, (2018) claimed that information which is shared by the company on social media is also significant to increase purchasing and at the same time it is practical to develop the decision of customers about their purchasing by providing attractive information. Also, social media is defined as an internet-based source which is a resource capability and powerful technology which is synergising complementary resources of firms (Gligor *et al.*, 2019).

3.3. Proposed Research Model

3.3.1 Social Media Technology usage and firm performance

According to Roberts and Grover, (2012) in this era of technology web technology and cyberspace becomes an everyday use and practice in all kind of business. Organizations are empowering them by connecting with their clients through internet usage without geographic issues (Roberts and Grover, 2012). Lamberton and Stephen, (2016) defined social media as a group which is comprised on different internet-based applications which were built or designed on the technological foundations and now these applications are allowing to create and exchange of information or user-generated content. Kaplan and Mazurek, (2018) claimed that social media comprised of many applications as well as social networking sites, blogs, microblogs, video sharing, social gambling and evaluation sites. According to Agnihotri *et al.*, (2012) in the recent era, social media is facilitating users to share their information and different social media websites such as YouTube, Facebook, Wikipedia, Twitter, LinkedIn, and other online forums are not only providing ratings but also sharing the customers feedback about the purchasing experiences etc. That is why social media is attracting users to seek information about the products or services regarding different companies, either it is the hospitality industry or any other. At the same time, social media is a vital source of communication channel which is helping businesses to accomplish their objectives for example marketing, branding, public relations, customer service, and as well as problem solving (Hanssens and Pauwels, 2016). In this perspective, Krush *et al.*, (2015) claimed that social media is a useful tool and platform which is helping enterprises to reach large potential customers who not only help to increase sales but also increasing organizational revenue. The online communities are also expanding the interconnectivity of business and existing and potential customers on a national and global level (Gligor *et al.*, 2019). Social media is impacting brand positioning by creating awareness in customers, helping to get customer loyalty as well as developing customer purchasing decisions.

In the recent era, most of the companies are transforming business through social media which is also helping to increase organizational performance. Agnihotri *et al.*, (2012) discussed the social media technology and the use of technology in organizational perspective as well its impact on organizational perspective. It described the social media and customer relationship management that how it directly influences the organizational financial performance and customer engagement.

That is why it is claimed that social media technologies need to be integrating along with CRM, which can strongly influence organizational performance. Social CRM capabilities allow

organizations to engage the customers in collaborative conversations which help to strengthen the customer relationship and help to get customer feedback (Giannikas *et al.*, 2019). The interactive marketing technologies not only enable to interact with stakeholders but at the same time quantity quality of the information create higher quality interaction sources to provide clear information to customers. Recent literature is determining that marketing capabilities are including social CRM capabilities which lead to developing strong customer relationship as well as positively influence the stakeholder's satisfaction, especially customer satisfaction. In a technological perspective, the given literature suggested that recent marketing technologies are enabling organizations to interact efficiently and effectively with customers. Pekovic and Rolland (2016) argued that the purpose of social media to encourage customers to purchase and provide brand awareness. That is why when brands show their information on social media, it ultimately increases customer engagement and increases the information available so customers can easily find it. The CRM capabilities are emphasizing on the integration as well as the accessibility of information which engage the customers and helps the brands to increase customer relationship. It means for better and effective customer relations, the integration of social media with corporate marketing is necessary. Vorhies *et al.*, (2011) stated that firms who are using these social media networks for business approaches are leading the business toward superior market position Thus, in the perspective of the textile industry also have few pieces of research which are considering the social media usage to improve organizational performance.

Based on the above review of prior studies the hypotheses proposed here is as follows.

H1 Social media technology use significantly associates with firm performance

3.3.2 Social media technology use and Marketing capabilities

Social media has become more than a social networking forum and to communicate with the consumers (Agnihotri *et al.*, 2012). Social media technology is now integrated with business processes such as customer relationship management (CRM), brand management, product development, innovation and supply chain management (Zhang *et al.*, 2013). Marketers are challenged with developing a more lasting relationship with the customers, and that requires critical business processes to engage and integrate with the social media platform. Technological developments have now made it possible for companies to conduct and align their business processes with social networking sites/platforms (Nesi and Prinstein, 2015). As per Anderson and Jiang, (2018) implementation of social media technology alignment with

business processes generates new competitive advantages and marketing capabilities for the companies. Zhang *et al.*, (2013) assert that big companies have their personalized information systems that handle the critical business functions such as marketing management, supply chain and financial management; however, small and medium enterprises now focus on integrating their crucial business processes with social media that helps them to closely associated and engage with the target audience (Berthon *et al.*, 2008). Berthon *et al.*, (2008) continue by arguing that such marketing capabilities for SME help to enhance business performance.

3.3.2.1 Innovation Capabilities

As per Nieves and Segarra-Cipres, (2015) distribution of knowledge within and outside the organization is now possible through social media technology use. Innovation processes are facilitated with such integration that helps the organizations to enhance their innovation potential. SME's are the backbone for any economy and is considered as a critical contributor towards employment creation. Therefore, the innovation capability of SME's is more prone to enhance through the integration of social media technology use (Cerne *et al.*, 2013). Agnihotri *et al.*, (2012) mentioned SME's as actors in creating, applying and introducing innovation. According to Ahearne *et al.*, (2007), small and medium enterprises should hire and train personnel who can recognize innovation and refine them through collaboration with the partners. Such collaboration can be put on fast-track through social media technology use. Hence, companies should apply such practices before going outside the boundaries of the organization for innovation search. Collaboration with various business partners becomes of the critical sources of innovation (Cerne *et al.*, 2013).

Further, Camison and Villar-Lopez (2014) argued that SMEs should collaborate for various synergies with other SMEs to increase innovation capabilities. For instance, marketing function can be enhanced and promoted through collaboration with other SME, who are expert in the field, and this can be done through integration and communication using social media platforms (Nieves and Segarra-Cipres, 2015). The notion of innovation has changed from 'cooperation between individuals and departments within the same organization' to 'dealing with the networks' that increases not only the footprint of the companies but also enhances innovation capabilities (Wright *et al.*, 2012).

Networking using social media technology implementation helps SMEs to generate support for various business activities that are not the primary capabilities or expertise of the company (Ahmed *et al.*, 2014). Small companies usually face the capacity, and specific expertise issue,

which is not available internally neither can be attained due to financial constraints. In such a scenario, the collaborations and networking matured through social media technologies help SME's to attain the required tasks done (Davicik and Sharma, 2016). Open innovation paradigm is also followed by big brands to get generate numerous ideas; even large corporations have their research and development department (Wright *et al.*, 2012). Large corporations also collaborate with SMEs to buy innovative ideas and implement them under their brand after catering all the copyrights and legislative issues. Small companies usually do not have the resources to produce/implement the ideas, and hence, they look towards large companies for selling their ideas (Cerne *et al.*, 2013). The purpose of an open innovation network is to strengthen the innovation generation process, and that helps all types of organizations (Camison and Villar-Lopez, 2014). According to Hecker and Ganter, (2013) social media networks provide methods for coordination and collaboration of SMEs with customers, suppliers, partners and even academia, and such collaborations enhance the innovation capabilities of the firms (Nieves and Segarra-Cipres, 2015).

3.3.2.2 Branding Capabilities

Social media presence is an essential part of almost all type of organizations (Agostini *et al.*, 2015). Big corporations and brands focus on reading and understanding consumer buying behaviour through social media platforms and related activities. Much of the marketing research is now focused on identifying and evaluating the social media technologies that lead towards shaping consumer purchase intentions (Davicik and Sharma, 2016). As per Agostini *et al.*, (2015) 81% of the consumers took their purchase decisions through the social media posts from their family and friends (Aichner and Jacob, 2015). 78% of the social media users mentioned that their purchase decision was influenced mainly through social media posts by the company. Branding is something that is now done mainly through social media platforms. However, the time it takes to build a brand over social media is much higher than the time it takes to defame it (Ahearne *et al.*, 2007). Social media news is spread like wildfire especially the negative news, and hence, brands are cautious in making posts and sharing contents over social media platforms and avoid being controversial (Nieves and Segarra-Cipres, 2015). As per Ahearne *et al.*, (2007), small companies can follow the social media brand-building strategies to build their brands and enhance their awareness. For instance, small brands of food-service suppliers and clothing retailers intensively uses social media to promote their brand that increases their brand awareness in lesser cost compared to traditional marketing techniques.

Reviewing the above theoretical knowledge and the assertive relationship following hypotheses is proposed.

H2 Social media technology use significantly associates with marketing capabilities

3.3.3 Marketing Capabilities and firm performance

According to Vorhies and Morgan (2005) resource-based view (RBV), the competitive advantage and organizational performance are reliant mainly on the company resources endowments. Roberts and Grover, (2012), in his research, stated that resource-based view emphasis on the company capabilities as compared to company resources. It also integrates the capabilities and its potential impact on business because according to this theory, only resources are not sufficient for company success. The vital thing to use the resources is capability usage which is most relevant to organizational success as compared to only resources. Agnihotri *et al.*, (2012) claimed that marketing capabilities could develop a particular link with customers by primarily focused on customer linkage capabilities. Peterson and Crittenden, (2018) stated in their research that marketing resources are leading competitive edge for the organization which need to understand by the organization because it is a market based intangible asset or capability of an organization for example brand and **customer equity**. Another research described that marketing capabilities performance could be divided into two different approaches. The first approach is about the conceptualization of marketing capabilities in which middle-level marketing provide support through 4Ps, market management and market research as well. The necessary limitation of the stream is known by proponents Vorhies and Morgan, (2005) claimed it is about the higher-level integrative capabilities, for example, brand awareness, and management, customer relationships and innovation as well. Krush *et al.*, (2015) conducted research to assess the higher-level marketing capabilities in which brand reputation, customer relationship and innovation was also included. A meta-analysis done by Kaplan and Mazurek (2018) demonstrated that marketing capabilities and organizational performance are strongly correlated with each other. This meta-analysis depicted that middle-level marketing helps to form marketing capabilities; that is why it can be claimed that the sum of different middle-level marketing activities is called marketing capabilities.

Hecker and Ganter, (2013) revealed through his research that marketing planning is crucial but at the same time marketing implementation is also a crucial element for marketing capabilities and these marketing capabilities are strongly influencing the business performance in terms of

success. At the same time, Agnihotri *et al.*, (2012) noted that marketing capabilities are having a direct impact on organizational performance and profit growth of company. Wright *et al.*, (2012) extended the research and he finds out the mediating role marketing capabilities and its relationship with customer relationship management as well as organizational performance. This research explored that marketing capabilities are playing a mediating role in customer relationship management and growth in organizational performance. Malthouse *et al.*, (2013) explored through his research that marketing capabilities are contributing its decisive role in firm performance and ultimately organizational profit growth, as well as outcomes in other economic conditions, can be increased. In this respect, Peterson and Crittenden, (2018) claimed that organizations are embedded as well as organizations are making links in the customers as well as business, so it means marketing capabilities are not only improving the financial situation of companies either small, medium or multinational organization but also providing opportunities to SMEs in terms of a vital source of targeting comprehensive market segmentation and to develop their purchasing behaviour. This research also stated that organizations could get a competitive edge in the market by using marketing capabilities, and these marketing capabilities can be developed through improving networks.

Giannikas *et al.*, (2019) explored the impact of online networks on firm performance and declared that marketing capabilities are helping to develop strong customer relationships as well as influencing the customer purchasing decisions by modifying the buyer behaviours or perception about the product or offered services. The online networks are helping customers to access the shared knowledge by the company, which impact the decision making of customers (Peters *et al.*, 2013). This research was continued by Saravanakumar and SuganthaLakshmi, (2012), who argued that marketing capabilities could be designed through different marketing strategies such as the most famous and used way is the **marketing mix**. At the same time, Kietzmann *et al.*, (2011) stated that significant marketing capabilities are about innovation and branding strategies. Krush *et al.*, (2015) also supported this factor. They claimed that innovation and branding strategies are capabilities which can provide a competitive edge in the market as compared to other traditional marketing strategies.

Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H3 Marketing Capabilities significantly associates with firm performance

3.3.4 Social media technology use and Customer Orientation

The organizational values, leadership beliefs help to design the two-way premises relationship. This two-way relationship is basically in customer and organization, which can be achieved through marketing capabilities. Chang *et al.*, (2010) argued that customer orientation could be increase by online forums. He stated that customer orientation is about the in-depth understanding of target buyers which makes them able to get a competitive edge by the creation of superior value. Customer orientation approach talks about why organizations must meet buyer needs (Pekovic and Rolland, 2016).

Peterson and Crittenden (2018) stated that in terms of customer orientation, it is necessary to develop a cheerful disposition and strong relation with customers by developing a high level technological or innovative way. Chang *et al.*, (2010) stated that it is the maturity of customer orientation that it is helping brands to manage their supply chain by developing understanding about customer needs that's why now brands are delivering right and quality products which are ultimately helping to get customer loyalty. Customer orientation is a central component of marketing which is helping brands to pursuit the new opportunities by exploring customer needs, wants and demands. This customer-orientated culture is not only providing customer familiarity but also emphasising to audit the customer profile, which can help to achieve the marketing and financial goals of the organization (Pekovic and Rolland, 2016). Agnihotri *et al.*, (2012) also argued that customer orientation approaches are helping to get the customer vision which is helping brands to keep an eye on customers and to analyse the market trends as well as to check the customer acceptability about the products.

Based on the review of prior literature above, the following hypotheses are proposed for this study

H4 Social media technology use associates with customer orientation

3.3.5 Customer orientation and firm performance

Every business has an intended purpose of satisfying the needs and wants of their customers that is ultimately linked with organizational objective of sales generation and increasing the profitability for the organization (Kocak et al., 2017). However, the satisfaction derived from a particular set of product benefits and services is dependent on the stated and unstated needs and wants of the customers that are related to the extent to which an organization is urged to

conduct in-depth research on customer needs and wants. Customer orientation has been defined as the pursuance of an organization to satisfy the needs and wants of their customers by assessing their underlying needs that they are not able to justify consciously. When an organization cater and consider the needs of their customers individual, the firm is considered customer-oriented as opposed to the conventional view of market orientation. From the point of view presented by recent research, it has been asserted that adoption of customer-oriented view is linked with firm performance in terms of increasing market shares and the number of customers served and resulted in a more satisfied bunch of customers. Frambach, Fiss and Ingenbleek (2016) presented their view to consider the personalized consideration of every customer leads to value creation for an entity and its customers. They are more likely to be satisfied and hence the business can gain a competitive advantage over its rival firms by more customer retention and loyalty that might not result in increased business profits in the short run. Still, in the long run, market share improves (Wang, Z., & Kim, 2017). Based on this following hypothesis has been proposed.

H5 Customer orientation significantly associates with firm performance

3.3.6 Social media technology use and Brand Equity

Social media has been able to revolutionize the traditional communication pattern of the organization. As per Kim, Han and Park (2001) brand equity which is the value underlying a particular brand derived by customers in the form of awareness, engagement, a sense of association with it and perception regarding quality has been inherently linked with promotional mix adopted by the entity. Social media from the study of Kim and Ko (2012) Were found more rapid communication medium to be aware the customer about a new product or service offering as opposed to traditional communication channels, e.g., newspapers and television due to declining in the audience that has been shifted towards the social media (Dwivedi et al., 2018). Interactive nature of social media has helped the businesses to engage their customers with product and services for a more extended period like interpersonal communication channels (Pham and Gammoh, 2015). Social media technologies provide the entities to reach their prospective customers with a set of needs that are inherently offered by the business to their intended customers by utilization of state-of-the-art intelligent technologies as opposed to mass media flow of information with less surety of customer reach. Hence customers are provided with relevant information and product categories entirely matching with their inherent needs, they derive value and ultimately stays loyal to the brand (Lowe et al., 2019). Based on this, the following hypothesis has been derived.

H6 Social media technology use associates with brand equity

3.3.7 Brand Equity and Firm Performance

Firm performance is intuitively expected to increase with more substantial brand equity (Santos-Vijande *et al.*, 2013). Usually, brand equity is determined through various aspects such as awareness, quality perception, association and loyalty (Chang and Liu, 2009). However, brand value is another concept, which gives a financial value to the firm's brand, and that is also sometimes referred to as goodwill. Various research studies prove the fact that higher brand equity increases the financial performance of the company, but in a simple scenario, increased brand equity brings more sales and revenue. Consequently, it increases its profitability (Wang *et al.*, 2016). Brand equity is an asset for the brand owners since, and it has various benefits associated (Su and Tong, 2015). Various advantages are highlighted in literature for the higher brand equity, for instance. Stahl *et al.*, (2012) argued that higher brand equity creates a differentiation factor for the company among competitors, and it increases the likelihood of enhanced purchase intentions for the customers. Aaker (1991) noted that higher brand equity brings more effectiveness and efficiency of the marketing campaigns conducted by the companies. According to Chang and Liu, (2009) higher brand equity allows the firms to charge higher prices since such brands are more associated and engaged with the customers and customers are also more loyal to the products or services provided by the company. Further, Fang *et al.*, (2014) assert that brand equity is given benefits to having higher bargaining power in front of suppliers and hence, have higher negotiation power which also improved the cost of goods sold and hence, positively reflects in the profitability of the firm.

As per Stahl *et al.*, (2012) higher brand equity leads to higher purchase intentions and enhance re-purchases of the company, which gives consistent and sustainable profitability to the firms. Firm performance can be calculated using various indicators such as higher brand association and perceived customer quality given more customers and hence, increases the market share of the company (Luo *et al.*, 2013). Increased brand loyalty means a substantial and long-term relationship with the customers, and hence, repurchases are assured that gives consistent profitability. Higher brand equity also brings growth opportunities for the companies as various market forces combine to enhance the business footprint.

From the above-stated reference and literature work below is the hypotheses proposed for this study.

H7 Brand equity associates with firm performance

3.3.8 Mediation effects

3.3.8.1 Mediation of Marketing Capabilities

Capabilities of marketing is an essential element to convert the resources which are valuable to the performance of the firm. An organization required marketing capabilities to convert the resources into products or services which are viable and commercial, which then convert into the performance of the firm. Capabilities of marketing encompass the skills where these are embedded deeply into the routines of the organizations and in the organization practices as well as to represent the knowledge which has been gained over the number of years. Krasnikov & Jayachandran (2008) did research in which they found out that capabilities of marketing are one of the driving factors when the firm or an organization is operating in such a dynamic environment. Morgan et al., (2009) state that the association or the link among the marketing capabilities and firm performance is positive and stronger in turbulent industries, whereas it is weak in such industries which are stable. Another research being carried out by Salisu Abu-Bakr and Rani (2017) found that capabilities of marketing are an essential factor which is the one who contributes to the attainment for the firm performance. Morgan (2012) also carried out research in which it found that capabilities of marketing in a firm are linked directly or cause an impact directly on profits or growth of the firm. Another research by Ahmed et al., (2014) found out that marketing capabilities contribute towards the outcomes of the firm performance in several different conditions economically. Based on research carried out by the number of different researches, presented below is the hypothesis for the research.

H8 Marketing Capabilities mediates the relationship between social media technology use and firm performance

3.3.8.2 Mediation of Customer Orientation

Based on the research carried out by Narver and Slater (1990) it has been found that customer orientation in the firm leads towards the performance of the firm to be superior. Ambler (1999) and Bitner et al., (1990) have recommended as well that the development of the customer orientation and the implementation of the customer orientation is the nucleus or impetus to organization positioning in the marketplace . Research carried out by Kennedy et al., (2002) found out that there is a significant as well as a positive relationship between market orientation and firm performance in the market. Research carried out by Liu et al., (2003) states that orientation of the customer is significantly important with regards to enabling the firm to understand the marketplace for the firm and to develop the strategies of product where they are

appropriate as well as the strategies where they are linked to meet the requirements and the needs of customers where this translate further into the firm performance. Another research carried out by Cheng and Krumwiede (2012) have postulated that customer orientation in the firm would lead to better or superior firm performance. And eventually, whereas it focuses on the focus on the creating of value or enabling of value for the customer which also enables the form to improve the customer satisfaction, innovation and loyalty where it leads eventually to the performance of the firm. Based on the number of different researches carried out on customer orientation and firm performance, hypotheses for the current research study has been developed as stated below.

H9 Customer Orientation mediates the relationship between social media technology use and firm performance

3.3.8.3 Mediation of Brand Equity

Based on several different researches carried out in the past, the mediating effect of brand equity has been found on the performance of the firm. Madden et al., (2006) found out in their research that brand equity is an antecedent which is strong to the firm performance where the number of different types of competitive advantages exists in the functions other than the functions linked with marketing only. Based on the research carried out by Weerawardena et al., (2006) the firms who can successfully collaborate with the multitude to the stakeholders and integrate the stakeholder's intentions are more likely that they would be able to identify and to respond the opportunities via new product, services or process which eventually increases the revenue. Based on the research carried by several different researchers, hypotheses have been developed for the research as stated below. Research by Vorhies et al., (2011) states that brand equity could not be the sole driver for the firm performance, and the effects of brand equity are contingent on the firm and the market forces, whereas nevertheless brand equity greatly has strategic significance because it results from the stakeholder's interaction and it could also improve the firm performance. It has been contended by Feng and Morgan and Rego (2015) that brand equity depends on the firm capabilities to maintain and to improve the quality of the firm in long run, where these may also acquire the trade-offs in the profitability of the firms in the short term.

H10 Brand equity mediates the relationship between social media technology use and firm performance

3.4. Conclusion

Following chapter has been prepared for the development of hypotheses for the research. Based on the literature review and the research being carried out by several different researchers, development of hypotheses has been done for the research for the current research study. Altogether 10 different research hypotheses have been developed for the research. First hypotheses have been developed for the impact of social media technology use on firm performance. Second hypotheses have been developed for use of social media technologies link with capabilities of marketing. Third hypotheses is Marketing Capabilities significantly associates with firm performance. Fourth hypotheses is Social media technology use associates with customer orientation. The fifth hypothesis is Customer orientation significantly associates with firm performance. Sixth hypotheses is Social media technology use associates with brand equity. Seventh hypotheses is Brand equity associates with firm performance. Eighth hypotheses is Marketing Capabilities mediates the relationship between social media technology use and firm performance. Nineth hypothesis is Customer Orientation mediates the relationship between social media technology use and firm performance. Tenth and last hypotheses is Brand equity mediate the relationship between social media technology use and firm performance. Next chapter of the research is aimed at the methodology of the research.

CHAPTER 4

4. Research Methodology

4.1. Introduction

Research is a systematic way to investigate and identify the underpinning information or additional information regarding a particular phenomenon to reach certain conclusions and develop theoretical frameworks for future intended studies of similar modules (Quinlan *et al.*, 2019). Research is intended to increase the existing knowledge about a specific area. Still, this increment must be based on facts and figures to justify the conclusion drawn. For this, it is essential that the fact collection process is systematic and based on scientific principles (Bell, Bryman & Harley, 2018). In every discipline, the individual research approaches are adopted to analyse and resolve problems, based on the pieces of evidence gathered to fill knowledge gaps pertinent to a problem area. Nature of data collected differs, i.e., observational, experimental, derived or simulation data. The nature of data collected for disciplines varies due to underlying objectives researchers intend to achieve.

In business research, the methods adopted for systematic gathering and analysis of data can range from observation to derived which implies for underlying objectives of business research, that intends to resolve problems or filling knowledge gaps from a broader perspective. Research in business and management field has an applied nature, which implies that existing knowledge and practical understanding related to a particular problem area or issue impacting an individual or groups are implementing to search for the optimal solution, provide explanation and settle the future course of action that can be adopted. Since, in business research, regardless the fact that scientific methods are applied, the adaptation, variation and flexibility pertinent to approaches adopted is part of a research which create specific issues related to validity and reliability to methods adaptation and has certain risks that actual results may disorientate from their underlying objectives. They were intended to achieve their generalizability overpopulation shall be a questionable aspect. To ensure that every aspect of research is as per standards of scientific studies with minimum margins of errors or deviation, a methodology adoption is a necessary aspect (Burns & Burns, 2008). A research methodology is the adoption of a procedural approach towards the data collection process for a research investigation so that adoption of approach shall not be a question and a clear description of

justification related to validity and reliability to processes adopted for data collection and analysis is provided. A research methodology differs from mere research method. A research method is a mere description of techniques through which research can be conducted. In contrast, a research methodology has a broader perspective which implies for identification of process through which these methods shall be applied in a systematic way to find a solution and ensure quality, i.e., reliability and validity of data collected, and results obtained. Quinlan et al. (2019) has been of the view that research methodology is science for the research that has been intended to be conducted and identifies the procedures that are used to describe, analyse and explain the phenomena occurring through generally developed theories and hypotheses testing.

Saunders et al., (2009) developed a systematic approach to defining a research methodology for a specific area of concern with an intent to guide the researchers about their intended approach towards defining their data collection process (see figure below)

Research Onion Diagram (based upon Saunders et al's diagram, 2009)

Since research methodology is a systematic process, it requires the adoption of an exemplary process and research onion provides researchers with steps that are deemed to be taken in a sequential manner that improves the quality of the process and ensure that researchers have considered each aspect of business research (Burns & Burns, 2008).

The figure presented above has depicted the research methodology as a process of peeling an onion. After peeling each layer, which means successful completion of each stage, the next layer appears, which is likely to be defined to encounter the next layer. Using this step-by-step approach, the researcher reaches the last stage, which is defining of data analysis phase and then the process is completed. Researchers cannot skip any step to reach the other next step as the procedural approach is compulsory to be observed (Bell et al., 2018). Main layers of a research onion are philosophy, its underlying approaches, strategies, the time horizon, methods for data collection and analysis. There are various underlying aspects/categories that a researcher has been intended to choose from each main layer and streamline a comprehensive research methodology for a specific problem area (Burns and Burns, 2008; Greener, 2008).

In the following chapter, a comprehensive overview of the research methodology adopted for this research has been explained with justification for each area of choice that has been made based on the pieces of evidence from existing grounded literature.

4.2. Philosophical Paradigm

A paradigm is defined as the belief system that a researcher/investigator holds about the process of breaking down complications into simple pieces of information. Saunders (2011) defined the selection of a philosophical paradigm as a varying internal mechanic approach to study outside world. There are distinctive categories of research paradigm, e.g., positivism, post-positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatic (Quinlan et al.,2019). The selection of a philosophical belief depends on the prioritization pertinent to the objectives a researcher intends to attain and has an individual inclination towards a specific system of philosophy. Saunders et al., (2009) has been of the view that philosophy is merely an assumption about nature of truth that exists in the world and how research intends to believe in it followed by their way to interpret the information gathered based on these assumptions, but, from the perspective of a research, these suppositions related to nature of reality are base for any research methodology development, and hence successive stages of research are related and modified using the preliminary philosophical assumption of the research (Burns and Burns, 2008; Greener, 2008) Using a philosophical belief, researchers identify the nature of data being

collected, the ways through which interpretations shall be made followed by the presentation of results obtained.

Since there are various philosophical paradigms as identified earlier, i.e., the realism that interprets the phenomena as independent to the existence of nature and how others have perceived them and pragmatic, which implies for drawing meanings of reality concerning the consequences being drawn based on the practicality and unrealistic views are subjected to rejection (Quinlan et al.,2019). However, there are two major categories which are widely applied by researchers in a business context are interpretivism/interpretivism and positivist /positivism as opposed to the beliefs that have been discussed earlier, i.e., pragmatic and realism. The former belief assumes that truth about the world or a particular knowledge area is brought frontward through human experience and involvement in the situation that has been integrated with subjective observation and creation of relation with the subject under consideration. On the other side, an opposing view, positivism intends to interpret reality using the social facts that exist in the surrounding which can be identified and analysed using the scientific methods having a minimum margin for the discrepancy (Saunders et al., 2009).

For this very research, the underlying paradigm is positivism which implies to rely on verification process during fact collection process as opposed to interpretivism, which is intended to understand the underlying reason for the occurrence of facts. A positivist approach has been intended to adopt the scientific approach towards data collection process and hence believes that reality exists in unitary form and can be achieved through replicated processes of hypotheses testing and can be quantified. The rationale of preferring a positivism approach over an interpretive approach lies in the generation of a more authentic and reliable set of information/results to improve the quality of research results generated for a specific study as compare to interpretivist approach that results in a more qualitative set of information that is complex to comprehend, understand. Its reliability is often a question due to the massive involvement of researchers in result generation process (Bell et al., 2018).

When a positivist approach is adopted, a researcher has an underlying objective to unleash the laws that naturally exist in the environment and hence they, the researchers are more likely to maintain a certain distance from the participant or the subject matter that on which experiments or scientific observations are deemed to be performed. Hence, it is justified that the analysis made shall be valid and reliable as a certain distance from the subject under consideration has been made (Kervin and Kervin, 1992). Additionally, the meaning drawn from the research

pieces of evidence from the adoption of a positivist philosophical view is interpreted through the formulation of objective results as opposed to interpretivist view in which meaning is drawn in the form of the subjective meaning of information and due to these reasons, there are greater probabilities that the results obtained and meaning drawn can be generalized through the adoption of a positivist approach as opposed to interpretivism, in which despite greater flexibility to interpret results, generalizing results on the whole population can be a matter of multiple questions as constructs of reality in interpretivism are based on mere meaning drawn by the subjects and their interrelated relation with the environment within which they operate (Bell, Bryman & Harley, 2018; Saunders et al., 2009).

Moreover, since the results can be replicated due to utilization of underpinning theoretical frameworks, they can be applied with more generous coverage to the outside world as compared to interpretivist approach where the conclusion is drawn usually based on a smaller set of objects and their generalizability is often questioned (Saunders, 2011).

4.3. Research Approach

A research approach is intended to define the plan or the procedures that shall be adopted by the researchers to conduct the study. The selection of research approach sets the basis for successive steps that shall be followed to collect the data (Saunders, 2011). Usually, a research approach is categorized into two broad categories, e.g., deductive and inductive. A deductive research approach intends to collect the facts by formulating research questions based on an already developed research framework. Hypotheses testing is the aim to reject or accept the assumptions made underlying a study as opposed to an inductive approach that has an intended purpose of collecting data to develop a new theoretical framework which implies that a research approach defines the underlying purpose of why data has to be collected; to justify the existing frameworks in a new setting and provide the phenomena under consideration based on the theoretical framework (deductive) or develop a new theory by collecting information (inductive approach) (Bell et al., 2018). For this research, the approach adopted is deductive, and the justification for preferring a deductive approach over an inductive approach lies in the ability of this approach to aid in developing and proving causal relations among variables provided with a foundation of existing research (Kervin and Kervin, 1992). The adoption of a deductive approach enables the theory testing with the help of quantifiable data that is considered a more reliable way to data collection as opposed to a qualitative way to data collection where authenticity is often hampered by involvement of the researcher in every step right from

approaching respondents to data analysis that might often result in biased results that are against the norms and ethics of research (Greener, 2008). On the other side, the adoption of an inductive approach has several limitations. For instance, it requires more time to be practically applied and hence due to limitation of time, deductive approach is preferred (Quinlan et al., 2019). Addition to that, theory development, which is the fundamental stance of inductive approach requires the researcher to exhibit the extensive experience of the problem under consideration and risk of failure is higher as compared to deductive approach (Saunders, 2011).

4.4. Research design

A research design intends to define the underlying collective stance adopted by an investigation to combine and link the underlying concepts associated with a particular study and a purpose to improve the authenticity of methodology arranged and combined logically. Since the purpose of defining a research design is to make sure that the pieces of information collected for data analysis process have been enabled with the ability to be free from any ambiguities and have inherent logical arrangements. For this intended research, the research design is explanatory that is based on existing frameworks and has an intended purpose of explaining the objects under study by using a justified theoretical framework (Kervin and Kervin, 1992). Adoption of an explanatory research design has many underlying advantages as it improves the understanding about an object by defining why a particular phenomenon has taken place and what process has been adopted for these phenomena to take place. A more comprehensive range of information sources can be utilized for this study that improves the reliability of conclusions drawn about a particular area of research and addition to that an explanatory research design helps the researchers to draw broad conclusions (Greener, 2008).

4.5. Research choice

The discussion of a research choice explains the style that shall be adopted by the researcher to elicit information from the respondents. Research choice is linked with the intelligent choice made in the very first stage of defining research paradigm. Since for this research, research paradigm is positivism that is a belief related to collecting justified information that is numerical or objective, and a survey questionnaire intended to elicit objective information from the respondents shall be an appropriate choice as opposed to other choices, e.g., experiments (Hair et al., 2007). A survey shall improve the probabilities of data collection from a large set of respondents that hence can be generalized on a broad set of the population which is further aided by a distance maintained between respondents and researchers that is indeed related to

no influence of the researcher on the data collection process. The information collected is hence analysed by using statistical procedures that are inherently not in control of researchers, and results are presented in their natural and authentic manner (Kervin and Kervin, 1992). The respondents, on the other side, are likely to enjoy the freedom of time to respond using their full set of information held in memory without any sort of interruption in the response process. Since the data can be collected from many respondents in a survey, as described earlier, many population representations can be attained which not possible when other methods are utilized (Greener, 2008). Addition to that, administering survey results in the collection of a broad range of information and since the respondents had time to respond, they were not bored to respond lengthy survey.

4.6. Data Collection Process

A data collection is defined as the process that shall be adopted in a natural setting to collect data from respondents (Hair et al., 2007). The data collection process is intended to define how respondents shall be profiled and then approached to collect the data from them. It is deemed to correlate with philosophy, research approach selected, and significant decisions made earlier in research design. In the following sections, population and sampling approach has been presented (Kervin and Kervin, 1992). The data collection process is about the measure. It gathers information from respondents on the variable of interest in a systematic way which enables a researcher to find an answer to the questions as well as to test the hypothesis. Appropriation of the data collection process about research objectives is likely to impact the outcomes of the research. Addition to that, since the rejection or acceptance of research hypotheses, is dependent on data collected for a specific study, researchers are deemed to adopt the right procedures to settle the process for data collection.

4.6.1. Population

A population for research is the set of objects that have inherent characteristics of the respondents for an intended research investigation. These characteristics can be demographic, e.g., age group, gender, education level or any occupation (Cooper et al., 2006). Addition to that, these characteristics can be psychographic, e.g., values, beliefs or followers of a particular religion. However, regardless of underlying population characteristics for research, it is necessary to define the population characteristics carefully, and the selection made based on these similarities (Bell et al., 2018). Greener, (2008) defined population by claiming that it is a well-defined individual's collection containing similar characteristics. These common and

binding characteristics of the population are enabling the researcher to meet the research objective. According to Greener, (2008) population is chosen in two ways deductively population is chosen on the base of theory and observations, especially when the theory claimed about validity.

Moreover, it depends upon the precision of the theory because the population can be less or weakly defined, which is unable to clear the population characteristics. Inductively population is considered as observation in this kind mainly results are implemented or generalized which are given by the selected sample. In inductive approach population is defined only for a specific purpose and from a particular sample, that's why results are generalized on the base of a different set of observations gather from a specific sample. Thus, the population is an approach which can be defined for a particular purpose and results from sample implemented on the base of empirical findings. The findings from this population can only be generalized if all the population is having sufficient close or matched properties, which are sufficient to analyse the sample; the selected sample can be infinitely small. That is why the population is choosing indistinguishable from the sample. Thus, according to the given types of population, inductive approaches will be implemented, which can support to generalize research findings.

The research is about SMEs in Pakistan. Small and Medium Enterprises is the largest sector in Pakistan economy, which is playing a crucial role in the Pakistan economy. SMEs are shaping national growth and improving living standard. SMEs sector is comprised of more than 90 percent of enterprises and contributing to country inclusive growth. In 2016 Farid SMEs accounted for 99 percent and having 35 percent in value addition moreover 86billion dollars are contributing to country GDP. These SMEs are consisting of different firms and businesses, but still, there is no specific number found to calculate these businesses. In previous years different numbers are found about the SMEs sector in Pakistan. Still, these numbers are not considered authentic because the government is not given or any registration of business. In 2010 micro-businesses were 2,930,350 and SMEs were 27,777 and in 2011 it was estimated total of 6.96 million in Pakistan, in Punjab 65.26 percent, Sindh 17.82 percent, NWFP 14.21 percent and Baluchistan 2.71 percent. With these figures, it was also claimed that these are not exact figures about numbers of SMEs in Pakistan. The retailing sector is contributing key role in SMEs, and it is known as the third largest sector, which is contributing its role in country GDP.

The retailing sector is one of the established and fast-growing sectors in Pakistan but still number or statistics are unknown about this sector. Pakistan retailing sector is comprised of 33 percent of the service sector and generating more than 18 percent of total country GDP. This industry is valued 42 billion US dollars. Some of the SMEs are in the retailing sector are well known and managing operations in all over the country. For example, some of crucial fashion retailing brands are Khaadi, Gul Ahmad, Sapphire, AL Karam, Sana Safina and many others. It was the trend that only fashion retailing industry was using social media, but with time different SMEs and other retailing companies are also using social media as a marketing tool. Most of the fashion retailing industry is a strong example of entrepreneurship and now listed in SMEs, and these retailing companies are contributing to their role country GDP.

Population for this research study are the small and medium enterprises that are using social media platforms. The purpose of using social media platforms could vary; for instance, companies that are using social media platforms for their product advertisements are included in the population. At the same time, the companies that are using social media platform only for information display about the company products, processes, and human resource are also included in the population. It implies that the purpose of using social media does not decide the inclusion in the population. The focus is on the companies that are using social media technology for their business, in any format. Therefore, the population for this research study are all those small and medium enterprise companies operating in Pakistan that are using social media technology for their business. However, this research is focused on the clothing industry; therefore, only those small and medium enterprises are focused that are in the retail clothing sector of Pakistan.

4.6.2. Sampling Technique

A population is a set that contains all objects with similar stated and unstated similarities, and their size can be so large that all of them cannot be taken into consideration to collect data due to constraint of time and complexities that may arise due to utilization of whole population set (Zikmund et al., 2013). For research, usually, a small proportion of the population is drawn called sample that has all characteristics of a population and hence results obtained from them can be generalized on the whole population based on this underlying assumption (Hair et al., 2007). According to Cooper et al., (2006) it necessary to use inferential statistics to conclude from samples which enable the researcher to observe population characteristics only in a small portion. There are different reasons to draw sample size, and the main reason is practical as compared to economical. Cooper et al. (2006) stated that inaccessibility to the whole population

force population to use sampling techniques. The sampling process is all about to choose those individuals in research which represent the whole population which they selected for research. The sample is a smaller representative to collect units from a large population which support to find results and findings from the research. The purpose of sampling is to increase the research effectiveness, reliability and credibility. Sampling increase research speed and increase research accuracy, it is an economical way of research as compared to reach the whole population. In terms of sampling, the better report can be formulated on the base of validity and reliability of the information. It is not easy to collect data from the whole research population and to analyse the real data that's why sampling is a better way to increase the efficacy and validity of the research. Sampling is a complex process, and mainly two types of sampling are used in research one is probability sampling, and second is non-probability sampling. Probability sampling means that all individuals or items have an equal chance to including or select in sample size.

Research supported that probability sampling is used when research is having in-detail and accurate information about the whole population it is because researcher constructs sampling frame on the base of in-depth information and later use random number generation by using manual or computer programs to pick a sample from the sampling frame. In social sciences, it is preferred to use probability sampling because it reduces sampling biases. These sampling biases are reduced through the equal opportunity of selection in the sample. In terms of analysis, random sampling is used because mathematical theorems mostly used or justify statistical procedures can be implemented on probability sampling. Random sampling is considered vital because it reduces the sampling error and brings more accuracy in the research process. Probability sampling is suitable for many the population; it is more expensive. In most of the cases, it is difficult to find lists of the full population. In probability sampling, more expertise and skills are required for investigators. There are different types of probability sampling, simple random sampling, systematic sampling, stratified random sampling, cluster sampling, and multi-stages sampling. In a simple random sample, every individual has an equal chance of being select, and systematic sampling is also a statistical method which involves elements selection in the ordered sampling frame. Stratified sampling is about to divide the sample into different subgroups which called strata and random sampling implement on these strata. These strata are generally based on characteristics. Cluster sampling is about the whole population when the sample is divided into different clusters, and random sampling applies to these clusters. The second type of sampling is non-probability sampling which associates with

qualitative research. Non-Probability sampling majorly focuses on small samples which design to examine real-life phenomenon without statistical inferences in terms of the wider population. There are different types of non-probability sampling, quota sampling is known as a non-random sampling technique in which research participants are selected on predetermined characteristics ultimately total sample of research have the same characteristic distribution in the whole population.

Snowball sampling is another type of non-probability sampling, and it is used when very few cases are available as population, so the researcher reaches to one case and asks for another case. It is used when the population is tough to find. Convenience sampling is also a type of non-probability sampling, and it is used when the population is readily available, it is mostly used in students because of its inexpensive feature. Purposive sampling is also known as a type of non-probability sampling; it also called judgemental sampling, which used when the population is close to hand. In non-probability sampling, there is no statistical method involved; it does not mean that non-probability sampling is not population representative.

Moreover, it does not mean that non-probability sample does not depend upon rational. Still, the fundamental reason behind non-probability sampling is to use sampling even when the population is not well known in terms of quantity or numbers. Non-probability sampling is time and cost-effective; it is mostly used when the probability sample cannot work or when population size is small.

Sampling is an essential aspect as it is not possible to collect data from the entire population. The population for this study is the small and medium enterprise business operating in the retail clothing sector of Pakistan and those huge in number (relatively unknown). Therefore, it is not possible to collect data from all the population members. Drawing a sample from the entire population is necessary to implement the study practically. However, experts are of the view that a sample size must be large enough to represent the population. Hence, the results obtained are likely to be implemented on the entire population and can be used in decision making, as suggested in the significance of the study. However, researchers cannot randomly select their sample as they are deemed to follow specific standards and techniques to draw a sample from the population (Cooper et al., 2006). For this purpose, sampling was done where data was collected from the sample size.

Here in this research Convenience sampling is used which is a non-probability sampling technique where data can be collected from the population simply because they are easily

accessible to the researcher. Preferably, in research, it is nice to test an example that addresses the population. Convenience sampling is a kind of testing where the available primary data will be tested without any extra necessities. At the end of the day, this sampling technique includes getting participants any place you can discover them and normally any place which is convenient. In other words, Convenience Sampling is affordable, easy and the subjects are readily available (Etikan, 2016).

4.6.3. Sample Size

There are almost 3.3 million Small and Medium Enterprises in Pakistan. These include manufacturing units, service providers, and start-ups operating on various levels. SMEs employ 78% of the non-agricultural labour force, make up about 25% of manufacturing exports and over 30% of the GDP in Pakistan. The part that they play in the economy is significant but the attention paid to them is negligible in comparison (Khan, 2020).5% of the total textile companies are listed on the stock exchange. There are 423 textile industries working in the country (Textile | Board Of Investment, 2021).

First of all you should be working with a finite population and if the population size is known, the Yamane formula for determining the sample size is given by:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n= corrected sample size, N = population size, and e = Margin of error (MoE), e = 0.05 based on the research condition.

The population is 423. At 5% MoE., the sample size would be: $423(1+423(.05)^2)$
 $423(1+423(0.0025))$
 205.5893074119
 $= 205$

In a finite population, when the original sample collected is more than 5% of the population size, the corrected sample size is determined by using the Yamane's formula.

In the example above, 5% of 423 is 21.15 and hence the corrected size is 205 although for research purposes, even 205 is a big number (for handling and collection point of view from different companies) and the researcher has to make a decision to collect even smaller number in order of ease of handling, costing but he has to ensure that the sample is representative (Adam, 2020).

SAMPLE SIZE GENERALISATION

The sample size is generalisable. Generalisation is the use of the outcomes from research to the more extensive targeted population. It depends on the understanding that the results from the samples will be something very similar for every other person in the target population.

Generalisation is an act of reasoning that includes drawing expansive inductions from specific observations, is generally recognized as a quality standard in quantitative research, however, is more questionable in qualitative research.

In quantitative work, replication of participant in sample size can add value in generalisation as well as statistical power. The more replications enhances the validation and removes the ambiguity in results which represents the whole population (Polit and Beck, 2010).

4.7. Research ethics

Since ethics are the moral rules and regulations that individuals are deemed to qualify with regardless of their interests and judgements, ethics impacts all areas of life and hence are also related to research. Ethics are codes directives for humans to streamline their behaviour in the environment through the realization of their rights and duties concerning those they interact in society through general meaning drawn based on morality and humanity which differentiate a human from the other species (Greener, 2008). These ethics are generally accepted principles related to morals and values and are entirely different but co-exist with legal rules and regulations and guides every discipline of human life. In research, different ethics guides the behaviour and conduct of researchers and are essential for a researcher to follow to validate the research procedures especially the data collection process adapted by researchers from subject matters (Hair et al., 2007; Burns and Burns, 2008).

From the perspective of research, ethics are defined as the moral principles, that researchers are subjected to comply with during research process (Greener, 2008). To prove the authenticity of research, there are various underpinning principles that researchers are deemed to comply with to claim their research to be authentic. Human experimentation and research process started in early 18th of Century. Still, business research ethics gathered the attention of researchers in the middle of 19th century as an effort to interfere and streamline the scientific studies that were based on the exploitation of humans, as a matter of subject or cases for analysis pertinent to specific research and in late 19th century, these basic research ethics, become an essential aspect of business research and were considered a base for valid and

reliable research pieces of evidence and their generalizability to the entire population from which case sample for analysis are drawn (Hair et al., 2007; Greener, 2008).

These research ethics are followed during the entire research process. Still, most of them are taken into consideration during data collection process due to human encounter which is likely to result in various ethical dilemma due to human nature to make errors in stressful situations where decision making become difficult due to suppressed brain activity (Cooper et al., 2006).

During this research project following research, ethics were taken into consideration.

4.7.1. Protection of participant

This principle is related to the right of the person who participates in research should be benefited but not harmed. The harm can vary from both of psychological nature or physical, and a researcher is not allowed to harm participant in the short or long run through their acts of any nature (Zikmund et al., 2013). From the perspective of nature related to data, it is implied that protection of participants when data is qualitative, i.e. interviews and focus group discussions, protection of participants are more likely to be at stake as compared to quantitative data collection method (Hair et al., 2007), in which researchers have an intention to collect confidential information about the subject matter of the discussion and as per Burns and Burns (2008), the probability that the respondent shall face emotional or physical discomfit is higher. Since this research has been entirely based on a collection of data from quantitative methodology using survey questionnaires as an instrument of data collection, it was less possible that someone would have been harmed.

During the data collection process, it was ensured that participants should not be harmed in terms of physical or emotional injury. Addition to that, a distance was maintained so that that researcher will not impact the data collection process. The participants were informed well about the intent of data collection and for what purpose this information shall be used, e.g., for academic purpose so that they are not unaware of any aspect of their valuable response.

4.7.2. Protection of free will

the respondents were asked to participate in the response process after giving them sufficient information about it. Then they were left free to decide on whether they will participate or not in this study. Addition to that, those who participated were provided with sufficient time-space to elicit their response and were not pressurized in this regard. A primary ethical consideration in an entire data collection process is informed consent, and it is defined as knowingly a person

participate in a research process (Cooper et al., 2006). Every individual who participated in this research process had not to be assaulted or oppressed to take part in this research process, and they voluntarily become part of this research.

4.7.3. Right of confidentiality

Since participants have provided their consent to take part in this research as they had been ensured that their opinions should remain anonymous, the actual responses given by the participants were kept confidential and were not shared with anyone except the internal stakeholders of this information, e.g., instructor and supervisor of the research. Further, it has been ensured that the data collected for the research has been saved at repositories which cannot be accessed by anyone but a researcher.

4.7.4. Avoiding discrimination

The data collection process is supposed to assume equality, and no one is deemed to be mistreated (Bell et al., 2018) or being subjected to showcase their vulnerabilities. During the data collection process, no discriminatory behaviour was exhibited among respondents concerning their job status, gender or any other ground. All respondents were equally and respectfully treated to ensure that their self-esteem is maintained.

4.7.5. Protection of individual privacy

As a human living in a free world, everyone has a right to safeguard their privacy and has the freedom to unleash the information about their personal life to the public (Zikmund et al., 2013). According to researchers, an invasion of privacy is related to inquiry about the personal beliefs, opinions to share them with others. As a result of which, many people shall be able to draw certain conclusions about a person or a group of individuals (Burns and Burns, 2008).

During the data collection process, the respondents were not asked about any personal information which they might feel shy or reluctant to share, e.g., personal income. Addition to that, they were at liberty to skip the questions they do not want to answer, and they were not inquired about that. Since this research was about customers and their opinions, i.e., their response to social media marketing, it was necessary to obtain their opinions and responses. For this reason, an anonymous questionnaire was filled by respondents as they had been able to give their views without any hesitation and risk of being exploited (Hair et al., 2007).

4.7.6. Presentation of results

After data collection, an important consideration that was made related to results intends to present them in their proper form, i.e., raw results with no tolerance for manipulation to gain results which were related to the personal interest of the researcher (Burns and Burns, 2008).

The results were presented as they have been obtained from the analysis, and no interference was made about these results so that reliability of these results shall not be hampered.

4.7.7. Right of intellectual properties

no information cited or quoted in research is without referring to their actual producer, and it has been made sure that all the information that has been obtained from journals or any other published material have not been left uncited within text or in Bibliography. Additionally, another important consideration that has been made throughout this research process was avoiding plagiarism which implies that all the data and information obtained from research journals, which are the primary source of knowledge, were not copied as plagiarism is a form stealing someone's property (Hair et al., 2007).

4.8. Analysis

The information obtained from the respondent is in its raw form and merely looking at the responses, no conclusion can be drawn about the inclination of respondents especially when researchers are deemed to cater many responses in which numeric information is obtained from the respondents. To obtain specific and useful information, data must be analysed using several mathematical or statistical techniques which are done in the data analysis stage of the research process (Cooper et al., 2006).

Data analysis has been defined as the process that consists of several underlying steps to be followed. The process consists of a collection of data into a repository, transformation into a workable form, e.g. in the spreadsheet, cleaning of information which consists of discarding unnecessary data sets, then modelling which implies the application of techniques, e.g. statistical techniques to elicit the information in the form of results, then interpreting which consist of activities related to communication of information in a presentable form which can be readily comprehended by the audience and the conclusions can be drawn based on information that has been obtained as a result of analysis (Hair et al., 2007).

Data analysis is the most crucial part of the research and needs expertise because, in this section, systematic statistical and logical techniques. In this process researcher describe, recap,

illustrate, and evaluate data. In this regard, various analytical tools are used, which lead toward inductive inference through data analysis and help to distinguish different phenomenon. This step of research declares that research is supporting the research hypothesis or not moreover researchers use data analysis techniques very consciously because of the complexity of this step. Researchers are conscious of data analysis because, in case of wrong analysis, results can mislead the researcher. It is considered an essential research component which ensuring data integrity through appropriate analysis; it is critical because improper statistical analysis has the potential to distort scientific findings.

While choosing the data analysis technique, researchers deem to consider various areas of concern so that, right statistical tools are used to present and interpret the results, and one of the considerations is related to statistical techniques opted. For researchers, it is compulsory to keep the research objectives in view while deciding on the statistical techniques they are about to use in their study so that the results obtained from the study shall justify and fulfil the research objectives.

For this research, the following research techniques have opted:

4.8.1. Descriptive Statistics

This analysis is preliminary and is often referred to as demographic or participant profiling. As the term indicates, this form of analysis, describe the characteristics of the participants or subjects as part of the study (Hair et al., 2007). Secondly, this analysis technique is used to consider specific research questions which are pertinent to a study, and descriptive statistics allows the researchers to have complete confidence that there had been no violations of the statistical methods being employed and the underlying assumptions (Bell et al., 2018). These descriptive statistics are absolute coefficients that are depicted in the form of numbers and provide the summaries related to the data set. In this research, descriptive statistics were made used to define or summaries categorical variables, i.e., those having fixed or limited values. These variables, as compared to ordinal variables, are subjected to certain limits. They are represented in the form of categories which are likely to represent groups of individuals (Cooper et al., 2006), i.e., gender, age group, income level or education. In this research, descriptive statistics have been employed to unleash the demographics of the participants. Hence, their various categories to which they belong, and this method is called demographic profiling of the subjects (Greener, 2008), the intended purpose of using descriptive statistics to profile the respondents that the sample characteristics have been distributed across the various

categories that have been developed. The sample has no leaning towards a group as these inclinations can impact the results obtained.

4.8.2. Correlation Analysis

In quantitative studies, where hypotheses testing is one of the key measures to assess that whether the research objectives have been attained or not, correlation analysis is one of the most trusted, convenient and widely used methods to the presentation of results (Greener, 2008). Correlation is a mathematical and statistical expression that intends to represent results in the form of numeric co-efficient to depict the degree to which two variables under consideration are related and the direction of their relation, i.e., inverse proportionality or direct proportionality (Cooper et al., 2006). The convenience of a correlation analysis lies in the description as a numeric value that is the sole measure to draw inferences about the strength and direction of the interrelation between the factors under consideration (Bell et al., 2018). The value range from -1 to 1 and it has been implied that more a value is closer to 1 or -1, there is more probability that the relationship is healthy if the values are statistically significant, i.e., $p < 0.05$. However, there are various assumptions that researchers have made to the acceptable range of the correlation. For instance, if the value is between .5 to 1 (both positive and negative) and the value of P is less than 0.05, it has been implied that the relationship is statistically significant among variables. Then if the value range from .49 to .30 (both positive and negative), and the value of P is less than 0.05, the correlation is moderate. Lastly, if the value is less than .30 (both positive and negative) the relationship among two variables is weak, or there is a low correlation among variables (Greener, 2008; Bell et al., 2018). The direction of relation, i.e., whether the variables are inversely related or directly related, is depicted by the sign (-, +) against the value of correlation. For instance, if the value obtained is -, it implies that change in one variable, shall cause the modification in other but in the opposite direction. On the other side, if the value of the case variables under consideration is positive, it implies that change in one shall change the other in the same direction.

4.8.3. Test of Mediation

Usually, in conceptual frameworks developed for the studies, there are two variables, i.e., an independent variable and a dependent one and the relations among these variables are usually predicted and tested (Bell et al., 2018). However, there are cases when these relationships are intervening by a third variable called a mediator. These variables are intended to explain the relationships that exist between dependent and an independent variable, as opposed to moderators which are likely to impact the strength of the IV and DV in a conceptual framework.

In mediation, the underlying reasons for the existence of the relation between two variables are explained. However, based on the literature reviews, such assumptions are hypothesized, and there is a need to test them using a statistical technique (Greener, 2008). In this research, it has been proposed that there are intervening or mediators who are marketing capabilities, customer orientation and brand equity, and it has been proposed that these three mediate the relationship between social media technologies as the independent variable and firm performance as a dependent. To test these claims, statistical tests, i.e., regression analysis, has been applied and then based on the results, hypotheses have been rejected or accepted.

4.9. Research Summary:

The fourth chapter of the research comprises of research methodology used for the research. The chapter explains the philosophical paradigm, furthermore, the chapter explains the research approach, research design, research choice. The chapter also includes the process of data collection which includes population, sampling techniques used for the research, the sample size for the research. In addition to this, the chapter also includes the research ethics of the research. Lastly, the research also includes an explanation for the techniques used for analysis of data. Next chapter of the research includes findings, analysis and discussion on the results obtained.

Research Design:

CHAPTER 5

5. Findings, Analysis and Discussion on Results

5.1. Introduction

Based on the collection of primary data using a questionnaire, results have been presented in this chapter. Collected data whereas having been processed for analysis using SPSS as a software tool and the results have been extracted using various techniques of analysis of data. Data analysis whereas have been driven based on the aims and objectives of the research as mentioned in the first chapter of the research study. In addition to this, the statements for hypothesis are tested as they were developed in the second chapter of the research. The core purpose of the analysis of data was to calculate the effect of the use of social media technology on the performance of the firm as well as to measure the effect of different mediators such as brand equity, marketing capabilities and customer orientation. This chapter whereas provides respondents profiles, reliability test, a summary of both correlation analysis as well as regression analysis. At the end of chapter 4, a summary of hypothesis testing is also presented.

5.2. Respondents Profile

The table below provides statistics of the respondent's profile who participated in the questionnaire survey conducted. The questionnaire was filled by both males as well as female respondents. From a total of 224 respondents, 129 respondents were males where it counts for 58% of the total respondents who responded to the questionnaires. In addition to males, female respondents also answered questionnaires. Out of a total of 224 respondents, 93 respondents were females, wherein percentage they account for 41% of the total respondents who responded to the questionnaires filled. Lastly, out of 224 total respondents, 2 respondents were such where they preferred not to share their gender, they may be male respondents or they may be female respondents since they have preferred not to share their gender, these respondents account for 1% of the total respondents.

Another aspect based on which respondents have been profiled are the basis of age, respondents starting from age 20 and going above 55 participated in the questionnaire. Out of 224 respondents, between age 20 going up till the age of 35 years, a total of 43 respondents belonged in this age bracket. In terms of percentage, the first age bracket 20 years till 35 years

account for 19% respondents. The second age group which participated in the research is between 36 years till 45 years of age. In this second category of an age group total of 66 respondents out of a total of 224 responded in the research. In terms of percentage, 66 individuals between the age group 36 years till 45 years account for 30% of the total 224 respondents' profile. Third age group where if filled the questionnaires shared includes respondents between the age of 46 years till 55 years. This age group, as well as the age group of 36 to 45 years, are counted as adults. In the age group of 46 years till 55 years, a total of 83 respondents filled the profile. In terms of percentage from the total 100%, 37% account for age group 46 years till 55 years which may include both males and females. Last age group where these participated in the research were respondents having more than 55 years of age. This is the maximum age group where it participated in the research. In the age group, 55 years and above, 32 respondents filled the profile. In terms of percentage these individuals both and women where they belong to 55 years and above account for 14% of the respondents.

To summarize it could be said that 43 respondents where they become 19% of the total respondents were from age group 20 years and above, similarly, 66 respondents where they become 30% of total respondents were from age group 36 years till 45 years, likewise 83 respondents where they become 37% of total respondents were from 46 years till 55 years, lastly 32 respondents where they become 14% of the total were from age 55 and more.

More females participated in the research as compared, which is 58% as compared to males 41%. Similarly, the highest group of people 37% were from the age group 46 years till 55 years, whereas the lowest group of people were from the age group 55 years and more.

Table 2: Respondent's Profile

Parameter		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	129	58%
	Female	93	41%
Age	Prefer not to say	2	1%
	20 to 35 years	43	19%
	36 to 45 years	66	30%
	46 to 55 years	83	37%
	Above 55 years	32	14%
Total Respondents		224	

5.3. Reliability Test

To perform the reliability test Cronbach's alpha has been applied to the test to test the reliability of each of the variable. Cronbach's alpha reliability (Cronbach, 1951) is one of the widely most used measure used to test the reliability in the social sciences and social sciences. Cronbach alpha whereas describes the reliability of the sum or average of q measurements, whereas measurements which are q may represent rates of q , occasions of q , forms of q , an alternative of q or maybe questionnaire/test items of the q . When the measurement whereas represents the different items in tests, where it is one of the most common applications of Cronbach, the test of Cronbach's alpha is referred to measure of reliability if it is internally consistent. If the measurements or variables are "parallel" (McDonald, 1999) these measures will have equal covariances and equal variances. And if the measurements are "tau-equivalent essentially" (McDonald, 1999) these will not have equal variance but will have equal covariance. Therefore, it can be seen that (McDonald, 1999) the reliability test of Cronbach's alpha correctly describes the reliability of the sum or the average of the measurements to q where they satisfy the assumptions which are parallel or the assumptions which are less restrictive known as tau-equivalent assumptions essentially. Whereas if the measurements of the test are "congeneric" measurements (Joreskog, 1971), these measurements could be represented by the model of one-factor with measurement errors which are uncorrelated. The assumption of congeneric is more realistic as compared to assumption of tau-equivalence since in it the measurements are not required to have variances which are equal as well as the covariances among the measurements where they are not required to be equal.

Internal consistency of instrument is based on the correlation between the various items of the same test. This correlation indicates that if several items where they are supposed to measure the construct which is the same produce the similar scores. For the Cronbach's alpha where it is computed with the correlation between all the pairs of the items, the internal consistency whereas can vary between zero and one, even though there are sometimes negative values as well. A generally accepted rule whereas is that where the Cronbach alpha value is between 0.6-0.7 where it indicates the acceptable level of the reliability, on the other hand, Cronbach alpha's value of 0.8 or greater are considered a very good level. Lastly, if the value is above 0.95 they are not considered as very good, because they might be an indication that the redundancy exists (Hulin, Netemeyer, and Cudeck, 2001). Even though the ideal situation whereas would be that all the items related to the test measure the same variable latent, wherein many different situations Cronbach alpha can register higher values even when the set of the values measures

different (Revelle, 1979; Schmitt, 1996; Zinbarg et al, 2006). Collecting as well as analysing the hundreds of articles as well as thousands of coefficients from them, Peterson (1994) described that a typical level of the Cronbach alpha is 0.77.

George and Mallery (2003) has provided the general thumb rule for Cronbach alpha: “_ > .9 – Excellent, _ > .8 – Good, _ > .7 – Acceptable, _ > .6 – Questionable, _ > .5 – Poor, and _ < .5 – Unacceptable”. Where while increasing the value of the alpha is dependent partially on the number of items which exist on the scale, where it should be noted that these values have diminishing returns. It should be noted that attaining a value of 0.8 for the Cronbach alpha should probably be a reasonable goal. It should also be kept in mind that where the value of Cronbach alpha being higher tells a good internal consistency to the items on the scale, where it also does not mean that scale is only one dimensional.

Table 3: Reliability Test Results

Research Variable	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Social Media Technology Use	6	0.872
Marketing Capabilities	7	0.701
Customer Orientation	5	0.900
Firm Performance	4	0.922
Brand Equity	3	0.810

The reliability test using Cronbach’s alpha performed in the table below shows the reliability significance of variables of research. For the first variable of the research “Social media technology use” the reliability of Cronbach’s alpha shows a result of 0.872 where it is greater than the suggested onset value of 0.7 (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). Similarly, for the second variable of the research “Marketing capabilities”, the result of Cronbach alpha shows a result of 0.701 where it is also greater than the onset value of 0.7 recommended (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). For the third variable of the research “Customer Orientation”, the result of Cronbach alpha shows a result of 0.900 which is also greater than the onset value recommended 0.7 (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). For the fourth variable of the research “Firm performance”, the reliability value of Cronbach alpha shows the reliability of 0.922 where this is also greater than the recommended value of 0.7 Cronbach alpha (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). For the fifth and last variable of the research “Brand equity”, the reliability value of

Cronbach alpha shows the reliability of 0.810 where it is greater than the recommended value of reliability 0.7 (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994).

5.4. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics provides information with regards to the data obtained through the questionnaires, where the statistics include N means number of individuals which filled the questionnaire, derived after that is the mean for the relevant variable, where it includes both dependent variable, independent variable and mediators. Next derived is the standard deviation of the relevant variable. Computed next is the skewness where it includes both the statistic value as well as the standard error for skewness. And lastly, the data includes Kurtosis where it also includes both statistic value and standard error.

Skewness, as well as kurtosis, are both used a rough indicator of the degree of the normality with regards to the distribution or with regards to the lack of, therefore. Unlike the test of statistics from the procedures of normality testing like the procedure of Kolmogorov-Smirnov D or the procedure of Shapiro-Wilk W , both skewness and Kurtosis are used as the size of the effect, to communicate the degree of the non-normality, instead of or rather than the statistical significance under some of the null hypothesis with regards to normality. The use of the method of skewness and kurtosis is to describe or explain the distributions dated back from Pearson (1895) whereas this has also been reviewed by Moors (1986), D'agostino, Belanger and D'Agostino (1990) and DeCarlo (1997). Skewness whereas is a rough index of the asymmetry with regards to the distribution, where the skewness which is positive in the unimodal distribution suggests plentiful relatively and or extreme values positive, and the negative skewness suggests the same to the negative values. Skewness is also represented as an estimate of the third moment standardized of the distribution of population

Skewness whereas has a value where it ranges from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$ as well as systematic distributions like the distribution normal have a skewness value of 0. The n -based bias term of correction for the estimate of population is negligible for the large samples, but these are still included for completeness.

Kurtosis whereas is an estimate of the fourth moment standardized of the distribution of the population. Kurtosis whereas ranges from 1 to $+\infty$. The kurtosis of the distribution normal is 3. Whereas it was also common to subtract the 3 from the value of k and describe this term then as "excess kurtosis" which is beyond that expected from the normal distribution.

In a rather simple language skewness is the measure of the symmetry, or more accurately or precisely as the lack of the symmetry. A distribution or set of data is symmetric if it also looks the kind of same towards the left and towards the right of the centre point.

Kurtosis whereas is the measure of whether the data are tailed-heavy or tailed-light to the distribution normal. The data set whereas with higher kurtosis tend to have tails as heavy, or tails are outliers. Data set with low kurtosis whereas tend to have tails as light or known as lack of outliers.

The rule of thumb for skewness is that if the statistics of skewness is between -0.5 and 0.5, the data is symmetrical fairly, whereas if the skewness is between the value of -1 and -0.5 (skewed negatively) or the data is between 0.5 and 1 (skewed positively), the data is then known as skewed moderately. And lastly, if the skewness is lesser than -1 (skewed negatively) or it is greater than 1 (skewed positively), then the data are skewed highly.

The table below illustrates the descriptive statistics based on the research. On average, the number of responses received for each unit was 224. The rating for social media technology use and customer orientation was very close, as the mean value for social media technology use was 4.38 and mean value for customer orientation was 4.53. The mean value for marketing capabilities whereas was 4.11 and mean value for firm performance was 4.00 and lastly the mean value for brand equity was 3.35.

The standard deviation for all the variables and mediators came up as below 1, where the standard deviation for social media technology use was .705, the standard deviation for marketing capabilities was .480, the standard deviation for customer orientation being a mediator came up as .598, the standard deviation for firm performance being the dependent variable came up as .646, lastly the standard deviation for brand equity being the mediator came up as .624.

By examining the skewness and Kurtosis, the univariate normality has been inspected. Univariate skewness was less than 2.7 whereas and the univariate kurtosis was much lesser than the threshold values of 5.0 to the skewness and the kurtosis (Kline, 2005). Therefore it is concluded that the data does not violate the assumption of the normality.

Skewness statistic for Social media technology is -1.310 where it is lesser than the threshold value as suggested by Kline (2005). Skewness statistic for Marketing capabilities is .049 where it is again lesser than the threshold value as suggested by Kline (2005). Skewness statistic for

customer orientation being a mediator is also lesser than 2.7 as recommended by Kline (2005). Skewness statistic for Firm performance being an independent variable is -.802 where it is again lesser than the value of 2.7 as suggested by Kline (2005). Lastly, the skewness statistic for brand equity which is a mediator for the research is .704, again lesser than the recommended value of 2.7 as Kline (2005) recommends.

With respect to Kurtosis, the statistics for social media technology is 3.318, the statistic for marketing capabilities is 2.322, the statistic for customer orientation is 4.169, the statistic for firm performance is 3.214, and lastly, the kurtosis statistic for brand equity is .448. For all the values of kurtosis for dependent, independent, and mediator variable all is below 5, which is the value recommended by Kline (2005).

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean		Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Social Media Technology Use	224	4.38	.047	.705	-1.310	.163	3.318	.324
Marketing Capabilities	224	4.11	.032	.480	.049	.163	2.322	.324
Customer Orientation	224	4.53	.040	.598	-1.371	.163	4.169	.324
Firm Performance	224	4.00	.043	.646	-.802	.163	3.214	.324
Brand Equity	224	3.35	.042	.624	.704	.163	.448	.324
Valid N (listwise)	224							

5.5. Correlation Analysis Results

Correlation is the measure of the association monotonic between two different variables. A monotonic relationship between 2 different variables is the one in which either (1) when the value of one variable increases, the value of other variable increases as well. Or (2) when the value of one variable increases, the value of other variable decreases. In a data where it is correlated when the change in the magnitude of the first variable is linked with the change in the magnitude of the second variable, either in the same direction or in the opposite direction. In other words, it could also be said that higher value of the first variable tends to be linked

with the higher or positive correlation either or linked with the lower or negative correlation values of the second variable.

A linear relationship between the two different variables is the special case of the monotonic relationship. Majority of the time, the term or concept of correlation is used in the context of such a relationship which is linear between the two continuous random variables, where it is known as a Pearson correlation of product-moment, where it is abbreviated commonly as “ r .”⁶

The degree to which the change in the first variable continuous is linked with the change in another variable continuous could also be described mathematically as in the terms of the covariance to the variables. Covariance whereas is like the variance but since the variance described the variability of the single variable, covariance on the other hand is a measure of how the 2 different variables vary or change together. However, the covariance is dependent on the measurement scale of the variables, as well as on its magnitude which is absolutely where it cannot be interpreted easily, or it cannot be compared across the studies. To facilitate the interpretation, the coefficient of Pearson correlation is used commonly. The coefficient where is the measure dimensionless of the covariance, where it is scaled such that this ranges from the value of -1 to +1.

According to Akoglu (2018) correlation is defined as such a relation where it is existing between phenomena or things or between statistical or mathematical measures where it tends to vary or be associated, or it may occur together in such a way that it is not expected alone by just a chance. A classic example whereas would be apparent as well as the higher correlation between the systolic (SBP) as well as the diastolic blood pressure (DBP). The correlation between both the variables whereas which are systolic and diastolic blood pressures is known as bivariate correlation where it could be shown on a diagram of scatterplot if both the variables are continuous variables or scale variables. Where both the variable systolic and diastolic when increase, they increase together and when to decrease, they decrease together, therefore both are correlated highly together. If it is required to remove the effect with regards to the third variable from any correlation which exists between the two variables, then it is required to calculate or find out the partial correlation. Whereas partial correlation is such a form of correlation where it quantifies the relationship which exists between the two variables in the meanwhile controlling the effect of the one additional variable or more additional variables, for example, age, treatment received, sex, etc. If both the male and females are separately

coloured to examine if the sex affects the correlation which exists between systolic and diastolic pressure or not.

One of the most important facts is that the correlation does not imply that there are any causations. Since if the increase in the sales of ice-cream happens, the rate of deaths because of the drownings increase as well. These facts both even though they happen at the same time, still they are not the cause of each other. The relationship where it is known as the correlation between both the variables for which correlation is found is denoted by the letter r as well as it is quantified with the number, where this number varies between -1 and $+1$. It is also essential to know that 0 where it comes between -1 and $+1$ still means no correlation, yet 1 is found as the correlation value it means as a complete variable or perfect variable. The sign of r whereas shows the direction to the correlation. A negative r whereas means that both the variables for which values are being found are related inversely with each other. The strength of the correlation of the variable increases in both directions which is 0 to $+1$ and towards 0 to -1 . The correlation coefficient falling between $+1$ to -1 is referred to as perfect correlation, whereas the correlation between $+0.9$ and -0.9 is known as strong correlation, the correlation between $+0.8$ to -0.8 as well as between $+0.7$ till -0.7 again known as strong correlation, yet the correlation between $+0.6$ and -0.6 also $+0.5$ and 0.5 and $+0.4$ and -0.4 is known as moderate correlation, and correlation below $+0.3$ and -0.3 is known as weak correlation (Akoglu, 2018).

For our research correlation has been found between the dependent variable, independent variable and mediators. The correlation between social media technology use which is independent variable and brand equity which is mediator variable is found as $.065$ where according to Akoglu (2018) it is a strong correlation. Then the correlation between social media technology use which is independent variable and marketing capabilities which is mediator variable based on Pearson correlation calculation is found as $.131$ as weak correlation. The correlation according to Pearson calculation between social media technology use being independent variable and customer orientation being mediator correlation is found at $.279$ which according to Akoglu (2018) is a weak correlation. Lastly between social media technology use being an independent variable and firm performance being a dependent variable is found at $.270$ which is again a weak correlation as according to Akoglu (2018).

The significance test for Pearson correlation can be taken whereas to derive a P-value for the coefficient of correlation, with the hypothesis statistical to test like the traditional approach. The null hypothesis whereas states that the population correlation coefficient from where the

sample was taken is zero. Whereas the alternate hypothesis states that the population coefficient of correlation from where the sample has been taken is not zero, the alternate hypothesis whereas is of two sides, because of which the coefficient of correlation might be <0 or it can be >0 . The significance test whereas is known as parametric which means that the value of c is false and therefore it requires a minimum one of the two different variables to be normally distributed (Sedgwick, 2012). The significance of variables from the current research whereas for social media technology use with the brand equity being a mediator variable is significant since the value of significance is .331. In addition, the significance of social media technology use being the independent variable with marketing capabilities being the mediator variable is .050 which is also significant according to Sedgwick, (2012). Then the significance of social media technology use with the customer orientation being a mediator variable is also significant since the value of significance is .001. Lastly, the significance of social media technology use being an independent variable with the firm performance being a dependent variable is also significant since the value of significance is .001.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis

		Social Media Technology Use	Brand Equity	Marketing Capabilities	Customer Orientation	Firm Performance
Social Media Technology Use	Pearson Correlation	1	.065	.131	.279**	.270**
	Sig. (2- tailed)		.331	.050	.000	.000
	N	224	224	224	224	224
Brand Equity	Pearson Correlation	.065	1	.249**	.167*	.393**
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.331		.000	.012	.000
	N	224	224	224	224	224
Marketing Capabilities	Pearson Correlation	.131	.249**	1	.411**	.392**

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.050	.000		.000	.000
	N	224	224	224	224	224
Customer Orientation	Pearson Correlation	.279**	.167*	.411**	1	.377**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.012	.000		.000
	N	224	224	224	224	224
Firm Performance	Pearson Correlation	.270**	.393**	.392**	.377**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	224	224	224	224	224

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

5.6. Regression Analysis

5.6.1. Assumptions of multiple regression:

Several assumptions concerning multiple regressions are too robust that they can be violated, and other assumptions are to be fulfilled to state the proper design of the study. Focus is on such the assumptions of the multiple regression which are not robust towards the violation and that can be dealt with by the researcher if these gets violated. Discussion includes the assumption of normality, linearity, homoscedasticity, reliability of the measurement and multicollinearity.

Normality assumption:

Regression makes sure that the variables have normal distributions. The variables which are distributed non-normally which could be kurtotic variables or variables highly skewed or variables which have substantial outliers could result in distorting the relationship as well as the test of significance. There is several different pieces of information which could be useful for the researcher to test the assumption of normality, where this information includes visual inspection for the plots of data, visual inspection of the skew, visual inspection of kurtosis, as

well as visual inspection of P-P graph where it provides the information about normality to the researcher and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is the one which provides inferential statistics to the normality. Outliers whereas could be identified either by doing the inspection visually of the histograms or by visual inspection of the frequency distribution or it can be inspected by converting the data to the z-scores.

Bivariate or Multivariate cleaning of the data could also be an important element in the multiple regression (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2001). Majority of the regression or the statistics of multivariate texts (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2001; Pedhazur, 1997) discuss the examination of the standardized residuals or studentized residuals or indices of the leverage. The removal whereas of the univariate outlier or bivariate outlier could reduce the probability of type 1 as well as of the type 2 errors and improve the accuracy of the estimates.

Univariate outlier or bivariate outlier removal in the majority of the statistical software is straightforward. Whereas it is not always desirable to remove the outlier. If the outliers are removed, transformations do result in improving the normality, but it does complicate the interpretation to the results, therefore the outliers should deliberately be used and in an informed manner be used. A full treatment whereas of the transformations whereas is beyond the scope.

Linearity assumption:

Standard multiple regression whereas can only estimate accurately the relationship where it exists between the dependent variables and independent variables only if the relationships are linear. Because there are several different instances in the social sciences where the non-linear relationships do occur, it is important and essential to examine the analysis for non-linearity. If the relationship between the independent variables as well as the dependent variables is not linear, the results therefore of the regression analysis will underestimate the relationship which is true. This underestimation whereas carrying two different kinds of risks, where the first risk is the chance of an error of type 2 for that independent variable and for the case of multiple regression, other risks are increased risks of the type 1 errors which is also known as overestimation for the other independent variables where these share the variance with the independent variable.

Authors such as (Pedhazur, 1997) and (Cohen and Cohen and West and Aiken, 2013) and (Berry and Feldman and Stanley Feldman, 1985) suggests that there are three different ways primarily to detect the nonlinearity. The first method whereas is the use of the theory of the use

of the previous research to inform the current analysis. Whereas much research in the past has overlooked probably the possibility of the non-linear relationships, therefore this method not a foolproof method. A more preferable method whereas for the detection is to examine the residual plots where residual plots are the plots of the standardized residuals and as a function of the predicted values standardized, where they are available readily in much statistical software.

The third method whereas of detecting the curvilinearity is to run the regression analysis in a routine where it incorporates the components which are curvilinear or using the option of nonlinear regressions. It is important whereas the non-linear aspects of the relationship are to be accounted for to best find the relationship between both the variable.

Reliability assumption:

The nature of the educational research and social science research means that many different variables that the researcher is interested in are also difficult to measure, where the measurement error of it makes a particular concern. In simple correlation measurement, regression measurement, as well as an unreliable measurement, causes the relationship to be underestimated, whereas increasing the risks to the type 2 errors. In the case of the multiple regression or to partial correlation, effect sizes to the other variables could be overestimated if the measurement of the covariate is not reliable because of the full effect of the covariate or covariates could not be removed. This is an important and significant concern if the goal of the research is to model accurately the relationships which are real in the population. Even though the majority of the authors have assumed that estimates of reliability done by Cronbach alpha of .7 up to .8 are acceptable Nunnally (1970) and Osborne and Christianson (2001) reported that the average amount of Cronbach alpha in the top education journals of psychology is .83, whereas the measurement of this level of quality still contains measurement errors which are enough to make the corrections worthwhile.

Correction whereas for low reliability is simple as well as disseminated widely in the majority of the texts with regards to regression, but this is seen rarely in the literature. It is argued that authors for the research should correct for the lower reliability to obtain a more accurate picture of the relationship which is true in the population and to the partial regression or multiple regression, to avoid the over-estimating of the effect of the other variable.

Since the presence with regards to the measurement of the errors in the behavioural research is the rule and not the exception and the reliabilities of many measures where they are used for

the behavioural sciences are at the best are moderate (Pedhazur, 1997). It is also significant and important that the researchers be aware of the methods which are accepted for dealing to the issue. For simple regression, whereas it provides an estimate of the relationship which is true between the independent variable and dependent variable in the population.

Even in the cases where the reliability is .80, the correction of the attenuation of the substantiality changes the size of the effect. When the reliability whereas drops to .70 or drop below it, this correction then yields a substantially different picture that is of the true nature of the relationship as well as it potentially avoids the error of type 2. Whereas with the addition of each of the independent variable to the equation of the regression, the effects of the reliability which is lesser than perfect on the strengths that are of the relationship become even more complex, and therefore the results of the analysis become even more questionable.

Assumption of Homoscedasticity:

Homoscedasticity means that the variance of the errors across all the levels is the same for the independent variable. When the variance of the errors differentiates at the various values of the independent variable, heteroscedasticity is there for indicated. In the words of Berry and Feldman and Stanley Feldman, (1985) heteroscedasticity, where it is slight, have an effect which is little on the tests of significance, howsoever when the heteroscedasticity is marked, this could lead the results to the serious distortion to the findings and weaken the relation seriously, therefore resulting in increasing the possibility of the errors of type 1.

This assumption whereas could be checked by the visual examination of the plot of the residual or errors standardized by the predicted value of the regression standardized. Ideally, the residuals or errors are scattered randomly around 0, providing such a relatively even distribution. Heteroscedasticity whereas is indicated or shown when the residuals are not scattered evenly around the line. There are many different forms which the heteroscedasticity can take, such as a fan-shape or shape of a bow-tie. When the plot of the residuals or errors appears to deviate too much or substantially from the normal, whereas more formal tests with respect to heteroscedasticity should therefore be performed. Possible tests for checking this whereas are Goldfeld-Quandt test where the term of error either decreases consistently or increases consistently since the value of the dependent variable increases as it is shown in the plot which is fan-shaped, or it can be checked by Glejser tests for the purpose of heteroscedasticity when there are smaller variances in the error term at the central observations as well as larger variance at the extremes of the observations as in the plot shaped in bow-tie

(Berry and Feldman and Stanley Feldman, 1985). In the cases where the skew is present in the independent variables, the transformation of the variables could reduce the heteroscedasticity.

Multicollinearity:

One of the basic three assumptions in the modelling of regression is that the independent variable is not model is not related linearly. The other two assumptions whereas are the model residuals or model errors are distributed normally with the zero mean and with constant variances and these also do not have autocorrelation. The existence whereas of the linear relationship among those which are independent variables is called as multicollinearity. The term multicollinearity where is due to Ranger Frisch (Joreskog, 1971). Multicollinearity whereas could cause large forecasting error and make it difficult to assess the importance which is relative to the variables in the model. If two variables or more variables have a relationship which is linear between them, then it is said that there exists perfect multicollinearity. The consequences of multicollinearity are:

- 1- In the model of two-variable when the multicollinearity is present, the standard of error estimated for the coefficient would be large. The reason for this is because in the formula of variance coefficient there is a multiplying factor in the format of $1/(1-r^2)$, where r is the coefficient of correlation between two of the variables and its value falls whereas between -1 and $+1$. The factor whereas is often called variance inflation factor. There is no multicollinearity when $r=0$, and the factor of inflation equals to value 1. As the r increases in absolute terms, the variances for the coefficients estimated increase as well. As r approaches to $+1$, the factor of inflation at that time reaches to infinity.
- 2- The coefficients estimated might become insignificant or have signs wrong and consequently will also be sensitive to the changes in the data. This is because of the reason that when the independent variables are correlated, the standard errors estimated for the coefficients would be at large and because of the t -statistics would be smaller. The coefficients estimated with a large standard of the errors would be unstable; an addition if done to the few more points of data to the sample would cause a change which is larger in the size of the coefficients and sometimes if the coefficient signs. When any of the coefficients change the size from positive sign to negative sign or from negative sign to positive sign at the updating model, the model would then not produce a good forecast.

- 3- When the coefficients estimated have larger errors of standard and these are unstable, it would then be difficult for the user of the model to assess properly the importance relative of the variables independent.
- 4- The presence of the multicollinearity whereas could lead the researcher to drop a variable which is important from the model because of the t-statistic low.

5.7. Hypothesis Testing

To conduct the mediation analysis, regression analysis has been used. Further, the approach used is Baron and Kenny (1986) that provides four-step process to find out the mediation of the variables.

Baron and Kenny 1986 Mediation Steps

Figure redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Baron, R. and Kenny, D. 1986. The moderator -mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), pp.1173-1182.

5.7.1. Model 1: Social Media technology Use → Brand Equity → Performance

Table 6: Model 1: Social Media technology Use → Brand Equity → Performance

Step	Description	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig.	Constant	B	Std. Error
1	STU → FP	0.270	0.073	0.069	0.001	2.913	0.247	0.059
2	STU → BE	0.065	0.004	0.001	0.311	3.095	0.58	0.059
3	BE → FP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

4	STU → BE → FP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
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Mediation is not possible as the step 2 does not demonstrate a significant relationship. To understand completely the relationship, it is essential to address the effect that social media technology use exercises on the performance of the firm about brand equity. Therefore it has been tested with the use of brand equity's effect of mediation as followed by the Baron and Kenny (1986), performing the four-step analysis. Mediators whereas provide information which is additional about how two variables or why two variables are linked or associated. The analysis whereas is carried out in four different steps. Since we are already aware of the fact that social media technology use has on the performance of the firm since the significance is shown in the table as 0.001. the second step whereas is to find out the effect of the social media technology use on the brand equity where brand equity is in the role of the mediator. The table above whereas indicate there is not a significant relationship between both social media technology use and brand equity since the significance value came as 0.311. Since the value of significance for social media technology use and brand equity is not significant, therefore we will not proceed with the performing further significance.

5.7.2. Model 2: Social Media technology Use → Marketing Capabilities → Performance

Table 7: Model 2: Social Media technology Use → Marketing Capabilities → Performance

Step	Description	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig.	Constant	B	Std. Error
1	STU → FP	0.270	0.073	0.069	0.001	2.913	0.247	0.059
2	STU → MC	0.131	0.017	0.013	0.050	3.716	0.089	0.045
3	MC → FP	0.392	0.154	0.150	0.001	1.831	0.527	0.083
4	STU → MC → FP	0.450	0.202	0.195	0.001	1.100	0.488	0.081

For the second model as well, the figure above makes use of three different regression equations to test for the significance statistically of the effect to the mediator. The first equation whereas

shows the significant predictor with regards to the mediator variable, the second equation whereas shows that the independent variable is the predictor significant of the variable outcome. The third equation shows the mediator is the predictor of the dependent variable and lastly the fourth equation shows that the independent variable as well as the mediator variable both entered simultaneously with the dependent or outcome variable. It is said that the two conditions should be met in the third equation if the mediator effect is supposed to be present. (a) the mediator is the significant predictor of the dependent or outcome variable and (b) the direct relationship of the independent variable to the outcome variable is significantly less than it was in the second equation (Baron and Kenny, 1986).

As in the first three-step, the p-value is less than 0.05 which means the mediation of marketing capabilities exists. Moving to step 4, multiple regression analysis has been conducted that shows the path b is still significant (means the effect of marketing capabilities on firm performance) remains significant. Also, the effect of social media technology use on firm performance is significant when marketing capabilities are controlled. All these effects show there is *partial mediation*.

5.7.3. Model 3: Social Media technology Use → Customer Orientation → Performance

Table 8: Model 3: Social Media technology Use → Customer Orientation → Performance

Step	Description	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig.	Constant	B	Std. Error
1	STU → FP	0.270	0.073	0.069	0.001	2.913	0.247	0.059
2	STU → CO	0.279	0.078	0.074	0.001	3.490	0.237	0.055
3	CO → FP	0.377	0.142	0.139	0.001	2.151	0.407	0.067
4	STU → CO → FP	0.415	0.172	0.164	0.001	1.678	0.354	0.069

For the third model, the figure above shows the use of three different equations of regression to evaluate the test for the statistical significance to the mediator, its effect on the independent variable as well as a dependent variable. Equations presented in table 7 shows four different equations for a mediator, its intervention and significance. The first equation whereas shows the predictor being significant between the use of social media technology and firm performance. The second equation shows the independent variable social media technology use, and the mediator predictor customer orientation has a significant relationship. The third equation whereas shows that customer orientation has a significant relationship with the firm performance. Lastly, the intervention of customer orientation being the mediator in the relationship of an independent variable and dependent variable shows a significant relation statistically. It is said that the two conditions should be met in the third equation if the mediator effect is supposed to be present. (a) the mediator is the significant predictor of the dependent or outcome variable and (b) the direct relationship of the independent variable to the outcome variable is significantly less than it was in the second equation (Baron and Kenny, 1986).

As in the first three-step, the p-value is less than 0.05 which means the mediation of customer orientation exists. Moving to step 4, multiple regression analysis has been conducted that shows the path b is still significant (means the effect of customer orientation on firm performance) remains significant. Also, the effect of social media technology use on firm performance is significant when customer orientation is controlled. All these effects show there is *partial mediation*.

5.7.4. Hypotheses Test Summary

In this section, the hypotheses test summary is presented based on the data analysis conducted earlier. The test summary helps to understand the accepted and rejected hypotheses followed by detailed interpretation of the results.

Table 9: Hypotheses Test Summary

Hypotheses	Details	Statistics	Result
H1	STU → FP	r = 0.363 (p-value < 0.05)	Accepted
H2	STU → BE	r = -0.033 (p-value > 0.05)	Rejected
H3	BE → FP	r = 0.509 (p-value < 0.05)	Accepted
H4	STU → BE → FP	Sig-value is not significant in regression analysis (STU → BE)	Rejected
H5	STU → MC	r = 0.244 (p-value < 0.05)	Accepted

H6	MC → FP	r = 0.392 (p-value < 0.05)	Accepted
H7	STU → MC → FP	p-value is significant for all three possible paths means some form of mediation exists, further STU → FP remains significant while MC is controlled showing <i>partial mediation</i>	Accepted
H8	STU → CO	r = 0.384 (p-value < 0.05)	Accepted
H9	CO → FP	r = 0.377 (p-value < 0.05)	Accepted
H10	STU → CO → FP	p-value is significant for all three possible paths means some form of mediation exists, further STU → FP remains significant while CO is controlled showing <i>partial mediation</i>	Accepted

Hypothesis 1: Use of social media technology has a positive effect on the performance of the firm:

The relationship whereas between the use of social media technology and the performance of the firm has been tested with the use of simple linear regression model. Table 5 above shows the summary of the model, where it does provide the value of both R and R². The value of R whereas represents the correlation which is simple and is 0.270 where it shows or indicates the weak degree of correlation. The value of R² (known as R-square) indicates or shows how much of the total variation could be explained where the value of it found through regression analysis is 7.3%, where it is weak and not normal. In addition to this, the value of p-value is 0.001 where it is less than 0.05 recommended which indicates that the regression model with the prediction of mediator shows outcome significantly well. The value of p-value 0.001 where it is less than 0.05 shows that the model advised is statistically significant and good fit. The table shows the beta coefficient where they are used to interpret the significance as well as the intensity of the impact of the variables of a predictor on the dependent variable. The results whereas show that the beta coefficient under the unstandardized coefficients is 0.247 and the p-value or significance is 0.001 where it is lesser than 0.05. Where the equation implies that the change of 1 unit in social media technology use will bring 0.247 positive change in performance of the firm and the relation is significant statistically.

Hypothesis 2: Use of social media technology has a positive effect on brand equity:

The relationship whereas between the use of social media technology and the brand equity has been tested with the use of simple linear regression model. Table 5 above shows the summary of the model, where it does provide the value of both R and R². The value of R whereas represents the correlation which is simple and is 0.065 where it shows or indicates the weak degree of correlation. The value of R² (known as R-square) indicates or shows how much of the total variation could be explained where the value of it found through regression analysis is 4%, where it is weak and not normal. In addition to this, the value of p-value is 0.311 where it is higher than 0.05 recommended which indicates that the regression model with the prediction of a mediator does not show outcome significantly well. The value of p-value 0.311 where it is higher than 0.05 shows that the model advised is not statistically significant and bad fit. The table shows the beta coefficient where they are used to interpret the significance as well as the intensity of the impact of the variables of the predictor on the dependent variable. The results whereas show that the beta coefficient under the unstandardized coefficients is 0.58 and the p-value or significance is 0.311 where it is higher than 0.05. Where the equation implies that the change of 1 unit in social media technology use will bring 0.58 positive change in performance of the firm and the relation is not significant statistically since the p-value is more than the recommended value of 0.05.

Hypothesis 3: Brand equity has a positive effect on the performance of the firm:

The relationship between brand equity and the performance of the firm has been tested with the use of a simple linear regression model. Table 6 above shows the summary of the model, where it does provide the value of both R and R². The value of R whereas represents the correlation which is simple and is 0.393 where it shows or indicates the weak degree of correlation. The value of R² (known as R-square) indicates or shows how much of the total variation could be explained where the value of it found through regression analysis is 15.5%, where it is weak and not normal. In addition to this, the value of p-value is 0.001 where it is less than 0.05 recommended which indicates that the regression model with the prediction of mediator shows outcome significantly well. The value of p-value 0.001 where it is less than 0.05 shows that the model advised is statistically significant and good fit. The table shows the beta coefficient where they are used to interpret the significance as well as the intensity of the impact of the variables of the predictor on the dependent variable. The results whereas show that the beta coefficient under the unstandardized coefficients is 0.407 and the p-value or significance is 0.001 where it is lesser than 0.05. Where the equation implies that the change

of 1 unit in social media technology use will bring 0.407 positive change in performance of the firm and the relation is significant statistically.

Hypothesis 4: Use of social media technology along with mediator brand equity has a positive effect on the performance of the firm:

The relationship among the use of social media technology along with the intervention of brand equity being the mediator on the firm performance being the dependent variable does not have any effect. Based on the hypothesis model 1 presented in table 6, the second step hypothesis failed since the relation between the use of social media technology on brand equity is not significant. Therefore, the impact of the use of social media technology with the intervention of brand equity mediators on firm performance has not been calculated.

Hypothesis 5: Use of social media technology has a positive effect on the marketing capabilities being mediator:

The relationship between independent variable use of social media technology and the mediator marketing capabilities has been tested using the model of linear regression. Table 6 above summarize the relationship between the use of social media technology and marketing capabilities. Where the table above provides the value of R and R². Where R is the value of the degree of correlation and which is calculated for the relationship as 0.131 which indicates that there are a weaker relationship and weaker degree of correlation. The value of R² whereas known as R-Square tells how much of the total variation could be explained, where the value of R² is 1.7%, which is a weak relationship and not normal. Moreover, the value of p-value which is also referred to as significance is 0.05 which is equal to the recommended value of p-value 0.05 which tells that the regression model because of the prediction of the mediator marketing capabilities shows the outcome as significantly well. Since the value of p-value is set at 0.05, therefore, is considered as the model which is advised is a good fit and a statistically significant model. The table also shows the value of the beta coefficient where the beta coefficient is used to interpret the intensity as well as the significance of the impact with regards to the variable of the predictor of a mediator. The result for the beta coefficient whereas shows that the beta coefficient is yet under the coefficient where it is unstandardized at 0.089 along with the value of p-value at 0.05 considered as significant. The equation, therefore, implies that the change in one use of social media technology will bring 0.089 units of positive change in the performance to the firm and the relationship is considered as statistically significant.

Hypothesis 6: Use of marketing capabilities has a positive effect on the performance of the firm:

The relationship between the use of marketing capabilities being the mediator on the firm performance being the dependent variable has a positive effect where this has been tested using the model of linear regression. Table 6 summarize the relationship between the use of marketing capabilities and performance of the firm. Where the table above provides the value of R and R2. Where R is the value of the degree of correlation and which is calculated for the relationship as 0.392 which indicates that there is a moderate relationship and moderate degree of correlation. The value of R2 whereas known as R-Square tells how much of the total variation could be explained, where the value of R2 is 15.4%, which is a moderate relationship and not normal. Moreover, the value of p-value which is also referred to as significance is 0.01 which is lesser to the recommended value of p-value 0.05 which tells that the regression model because of the prediction of the mediator marketing capabilities shows the outcome as significantly well. Since the value of p-value is still at 0.01, therefore, is considered as the model which is advised is a good fit and a statistically significant model. The table also shows the value of the beta coefficient where the beta coefficient is used to interpret the intensity as well as the significance of the impact with regards to the variable of the predictor of a mediator. The result for the beta coefficient whereas shows that the beta coefficient is yet under the coefficient where it is unstandardized at 0.527 along with the value of p-value at 0.01 considered as significant. The equation, therefore, implies that the change in one unit of marketing capabilities will bring 0.527 units of positive change in the performance to the firm and the relationship is considered as statistically significant.

Hypothesis 7: Use of social media technology along with mediator marketing capabilities has a positive effect on the performance of the firm:

The relationship between the use of social media technology along with the intervention of marketing capabilities being the mediator on the firm performance being the dependent variable has a positive effect where this has been tested using the model of linear regression. Table 6 summarize the relationship between the use of social media technology along with the intervention of marketing capabilities being a mediator on the performance of the firm. Where the table above provides the value of R and R2. Where R is the value of the degree of correlation and which is calculated for the relationship as 0.450 which indicates that there is a moderate relationship and moderate degree of correlation. The value of R2 whereas known as R-Square

tells how much of the total variation could be explained, where the value of R² is 20.2%, which is a moderate relationship and normal. Moreover, the value of p-value which is also referred to as significance is 0.01 which is lesser to the recommended value of p-value 0.05 which tells that the regression model because of the prediction of the mediator marketing capabilities shows the outcome as significantly well. Since the value of p-value is still at 0.01, therefore, is considered as the model which is advised is a good fit and a statistically significant model. The table also shows the value of the beta coefficient where the beta coefficient is used to interpret the intensity as well as the significance of the impact with regards to the variable of the predictor of the mediator. The result for the beta coefficient whereas shows that the beta coefficient is yet under the coefficient where it is unstandardized at 0.488 along with the value of p-value at 0.01 considered as significant. The equation, therefore, implies that the change in one unit of use of social media technology along with the intervention of marketing capabilities will bring 0.488 units of positive change in the performance to the firm and the relationship is considered as statistically significant.

Hypothesis 8: Use of social media technology has a positive effect on customer orientation:

The relationship between the use of social media technology being the independent variable on the customer orientation being the mediator variable has a positive effect where this has been tested using the model of linear regression. Table 7 summarizes the relationship between the use of social media technology and customer orientation. Where the table above provides the value of R and R². Where R is the value of the degree of correlation and which is calculated for the relationship as 0.279 which indicates that there is a weak relationship and a weaker degree of correlation. The value of R² whereas known as R-Square tells how much of the total variation could be explained, where the value of R² is 7.8%, which is a weaker relationship and normal. Moreover, the value of p-value which is also referred to as significance is 0.01 which is lesser to the recommended value of p-value 0.05 which tells that the regression model because of the prediction of the mediator customer orientation shows the outcome as significantly well. Since the value of p-value is still at 0.01, therefore, is considered as the model which is advised is a good fit and a statistically significant model. The table also shows the value of the beta coefficient where the beta coefficient is used to interpret the intensity as well as the significance of the impact with regards to the variable of the predictor of the mediator. The result for the beta coefficient whereas shows that the beta coefficient is yet under the coefficient where it is unstandardized at 0.237 along with the value of p-value at 0.01 considered as significant. The equation, therefore, implies that the change in one unit of social

media technology will bring 0.237 units of positive change in the customer orientation and the relationship is considered as statistically significant.

Hypothesis 9: Use of customer orientation has a positive effect on the performance of the firm being the dependent variable:

The relationship between mediator customer orientation and the dependent variable performance of the firm has been tested using the model of linear regression. Table 7 above summarize the relationship between the use of customer orientation and performance of the firm. Where the table above provides the value of R and R². Where R is the value of the degree of correlation and which is calculated for the relationship as 0.377 which indicates that there is a moderate relationship and moderate degree of correlation. The value of R² whereas known as R-Square tells how much of the total variation could be explained, where the value of R² is 14.2%, which is the moderate relationship and normal. Moreover, the value of p-value which is also referred to as significance is 0.01 which is lesser to the recommended value of p-value 0.05 which tells that the regression model because of the prediction of the mediator customer orientation shows the outcome as significantly well. Since the value of p-value is still at 0.01, therefore, is considered as the model which is advised is a good fit and a statistically significant model. The table also shows the value of the beta coefficient where the beta coefficient is used to interpret the intensity as well as the significance of the impact with regards to the variable of the predictor of the mediator. The result for the beta coefficient whereas shows that the beta coefficient is yet under the coefficient where it is unstandardized at 0.354 along with the value of p-value at 0.01 considered as significant. The equation, therefore, implies that the change in one use of customer orientation will bring 0.354 units of positive change in the performance to the firm and the relationship is considered as statistically significant.

Hypothesis 10: Use of social media technology along with mediator customer orientation has a positive effect on the performance of the firm:

The relationship between the use of social media technology along with the intervention of customer orientation being the mediator on the firm performance being the dependent variable has a positive effect where this has been tested using the model of linear regression. The table summarizes the relationship between the use of social media technology along with the intervention of customer orientation being a mediator on the performance of the firm. Where the table above provides the value of R and R². Where R is the value of the degree of correlation and which is calculated for the relationship as 0.415 which indicates that there is a moderate

relationship and moderate degree of correlation. The value of R² whereas known as R-Square tells how much of the total variation could be explained, where the value of R² is 17.2%, which is a moderate relationship and normal. Moreover, the value of p-value which is also referred to as significance is 0.01 which is lesser to the recommended value of p-value 0.05 which tells that the regression model because of the prediction of the mediator customer orientation shows the outcome as significantly well. Since the value of p-value is still at 0.01, therefore, is considered as the model which is advised is a good fit and a statistically significant model. The table also shows the value of the beta coefficient where the beta coefficient is used to interpret the intensity as well as the significance of the impact with regards to the variable of the predictor of the mediator. The result for the beta coefficient whereas shows that the beta coefficient is yet under the coefficient where it is unstandardized at 0.354 along with the value of p-value at 0.01 considered as significant. The equation, therefore, implies that the change in one unit of use of social media technology along with the intervention of customer orientation will bring 0.354 units of positive change in the performance to the firm and the relationship is considered as statistically significant.

5.8. Discussion on Results

In this model, we have examined and evaluated the impact of the use of social media technology on the performance of the firm. Therefore, we take a comprehensive approach to factors affecting such performance. Do brand equity, marketing activities or customer orientation have an impact or influence on social media marketing use on the performance of the firm? Based on primary as well as secondary data, it is seen that the use of social media marketing technology impacts firms' performance.

First, from the research, we conclude that the addition of brand equity with the use of social media marketing does not have a significant positive influence on firms' performance. These findings contradict previous studies and arguments which claim that brand equity, along with the use of social media marketing, has a positive impact on firms' performance. Second, it is concluded that marketing activities using social media technology create a positive impact on the performance of the firm. Lastly, it is concluded that customer orientation creates a positive impact on the performance of the firm using social media marketing.

In recent years, the use of digital media and social media marketing among the population, in general, has become ubiquitous. Consumers nowadays are spending more time using the range of different media that are available digitally to gain information as well as to communicate.

Among the different formats of digital media, one form, namely social media, is of particular interest to marketers. Consumers in today's world do not only learn about different services and products from their family, friends or strangers; they are now also able to share the experiences they have had with services or products with the world. This has created interest amongst marketing managers, as these managers wrestle to understand fully how the content of social media has an impact on the bottom lines of business.

The relationship between social media marketing and firm performance is based on the idea that comments on social media and the sentiments expressed in these comments will have an influence or impact on the mindsets of other consumers of the given firm. Whether the consumer's mindset is negative or positive, it should then influence his or her decision about the purchase of services or products from the organization. This decision whereas affects how the firm's products perform in the marketplace, which ultimately impacts the firm's financial performance in terms of the generation of cash flow or stock market returns. Previous research in the context of online user-generated content and its impact on firms' performance has focused on specific types of content generated by consumers, such as users' reviews, blog posts, or ratings on the performance of a firm. However, a bigger portion of the content generated by users online is in the form of social media communications, which have not been studied. This dissertation has focused on bridging this gap by examining the relationship between the various factors and whether they affect the performance of a firm, namely brand equity, marketing activities and consumer orientation.

5.8.1. Use of social media technology effect on firm performance:

From research has shown that the use of social media technology has a positive effect on firms' performance. It thus concurs with other studies that conclude that technology can improve businesses' processes and performance (Gera and Gu, 2004; Paniagua and Sapena, 2014; Hakala and Kohtamäki, 2011). Some researchers have found that corporate adoption of social media does provide benefits, while several others have identified a positive relationship between the adoption of social media and corporate performance (Ainin et al., 2015; Paniagua and Sapena, 2014; Parveen et al., 2014; Rodriguez et al., 2012). In addition to this, Rodriguez et al. (2015) also found that the use of social media had positive effects on customer-facing activities and therefore on sales performance. Moreover, Ferrer et al. (2013) found that the adoption of social media positively affected the social capital of organizations, which in turn affected their performance. Both Kwok and Yu (2013) and Wong (2012) also found that the adoption of Facebook had a positive effect on the sales performance of SMEs. Moreover,

Hassan et al. (2015) noted that social media could have a significant impact on business by influencing purchasing decisions. The following studies are consistent with the previous literature on technology adoption, which found that such adoption had a positive impact on performance both financially and non-financially (Damanpour et al., 1989; Scupola and Nicolajsen, 2013; Thong, 2001; Tushman and Nadler, 1986; Zhu et al., 2003).

The result also has similarities with the findings of Cervellon and Galipienzo (2015) and Garrido-Moreno and Lockett (2016), who found that social media had a positive effect in improving firms' success and performance. In addition to this, a study conducted by Schniederjans, Cao and Schniederjans (2013) highlighted a positive effect of the use of social media on firms' financial performance. Moreover, the results found in the current study are comparable to the findings of Harris et al. (2012), who argued that SMEs use a combination of both offline and online networks for business activities such as sales and marketing. Their research revealed that participants were interested in both online and offline networks. By using the internet, several different companies considerably reduced the cost of international business and increasing their ability to flexibly respond to the opportunities of the new international market as well as the needs of foreign customers. The internet also offers the possibility to provide targeted information to specific customers and other stakeholders of the organization and to obtain feedback from those stakeholders and customers (Biloslavo and Trnavcevic, 2009).

With regard to this, social media profoundly contribute towards a radical transformation of the practices of marketing, e-business and customer behaviour. Social media applications such as social networking sites, blogs, discussion forums and communities created by users have been transformed from customer-specific completely to the tools of customer-centric that allow organizations to participate in the interactions of network members (Trainor, 2012; Trainor et al., 2014). As argued by Deighton and Kornfeld (2009), because social media enables a substantial increase in customers' power, the use of marketing strategies that engage social media is a logical choice for business. There are numerous indications that the impact of the social web is very important or significant in several areas of business, particularly in the marketing area of the communication and innovation of products (Kim and Bae, 2008; Piller and Walcher, 2006). In the literature related to export, many authors agree that IT and internet capability are essential to new international ventures as well as internationalizing SMEs, particularly firms which have fewer financial and physical resources, enabling them to perform earlier and more successfully abroad (Gabrielsson and Gabrielsson, 2011; Loane, 2006;

Mathews and Healy, 2007; Mostafa et al., 2006; Sinkovics et al., 2013; Zhand and Tansuhaj, 2007; Zhang et al., 2013).

5.8.2. Use of social media technology and brand equity:

This research found that social media technology does not have a significant impact on organizations' brand equity. According to a study conducted by Hutagalung and Situmorang (2018), however, social media has a positive and a significant impact on brand equity. This indicates that as increasing numbers of entrepreneurs promote their products or services through social media, it will help in growing their brands. Social media will generate awareness of the brand so that more customers know about the product. Hardeep and Rani (2017) found that social media engagement has a significant impact on customer-based brand equity. Customer-based brand equity has four different dimensions: brand image, brand awareness, brand loyalty and perceived quality. Erdogmus and Cicek (2012) also found from their research that social media marketing has a positive impact towards customers' brand loyalty. Their results showed that consumers' brand loyalty is positively affected when the brand offers popular or relevant content or advantageous campaigns. Social media also have a significant and positive relationship to equity, meaning that if the if equity increases, then social media use will also increase. This means that entrepreneurs should build a connection to consumers. Consumers who are interested in a company's products are likely to follow its social media. These findings are in line with the research of Kim and Ko (2010), who found that social media marketing positively influenced purchase intentions and customer relationships.

According to the research carried out by Nyairo (2016), the use of social media enhances the equity of the brand. Firstly, the social media exposes the brand to a global audience, which results in widening their reach. Nyairo's findings indicated that social media are an effective tool for communication and provides a cost-effective means for advertising. Social media are accessible and easy to use, unlike the traditional media, and are a good source of sales leads. The impact of social media marketing on brand equity has been examined in several different studies (Naveed, 2012). According to Naveed (2012), social media have been identified as having an influence on brand image, whereas traditional media focus on brand awareness. Further to this, social media as an element in the communication mix has a significant impact on brand equity (Godey et al., 2016). This relationship has been tested in a study conducted by Jayasuriya, Azam and Ferdous (2017), in which brand equity was measured based on Keller's components. Brand image and brand awareness were also considered, and the researchers also invited future researchers to incorporate the other components of brand equity as well.

Economic crises encourage companies to study the connections between consumers and luxury brands in greater depths. Consumers buy luxury products for two core reasons: for their pleasure and as symbols of their success. Kapferer (2009) maintains that the future of luxury brands depends on the balance between these two different kinds of motivations. The balance may vary with regard to different geographical areas, such as in countries where luxury brands are a more recent phenomenon (Kapferer, 2009). In addition to this, consumers also often buy luxury products as gifts. A brand may influence the customers' perceptions and attitudes in several ways, including brand awareness, preference for the brand and perceptions about brand image. In social media settings, marketing activities enhance customer-based brand equity (Bruhn et al., 2012; Kim and Ko, 2012). In the words of Mangold and Faulds (2009), the actions of social media marketing are part of the promotional mix in a brand new communication paradigm. Bruhn et al. (2012) also disclose that both traditional communication and social media communication have a significant impact on brand equity. Traditional media have a stronger impact on brand awareness, while social media communication strongly influences the brand image.

From all the research done in the past, it has been found that social media marketing has a positive influence on brand equity, whereas the present study, carried out in the clothing sector, did not find a significant relationship between social media marketing and brand equity.

SMTU → BE

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.065 ^a	.004	.000	.624

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.370	1	.370	.950	.331 ^b
	Residual	86.469	222	.390		
	Total	86.839	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Brand Equity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		

1	(Constant)	3.095	.263		11.766	.000
	Social Media Technology Use	.058	.059	.065	.975	.331

a. Dependent Variable: Brand Equity

5.8.3. Brand equity and firm performance:

The present study found no significant relationship between brand equity and firm performance. In contrast, according to Morgan et al. (2009) and Madden, Fehle and Fournier (2006), brand equity is a strong antecedent of firm performance, but various types of competitive advantages exist in the functions other than marketing, such as the unit cost of manufacturing, management leadership strategy, turnover of inventory, and flexibility to change the volume, delivery, or access to the working capital (Saeidi et al., 2015). Even if strong brand equity exists, some of the desired performance outcomes might not result, because of technological or market changes or poor execution of marketing programs. Feng, Morgan and Rego (2015) contend that brand equity depends on the firm's capabilities to maintain and improve its equity in the longer run, where it may acquire trade-offs in the short-term profitability of the firm and the cash flows. The authors also highlighted the role of leveraging the capabilities for the transformation of brand equity into superior firm performance.

Even though brand equity could not be the sole driver of firm performance, as its effects are contingent on the market forces as well as on the firm, it nevertheless has great strategic importance, because of the dynamic capabilities of marketing, resulting from the interactions of stakeholders and embodied in the brand equity, which could improve firm performance (Vorhies et al., 2011; Morgan et al., 2009). A firm that is better able to absorb and manage new knowledge of the market and also to make use of that knowledge is likely to reconfigure its organizational resources and change its routines and processes (Barrales-Molina et al., 2014). As an example, innovation capabilities and their effects, in addition to learning capabilities, could improve the speed, effectiveness, and efficiency of new product development and the processes of supply chain management, therefore eventually improving the performance of the firm (Ngo and O'Cass, 2012; Bruni and Verona, 2009; Olavarrieta and Friedmann, 2008). In addition to this, firms that can collaborate successfully with the multitude regarding stakeholders and integrate these stakeholders' intelligence are more likely to identify and respond to opportunities through new services, products and process, which may increase their revenue (Weerawardena, O'Cass and Julian, 2006; Ayuso et al., 2006; Dangelico et al., 2013).

BE → FP

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.393 ^a	.155	.151	.595

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Equity

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.389	1	14.389	40.636	.000 ^b
	Residual	78.607	222	.354		
	Total	92.996	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Equity

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.633	.217		12.106	.000
	Brand Equity	.407	.064	.393	6.375	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

5.8.4. Marketing capabilities and firm performance:

The present study found a significant positive relationship between marketing capabilities and firm performance. The relationship between marketing capabilities and firm performance has received heightened research attention in recent years (Krasnikov and Jayachandran, 2008; Morgan et al., 2009; Murray et al., 2011; Vorhies et al., 2009). Overall, the findings of the aforementioned studies support that there is a positive significant relationship between capabilities and performance, which is consistent across diverse research contexts (Krasnikov and Jayachandran, 2008). Conceptually, the relationship is based on the recognition that capabilities encompass skills that are deeply embedded in organizations' routines and practices and represent knowledge that has been accumulated over a number of years. As a result, these capabilities are difficult to imitate, trade or duplicate, and represent a sustainable source of competitive advantage (Day, 1994; Teece et al., 1997). In addition to this, marketing capabilities also enable firms to effectively implement their strategic orientations, which are

designed to match the marketing conditions they face and achieve their specific performance objectives (Morgan et al., 2009).

Based on the research carried out by Krasnikov and Jayachandran (2008), marketing capability is one of the driving forces when the firm is operating in a dynamic environment. Firstly, according to these authors, the association between marketing capabilities and firm performance is stronger in turbulent industries in comparison to those that are stable. On the other hand, when conditions outside the firm have higher uncertainty, firms rely more on their abilities to organize their resources and detect opportunities earlier than their competitors, as well as creating better market situations and maintaining their relationships with customers. Relying on their abilities such as marketing capabilities, firms could make their future more profitable and more predictable in a dynamic environment. Secondly, the role of environmental dynamism is interesting as well. Sun (2010) found that firms that have low levels of marketing capabilities would be hurt by the dynamism of the environment and their performance would be lower in stable environments, whereas higher marketing capability makes improved or better use of dynamism to turn an unfavourable situation into one that is more favourable. This dichotomy of low state in comparison to high state is that a dynamic environment supports the beneficial role of marketing capability, as described in dynamic capability theory and in resource theory.

Research by Sun (2010) showed that in industries where there are lower complexities, marketing capability is only marginally associated with performance, whereas in industries with higher complexity, where there is greater competition, marketing capabilities are strongly connected with the performance of the firm. As per the research conducted by Salisu Abu-Bakr and Rani (2017), marketing capability is an essential factor that contributes towards the attainment of the performance of the firm. The result from their research is in line with previous studies (Boachie-Mensah and Acquah, 2015; Hassan et al., 2013; Saunila and Ukko, 2013).

Similarly, Day (1994), Hunt and Morgan (1995), Song et al. (2008) and Vorhies and Morgan (2005) have also emphasized the role of marketing capabilities to achieve and sustain competitive advantage. Griffith, Yalcinkaya and Calantone (2010) defined marketing capabilities as the firm's ability to integrate its skills, collective knowledge and resources to respond effectively to changes in the market's needs and to meet the competitive pressure. They argued that marketing capabilities could be a joint process to bring tangible and intangible resources together to create valuable outcomes. These capabilities are considered as unique

because the individuals combine their collective knowledge and skills through their past experiences to achieve, for example, new product development, selling, and distribution. As a result of this, marketing capabilities could not be imitated easily by the competitors, and thus can provide sustainable competitive advantage (Grant, 1996). Moreover, Hunt and Morgan (1995) also argue that in the resources the comparative advantage which then can translate this comparative advantage into the marketplace and finally into the financial performance is superior. Based on this argument, through the leveraging and development of its resources, the firm establishes a specific set of capabilities known as marketing capabilities, which allow it to accomplish performance at a higher level. Hunt and Morgan (1995) have also conceptualized the performance of such firms as being superior, implying that the firm seeks a level of performance which exceeds that of all its referents.

The findings also support the arguments of Hult et al. (2007) and Capelleras et al. (2008) that the structure and processes of businesses are not bound by the unique contexts of institutions.

5.8.5. Mediating role of marketing capabilities:

This study has found that marketing capabilities play a positive and significant mediating role between social media technology and firms' performance. Organizational capabilities are identified as the main or core determinants of the performance of a business and for achieving competitive advantage (Wong and Karia, 2010). The resource-based view suggests that inter-firm capabilities, such as marketing, technology and operational capabilities, are the main elements with regards to the success of the organization (Barney, 2001). Various prior studies reveal that marketing capabilities are among the most decisive drivers with regard to firm performance (Su et al., 2013). Therefore, marketing capabilities are considered as inimitable (Bharadwaj et al., 1993), immobile (Capron and Hulland, 1999), and non-substitutable (Moorman and Rust, 1999). In addition to this, it is also claimed that the firms with greater marketing capabilities could obtain sustainable competitive advantage and superior performance (Wong and Karia, 2010). Morgan et al. (2009) revealed that planning and implementation of marketing, as two of the elements of marketing capabilities, have a positive influence on performance. On the flip side, Morgan (2012) argued that the marketing capabilities of a firm have a direct as well as a complementary impact on growth with regard to the firm's profit. Moreover, Chang et al. (2010), who investigated the mediating role between social media technology and performance, revealed that marketing capabilities positively mediate the relationship between firm performance and social media technology. In

addition to this, Ahmed et al. (2014) found that marketing capabilities contribute towards the improvement of firms' performance outcomes in different economic conditions.

When organizations are embedded within networks, they can create links with their customers as well as with other businesses. Social media provides the opportunity for small businesses to make stronger networks and to improve their capabilities to create an effect on their performance (Gensler et al., 2013). It has also been argued that one of the most significant models for firms to use to obtain competitive advantage is the improvement of their networks (Boso et al., 2013). Online marketing, such as social media marketing, impacts on the performance of the firm by developing strong relationships with the client firm, as well as influencing customers' purchase intentions and accessing shared knowledge (Walter et al., 2006). Based on the research by Tajvidi and Karami (2017), the effect of marketing capabilities on the performance of firms in the hotel industry continue to lag (Leonidou et al., 2013; Odoom et al., 2017; Ramanathan et al., 2016). Also, several prior studies have focused on marketing capabilities at mid-level as components of the marketing mix (Aaker, 1996; Ahmed et al., 2014; Keller, 1993; Su et al., 2013) rather than on marketing capabilities at a higher level (Merrilees et al., 2011). The findings of the present study are consistent with several previous studies (Martínez-Roman et al., 2015; Merrilees et al., 2011; Michaelidou et al., 2011; Yu et al., 2014).

5.8.6. Customer orientation effect on firm performance:

This research has found a positive and significant relationship between customer orientation and firm performance. This relationship is moderately positive because of human leadership. Customer orientation is particularly important with respect to enabling the firm to understand the marketplace as well as to develop appropriate product and service strategies to meet customers' needs and requirements (Liu et al., 2003), which further translates into performance. Ambler (1999) and Bitner et al. (1990) found a positive relationship between market orientation and performance in the market. Kennedy et al. (2002) also recommended that the development and implementation of customer orientation is an impetus for the positioning of the organization in the marketplace. This position is supported by an array of different studies that confirm significant associations between the customer orientation regarding the firm and both financial and market performance. Therefore, it is also believed that the element of customer orientation puts the customer at the centre with regard to its operation and sees that customers have their reasons for being in the business, while firms deliver services and goods to meet these needs. Customers are likely to patronize products or

services where they are borne out of their needs, resulting in translation into sales growth and therefore the performance of the firm.

Because of globalization, much pressure has been exerted on firms. To win business, there is a constant and consistent demand for them to focus on customers' needs and to provide quality in the services and products they offer. Customer orientation therefore does matter, since it is an internal capability that is expected to be shown or demonstrated in smaller businesses (Thomas et al., 2011; Tsiotsou and Ratten, 2010). With respect to the resource-based view, this capability contributes towards the competitive advantage as well as the profitability of the organization (Barney, 1991). A customer-centric view is linked with gathering of first-hand customer information (Shaw et al., 2011) and identifying and closing service gaps (Altinay, 2010). Tajeddini (2010) also showed that entrepreneurial orientation, customer orientation and innovativeness all have a positive impact on the performance of the firm. Tajeddini and Trueman (2012) have also reached a similar conclusion in their study with smaller retailers in Switzerland.

The link between customer orientation and firms' performance has been investigated in a number of studies, which have mainly focused on large hospitality enterprises, manufacturing firms and organizations in the service sectors (Tang, 2014; Cheng and Krumwiede, 2012). Customer orientation requires the sellers to understand the value chain with regard to the buyers in order to continuously create superior value (Narver and Slater, 1990). These researchers have postulated that customer orientation in a firm would lead to superior firm performance. This follows from the perspective that focusses on the creation or enabling of customer value, which enables firms to improve customer satisfaction, innovation, and loyalty, as well as subsequent performance and success (Frambach et al., 2016). This view has also been supported by many different studies that have confirmed the existence of a significant positive relationship between customer orientation and SMEs' performance (Asikhia, 2010; Dauda and Akingbade, 2010; Kirca et al., 2005; Neneh, 2016a; Pongwiritthon and Awirothananon, 2014; Smirnova et al., 2011). The customer is the focal point in the strategy of customer-oriented firms, and this improves these firms' opportunity to foster their performance, since their superior treatment of customers could result in the growth of sales. This is because such firms formulate their plans of actions based on market intelligence rather than on verbalized opinions of the customers alone, and ensure that they deliver goods and services to meet their needs (Asikhia, 2010). The strategic moves through which business owners attract customers to buy

their products and services, which are based on customers' needs, translate into sales growth and improvements to overall performance.

5.8.7. Influence of social media marketing on firm performance:

This study conducted an empirical investigation of how social media technology use influences firm performance. The conceptualization of the capability of social media marketing was first developed by using the five aspects with regard to spanning capabilities presented by Day's (1994) strategic framework. In particular, the role or capability of social media marketing was classified into five different dimensions of activities of marketing that are implemented in social media. In addition to this, the overall results with regard to profit or loss analysis, where they are supported by the five dimensions related to the capability of social media marketing, tended to relate differently to the two different aspects of firms' performance. More specifically, Day's (1994) results showed that capabilities of social media product development and the implementation of social media marketing, were significantly and positively related to customer relationship performance and financial performance. The positive contribution of the two different components of the capabilities with respect to both of these aspects of performance have some important implications. First, firms' ability to use social media for the development of new products could allow them to use the information they have gathered from social media to come up with new products to meet customers' demands, thus increasing customer satisfaction and retention (Tuten and Solomon, 2013), potentially improving financial performance. Similarly, because social media marketing involves the execution of marketing strategies which deal directly with customers (Canhoto et al., 2013; Sasatanun and Charoensukmongkol, 2016), these strategies could help firms to effectively respond to their customers' needs and preferences of customers, which could also increase their opportunities to gain greater financial benefit.

On the other hand, the communication capability of social media marketing was found to have a significant positive relationship only with customer relationship performance, whereas the capability of social media planning was found to have a significant positive relationship only with the financial performance of the firm. The findings of a study conducted by Charoensukmongkol and Tarsakoo (2019) explain that these two capabilities have different focuses and target different aspects with regard to performance. First, the communication capability of social media marketing involves direct communication with customers through social media platforms to create better relationships (Sasatanun and Charoensukmongkol, 2016; Tuten and Solomon, 2013); also, their outcomes seem to be more relevant with regard to

the performance of customer relationships than with financial performance (Tuten and Solomon, 2013). On the other hand, the planning capabilities of social media also involve the planning of resource utilization (Nakara et al., 2012; Trainor et al., 2014), and these outcomes tend to be more relevant to financial performance than to customer relationship performance.

The overall results of the research carried out in this study are inconsistent with previous marketing research, which has emphasized the marketing capabilities required by firms to develop and gain competitive advantage (Rodriguez et al., 2012; Sirmon et al., 2007; Song et al., 2007). However, the results are in line with previous research which supported the role of social media activities in helping firms to enhance their competitiveness (Nakara et al., 2012; Sasatanun and Charoensukmongkol, 2016; Trainor et al., 2014).

The main objective of this research was to identify the effects of social media adoption on firms' performance. The results revealed a significant and positive effect, suggesting that firms were benefiting from their investments in social media. Nair (2011) argued that firms' use of social media is a process of experimentation, the results of which should not be immediately calculated. Nair suggested that more companies of all sizes are required to report on both the advantages or benefits realized from their investments in social media and how they measured these benefits. There is no standard measurement for adoption of social media or its effect on performance, and this makes it impossible for organizations to prove that their investments in social media technologies have resulted in direct profit or loss (Divol et al., 2012; Mangiuc, 2009). Any measurements are highly subjective and are usually interpreted uniquely by the entity doing the measurement (Owyang and Toll, 2007).

It has also been argued that measurements of success, and whether it is meaningful or not, should relate to the original objectives with regards to the initiative: in this case, the adoption of social media (McCann and Barlow, 2015). Hoffman and Fodor (2010) argued that the question here is not whether to blog or tweet, but what objectives are required and what tools and metrics could be used to achieve the best outcome. To make effective use of social media, therefore, businesses should use them strategically, and should consider why they are using them. Businesses should also be aware of how the selected tools could help them to support their objectives (Stockdale et al., 2012). This argument resonates with the work of Blanchard (2011), who emphasized that the adoption of social media could only provide value if used by the adopters as a tool to support the already available or existing strategies and objectives of the business, and not as an end in itself.

Social media is not only a simple place to communicate or to get in touch with family and friends, but has become a significant ingredient in the marketing and promotion mix, where it boosts the financial performance of the firm (Bashar et al., 2012). In the words of Felix, Rauschnabel and Hinsch (2017), a massive body of empirical research has shown that social media increases brand awareness, stimulates sales, improves brand image, reduces the cost of marketing, generates traffic for online platforms, and creates interactivity by stimulating users to post or share content. To understand how the customer views the firm, its actions and its products, firms could monitor and analyse conversations on social media platforms (Schweidel and Moe, 2014). Managers and marketing executives can then act on the information received from social media to check the firm's performance.

Firms could also use the seven functional building-blocks with respect to social media as identified by Kietzmann et al. (2011) to help to grow and create value. These building blocks are conversation, identity, presence, sharing, reputation, relationships, and groups. Another approach which could help in boosting firms' performance and sales is viral marketing on social media. People on social media are influenced by others. The firms' standard in the society, whether weak standard or strong, could influence the actions, decisions and opinions of others (Mochalova and Nanopoulos, 2014). This could bring about viral marketing, which could boost performance if the company acts on it. Consumers spend significant time every day on social media. The fundamental nature of social media as a platform for the consumers to interact with and influence one another has a direct impact on the brand communities and produces higher response rates and greater customer engagement of than the traditional marketing methodologies, which focus only on the firm-consumer relationship (Trusov, Bucklin, & Pauwels, 2009). This is correct in the sense that firms also interact with the customer on social media irrespective of where the customers are. Facebook or Instagram, for example, provide the functionality of pages or groups, which the firms use to interact and communicate with customers and as a platform for strengthening the firm-customer relationship. Trainor et al. (2014) showed that firms' performance is not improved by just investing in hardware and software to support CRM systems, but also by deploying the resources of technological CRM alongside the other complementary resources. One significant positive element has been identified, namely 'trust', which influences online customers' repurchasing behaviour. Social media is very well known for building trust (Chong et al., 2018), such that if the firm integrates the technologies of social media marketing and CRM systems to facilitate the development of marketing capability, increase customer satisfaction

and improve relationships with customers (Wang and Kim, 2017). It can thus be seen that with the help of social media, customers and organizations can interact and communicate with one another, and this will empower them to take advantage of their active role to co-create experiences (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004).

This research proposed that firms' activity on social media would have a positive relationship with their performance. This is based on the idea that social media use could increase customers' involvement and commitment towards the company, leading to increased loyalty and satisfaction (Trainor, 2012), which would have a positive impact on the firm's equity value (Anderson et al., 2004; Luo et al., 2010). An indirect effect of participation on social media is better performance of the firm. Karjaluoto et al. (2016) identified this relationship in the use of LinkedIn and Twitter. They found that larger companies that had more personnel working for them had more tweets overall on these platforms and were also more active on LinkedIn in comparison with smaller companies with fewer personnel.

In addition to this, companies with larger net revenue were found to be more active on both LinkedIn and Twitter as compared with those that had smaller net revenue. More profitable companies registered more activity on Twitter and LinkedIn as compared to companies with lesser profits. On the Facebook platform, people had more conversations about larger and more profitable companies, but companies' activity on Facebook was found to have no relationship to the performance of the firm or size of the company in the research by Karjaluoto et al. (2016). Similarly, no relationship was found between companies' activities on YouTube and their size and performance. The theoretical contribution of the study by Karjaluoto et al. (2016) was that it demonstrated that active companies had a better reputation on social media platforms in comparison to those that were less active, whereas a partial link was found between activity on social media and firms' performance.

Uyar et al. (2018) found that use of social media increases the performance of the firm, in line with earlier studies (Da et al., 2011; Luo et al., 2013; Yu et al., 2013). However, Uyar et al.'s (2018) study only shed light on three metrics, namely the presence of accounts on social media, the breadth of engagement, and the effective depth of utilization. Although they predicted a positive relationship between the abovementioned three metrics and the value of the firm, two of their three hypotheses were rejected and only the third hypothesis was accepted. Their findings imply that the presence of social media accounts and increasing the variety of social media accounts that a company has are not sources of value for companies if this presence of

multiple platforms is not used effectively. Their results confirm that simply creating a presence on online platforms does not offer a guarantee that the company will gain value by using social media (Culnan et al., 2010). Their study highlights that it is the use of the communication platforms which acts as a bridge to reach out to customers, civil society and shareholders, hence providing benefit for the company (Siamagka et al., 2015). Doing so might also improve non-financial performance (Schaupp and Belanger, 2014; Ainin et al., 2015; Parveen et al., 2015), as well as increasing financial performance (Schniederjans et al., 2013; Kim et al., 2015), and attracting the attention of investors (Da et al., 2011), therefore ultimately improving the value of the firm (Kim et al., 2015a; Da et al., 2011; Luo et al., 2013; Yu et al., 2013; Du and Jiang, 2015). In summary, from their research, it was found that social media is becoming an indispensable tool to help organizations to achieve both long-term and short-term goals. Therefore, firms should not perceive that investment in social media is a net cost, but rather should consider it as a tool for value creation (Luo et al., 2013).

A study conducted by Del Bosco et al. (2017) aimed to find out how the mode of use of social media platforms for marketing communication activities influences their efficacy in terms of the impact on firms' performance. Two hypotheses were tested: (1) the adoption of integrated communication strategies, and (2) the choice of the use of social media concerning reaching new target customers. Regarding the first aspect, Del Bosco et al. (2017) found that efficacy of social media appeared to enhance firms' decisions to manage the different channels they used in a coordinated way. It emerged in the research that the importance of extending integration and coordination efforts not only to online tools but also to offline communication. This might be because this extension may help firms to achieve consistent communication by exploiting the potential synergistic effects of joint use of the different tools and channels. Whereas integrated management of the different formats of online communication is quite common, the elements which are discriminant appears to be the effort to integrate the communication across all media.

For the second hypothesis of the research, the probability of observing a significant positive impact on the performance of the firm was found to be higher in firms that declared the use of social media to reach new customers and not to restrict their use to communication with existing customers by reaching out to them with other tools and channels. Del Bosco et al. (2017) found that the effectiveness of social media use appeared to be related to their use as complementary tools in the communication mix, allowing the firm to benefit from the potential of these platforms in addition to other channels. Firms that substitute other tools instead of

social media tend to less frequently register a positive perceived impact. This might also be interpreted as a signal of actual complementarity of social and traditional media. If different media allow different targets to be reached or have different efficacy in terms of these different targets, using them jointly could obtain the best results. In addition to this, using social media in connection with communication tools and communication media might also help to reinforce relationships and messages with customers. On the other hand, the study found that substituting one type of communication media with another communication tool may improve one dimension of communication, but it would weaken the other dimension at the same time.

A study performed by Etim et al. (2018) on the telecommunication sector in Ghana examined the relationship between social media initiatives and firms' performance. The analysis concluded that social media initiatives positively and significantly affected the performance of telecommunications firms in Ghana. The research found that this might be the reason why almost all the telecommunication firms were exploring the opportunities through the flexible nature of social media for promotion, product branding, image-making, advertising as well as endearing their services to their clients. The findings corroborates those reported by other scholars where they submitted that social media initiatives had a positive relationship with firms' performance (Dhar and Chang, 2009; Culnan et al., 2010; Aral et al., 2013; Lam et al., 2016). Also, Lam, Yeung, and Cheng (2016) investigated the influence of social media initiatives on firms' operational efficiency and innovativeness and concluded that usage of social media leads towards the development of new ideas and ultimately to greater efficiency. Moreover, Aral, Dellarocas and Godes (2013) also submitted that social media usage promotes the transformation of business. Similarly, a study conducted by Sang (2014) regarding social media initiatives and operational and financial performance found that social media initiatives correlated positively with firms' performance. Likewise, Amue, Umoh and Ngaage (2012) found that increasing market share, in the long run, depended on the ability to retain customer loyalty, which could be achieved via effective communication through the help of social media.

A study conducted by Musa et al. (2016) showed that practices of social media marketing could influence organizations' online performance. To effectively improve their performance, SMEs should develop their strategies regarding social media marketing to support their implementation. The research revealed a strong and significant positive relationship between the brand reputation and image and organizations' performance, as supported by prior studies (Dobni and Zinkhan, 1990). Therefore, the research by Must et al. (2016) contributed to the literature by showing that successful application of social media marketing could enhance

firms' success through managing the strategies of organizational marketing and commercialization. The use of smart and simple strategies, as explored by the research, positively effects the number of customers and therefore increases the number of purchases made. In addition, effective and efficient implementation of the practices of social media marketing would help the organization to increase its product sales and thus to achieve its objective.

Because of the increasing number of different efforts to improve companies' reputation, it is widely agreed that the correlation between the practices of social media marketing and its elements is important to increase profits and improve customers' satisfaction. The research performed by Musa et al. (2016) indicated that this assists the managers in organizations or marketing managers with regard to their decisions to practice and to develop the strategies of social media marketing to raise profit margins, respectively.

In a study conducted by Adegbuyi and Akinyele (2015) on the effects of social media marketing on small-scale business performance in Nigeria, it was posited that SMEs often do not have a specific strategy when they begin to use social media for business. This could result in wasted time and effort. Nevertheless, it is essential for businesses to recognize the goal that they are looking to derive from the usage of social media. Simply creating an account on Facebook or Twitter and posting some messages on it every week is not enough. The business should be active on the social media networks and should have some fundamental know-how with regard to how to use them, including the techniques required to maintain consumers on the platform. In today's information- and communication-driven environment, businesses, whether big or small, should understand Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and all the techniques which are employed to use social media. With the use of social media being well-regulated, businesses have the opportunity to inform a wider array of their potential prospects. Therefore, how small businesses use social media networks to engage with their customers is very important for their success. For many newer businesses, social media may be a platform that has come to stay. Smaller businesses do learn through participation on social media, but this might be a major task for such businesses if they have a sound understanding of the benefits that can be achieved. Smaller businesses, therefore, require know-how with regard to usage of social media to engage consumers and to build relationships to project growth (Adegbuyi and Akinyele, 2015).

Nyambu (2013) conducted a study in Kenya and concluded that organizations had realized and developed on social media because of their marketing efforts. Likewise, through the new information that diffuses through social media networks, opportunities become available through new ideas and access to more and better resources. In addition to this, Nyambu (2013) concluded that organizations' management place greater emphasis on networking on social platforms as a way of influencing customers' loyalty and therefore improving organizations' performance in a wider context. The study also concluded that the majority of organizations apply information technology as a tool for social marketing socially through enabling human interactions on a scale which has never before been witnessed. Nyambu also concluded that organizations have invested heavily in the field of information technology, resulting in direct linkages between investment and increases in productivity and performance.

Nyambu (2013) also concluded that the majority of the organizations investigated made use of social media for promotional campaigns, which helped them to identify exactly when, how and where the social media helped them in influencing consumers, thus helping the executives to craft marketing strategies to take advantage of the unique ability of social media to engage with end customers. Therefore, the study concluded that keeping the customers engaged with social media marketing helps the company to retain existing customers and to attract new customers. The majority of social media were found to improve, increase, or enhance the effectiveness of customers' feedback in most of the organizations studied. The study also concluded that social media provide a better platform for organizations' performance by helping to generate quick and timely feedback from their customers (Nyambu, 2013).

Braojos et al. (2019) conducted a study from which they concluded that firms which better leverage their social media and e-commerce end up achieving fine-graded knowledge of their customers by engaging these customers virtually on their social media and websites. As an example, Finnair ran some social media accounts to look for innovative ideas from customers. After the development of the community, Finnair gathered hundreds of different ideas from members of the community. Some of the most voted ideas for implementation were to give the passengers a service where they could swap books and offer some vegetarian meals on board. This example shows how a company with proficiency in social media could engage with its customers to acquire the knowledge required to innovate their products and services. These findings show that firms' overall social media and e-commerce capabilities individually as well as jointly motivate the customers to participate and give their opinions and swap ideas, as well as creating a sense of brand commitment, identification and loyalty (Chen and Shen, 2015).

These deep connections and interactions are beneficial for the firms, eventually resulting in better performance.

Hery's (2018) research on "social network to firm performance" also confirmed that social networks provide support for firms' performance, in line with previous studies (Bicen and Hunt, 2012; Kregar and Antoncic, 2016; Foroudi et al., 2017). Hery's findings highlighted that trust played an important role in the structure of social networks in the firms observed, allowing them to generate selling and pricing capability, the result of which is a significant and positive impact on performance. The research also provided evidence that firms could exploit social media platforms to enhance or increase the capability of pricing, and that social media does not have a direct impact on the performance of a firm, but rather an indirect impact. This indicates that the initiative to exploit social networks is not enough to generate profits until or unless this entails a relationship based on trust, which plays a pivotal role in the complex relationship between social networks and firms' performance.

5.9. Chapter Summary

The chapter has presented the findings, analysis and discussion of the results obtained from the research. The chapter has set out an introduction to the analysis of the data, presented the profiles of the respondents, explained the reliability test performed and its results, and then presented the descriptive statistics, the results of the correlation analysis, and the regression analysis and its assumptions. The research hypotheses were tested in the form of three different models derived from the study's conceptual framework. Finally, the chapter provided a discussion of the results in relation to the research hypotheses. The next chapter provides the conclusion of the research, limitations, and recommendations for future research.

CHAPTER 6

6. Conclusion, Implications and Future Research

6.1. Research overview

This study was performed to examine the impact of the use of social media technology on the performance of SMEs and to evaluate the effect of mediators such as customer orientation, marketing capabilities and brand equity. The conceptual model set out in Chapter 2 was used to measure this impact. Quantitative research was performed to test the hypotheses using a survey questionnaire technique to collect data, with various research questions to target each variable of the research. Non-probability convenience-based sampling was used to perform the research. Data were then analysed using SPSS tools and the results for each hypothesis were determined. It was found that brand equity does not have a positive impact on firms' performance with the use of social media technology. Marketing capabilities and customer orientation, however, do create an impact on performance when social media marketing is used.

6.2. Meeting the aims and Objectives of this Thesis

6.2.1. *Objective 1: To evaluate the role of social media technology use on performance of SME's in Pakistan.*

Based on the research, it has been found that social media technology has a positive impact on the performance of SMEs in Pakistan. These results are in line with those from other studies which concluded that technology could improve businesses' processes and performance (Gera and Gu, 2004; Paniagua and Sapena, 2014; Hakala and Kohtamäki, 2011). Several other studies have also found a positive relationship between the adoption of social media and organizations' performance (Ainin et al., 2015; Paniagua and Sapena, 2014; Parveen et al., 2014; Rodriguez et al., 2012). Rodriguez et al. (2015) also found that social media use has a positive effect on customer-facing activities and consequently on sales performance. Similarly, Ferrer et al. (2013) found that the adoption of social media positively affects organizations' social capital and ultimately affects their performance as well. Both Cervellon and Galipienzo (2015) and Garrido-Moreno and Lockett (2016) found a positive relationship between the use of social media and firms' financial performance. This concurs with the findings of Harris et al. (2012), who found that SMEs make use of both offline and online networks for business activities, of

the which include marketing as well as sales. Similarly, Deighton and Kornfeld (2009) also argued that social media helps in enabling a substantial increase in customers' power, using a marketing strategy that engages the social media towards the logical choice for the business. In line with all of these findings, the present study demonstrates, through correlation and regression analysis, that there is a positive relationship between social media technology use and performance in SMEs in Pakistan.

6.2.2. Objective 2: To evaluate the impact of social media technology use on customer orientation, marketing capabilities and brand equity of SME's in Pakistan

For the second objective of the research, a negative relationship was found between social media technology use and brand equity, which is the opposite to the findings from prior research. For example, Hutagalung and Situmorang (2018) found that social media had a positive impact on brand equity. Similarly, Hardeep and Rani (2017) also found that engagement with social media has a substantial impact on customers' brand equity. Erdogmus and Cicek (2012) found that marketing on social media has a positive impact on customers' brand loyalty, while Kim and Ko (2010) also found that marketing on social media positively influenced purchase intentions and relationships with customers.

The present study found the impact of social media technology use on customer orientation and marketing capabilities to be positive. Marketing capabilities were increased by the use of social media technology in this study, in line with the results of prior research. For example, Chang et al. (2010) found the role of social media technology to be beneficial for marketing capabilities. Companies' marketing capabilities also contribute positively towards their performance. Tajvidi and Karami (2017) found that the effect of marketing capabilities of the firm's performance in the hotel industry continues to lag (Leonidou et al., 2013; Odoom et al., 2017; Ramanathan et al., 2016). Lastly, customer orientation and social media technology use had a positive impact on each other. So, the present study found that the impact of social media technology use on variables other than brand equity was positive for SMEs in Pakistan, but for brand equity, it was found to have a negative impact, which is different from the findings of previous research.

6.2.3. Objective 3: To evaluate the impact of customer orientation, marketing capabilities and brand equity on firm performance of SME's in Pakistan

The present study found that the impact of customer orientation and marketing capabilities on the performance of SMEs in Pakistan was positive, whereas brand equity was found to have a

negative impact on the performance of these SMEs. Ambler (1999) and Bitner et al. (1990) both found a positive relationship between the firm's orientation in the market and its performance in the market. Moreover, Kennedy et al. (2002) found that the development and implementation of customer orientation was related to the firm's position in the market. However, Thomas et al. (2011) and Tsiotsou and Ratten (2010) found that customer orientation does not matter, since smaller businesses show internal capability. Tajeddini (2010) also found that customer orientation, as well as entrepreneurial orientation and the innovativeness of the firm, have a positive impact on firm performance. Likewise, according to the research carried out by Morgan et al. (2009), marketing capabilities help in enabling the firm to effectively implement its strategic orientation and are designed to match the marketing conditions and help in attaining the specific performance objectives of the organization. Also, Krasnikov and Jayachandran (2008) found that the firm's marketing capabilities are its driving forces when it is operating in a dynamic environment. Another study carried out by Sun (2010) found that in industries which are lower with respect to their capabilities, marketing capabilities are the only capabilities which are linked with firm performance. Similarly, Salisu Abu-Bakr and Rani (2017) found that marketing capabilities are essential for firms, since they help it to achieve its performance. Thus, the present study's findings that marketing capabilities and customer orientation have a positive impact on the performance of SMEs in Pakistan are in line with the literature.

6.2.4. Objective 4: To investigate how customer orientation, marketing capabilities and brand equity mediates social media technology use and firm performance relationship for SME's in Pakistan

Only two of the three mediators in the research demonstrated a positive relationship between the use of social media technology and the performance of the firm. Brand equity did not show a positive impact as a mediator between social media technology and firm performance in SMEs in Pakistan, whereas customer orientation and marketing capabilities both worked as significant mediators between the use of social media technology and firms' performance. Research carried out in the past has mainly focused on the impact of social media use and firm performance directly, and the role of mediators has not been studied extensively, yet all three mediators' roles have been studied separately and all three of them have previously been found to have a positive impact on firms' performance. For example, Day (1994) showed that social media product development capabilities and social media implementation in marketing were positively and significantly related to firms and customers' performance. Research performed

by Tuten and Solomon (2013) reflects that social media marketing activities help organizations to respond effectively towards customers' needs and preferences to gain more financial benefits.

6.3. Key Finding of thesis

The present study found that social media technology had a positive impact on the performance of SMEs in Pakistan. These results concur with the results from other studies in indicating that technology could improve businesses' processes and performance (Gera and Gu, 2004; Paniagua and Sapena, 2014; Hakala and Kohtamäki, 2011). This positive relationship was demonstrated using correlation and regression analysis.

In the Pakistani SMEs, the impact of customer orientation and marketing capabilities on performance were positive, whereas the impact of brand was negative. Not all the three mediators examined in this research had positive impacts on the relationship between the use of social media technology and firms' performance. Brand equity did not show a positive impact as a mediator between social media technology and firm performance in the SMEs of Pakistan, although both customer orientation and marketing capabilities had significant positive impacts as mediators between the use of social media technology and firms' performance. The negative relationship between social media technology use and brand equity contrasts with findings from research.

6.4. Research Contribution and Novelty

SMEs have an essential and critical role in the development and economic growth of any country. SMEs play a massive role in the context of business innovation, employment, and social development, and are a source of revenue across the globe. With the advent and rise of SMEs, poverty levels decrease as individuals' income and spending power increases.

SMEs make up over 90% of all organizations around the world: hence, it is crucial to know how they make use of social media advertising and what obstacles they come across in executing these social media strategies in their businesses. Nonetheless, SMEs in developing countries are still not gaining the full potential from online media marketing, even though it offers SMEs great opportunities in terms of growth (Yadav, 2017).

By using social media, SMEs will be more competitive in the global economy, giving them access to larger marketplaces. The research focused on SMEs in Pakistan that use social media

marketing to an extent but are lacking in strategic marketing plans to earn competitive advantage over their competitors and other large enterprises.

Even though social media as a marketing tool is helpful to promote socialization and information sharing about SMEs' products in the context of retail clothing, there is still a lack of understanding of how social media marketing tactics can influence the sustainability and profitability of SMEs, especially in the developing countries when there are restrictions on the usage of social media applications. Most of the previous literature links social media marketing strategies and SMEs' sustainability and profitability in the context of western culture or developed countries. However, very little literature is available to provide a better understanding of the use of social media marketing for SMEs in Pakistan.

This study centred on how the usage of social media technology can influences businesses' performance and growth. It also helped to clarify the role of brand equity factors, market orientation, and customer orientation on the relationship of social media technology use and business performance satisfaction.

Online shopping is a new trend in Pakistan, so SMEs need effective online marketing strategies to take advantage of this online platform not only to establish their presence online and boost sales but also to as a means reach their existing and potential new customers. The present study explored different marketing tools and strategies that can help SMEs in Pakistan to boost their sales and growth with online presence. It found a positive and significant relationship between marketing capabilities and firm performance. Marketing capabilities can be explained as preparing a marketing team that can fabricate stronger brands. Marketing capabilities encompass the complex blend of information, measures, methods of working, tools and best practices that have an effect in brand building.

This study highlights the positive impact of customer orientation on the performance of a firm. Further, it recognizes that the firm needs to use different forms of [user feedback tools](#) to identify and address its weak points. Most customers make purchase decisions based on the information available on various social networking sites, which increases the importance of social media platforms and the well-established presence of the brand online (Karimi and Naghibi, 2015).

The study findings contribute towards the extant literature and fill some critical gaps, as the conceptual framework has not previously been used in Pakistan. The implications of the framework can support SME owners in the retail apparel sector in Pakistan. Many brands in

Pakistan use social media platforms for sales purposes; however, other aspects are yet to be explored, tried and tested by the businesses. Therefore, the findings from this study would help these business owners to make use of the factors identified for increased business performance.

The research offers several insights about the impact of online marketing and how SMEs should have a proactive way to deal with exploring and taking on new marketing tools. Companies that seek promising opportunities through creative digital solutions will gain competitive advantage over their opponents and those who do not pay attention could rapidly see themselves lose ground

6.5. Research Implications

The results obtained from the research carried out have several practical implications. The research provides insights for SMEs that when social media is positively employed for networking, it can improve the performance of the business. Merely having access to the online networks of social media and the internet is not the same as making optimal use of these resources. Firms should develop their innovation and branding capabilities of marketing to make the most of social media.

6.5.1. Implications for Social Change

After the financial collapse in 2008, small businesses are playing an important role in employment in the private sector. Larger corporations faced massive setbacks following the financial crises. Smaller businesses, on the other hand, have continued to rise, since their costs of operations are lower. Since large corporations in Pakistan were not adding more jobs to the market, the government's focus shifted towards promoting small businesses in the country (Kashif, 2016). If a company aims to maintain its position in developing countries, it should facilitate the running and rise of small businesses (Audretsch *et al.*, 2015). In this study, the barriers faced by small businesses concerning social media marketing were identified, and the results of this research will help SMEs to improve their social media marketing activities, thus improving their performance.

This study is also helpful in enabling businesses to devise a social media marketing strategy to attract more customers. It can improve the business situation for SMEs operating in Pakistan. Dutot and Bergeron, (2016) define social media marketing as a process whereby businesses develop virtual communities to promote and project their message about products and services. The trustworthiness of large corporations has been questioned by many in recent years despite

the increased level of corporate social responsibility measures taken by large corporations (Shaltoni, 2017). Therefore, small businesses are in a unique position for improving communication with stakeholders and for contributing to employment in the market. Small businesses are also able to address customers' concerns by utilizing social media as a channel of communication. Thus, the current study is a step forward concerning SMEs in Pakistan, as it suggests that they should make use of social media marketing to maintain their competitiveness in the market.

6.5.2. Theoretical Implications:

Both Aaker (1991) and Keller (1993) suggest that holding a competitive position in the marketplace yields the measurable value of a brand. According to Aaker (1991), brand equity would need a new conceptual framework. Meanwhile, the concept should acknowledge the functions in parallel with respect to garnering competitive position and relative to the stakeholders. Such stakeholders may include outgroup members as well as ingroup members. The current study also draws on Bourdieu's (1986) concept of social capital to explain this human social capital in parallel to brand equity in the business marketplace. Aaker's (1996) studies with respect to brand equities and social media use focus on the brands of organizations. This overemphasis on the brands of organizations means that brands of humans are potentially underexplored. Brand equity refers to the position of the brand in the marketplace (Aaker, 1996), which includes social media and firm performance.

Underwood et al. (2001) found that factors such as marketing capabilities and customer orientation reveal an emotional connection between brands and consumers, which sometimes results in fervent commitment. This study does not quite gauge emotional resonance with respect to brands, but it does examine how brand identity can potentially influence the perception of the brand. A theoretical implication of the current study is the acknowledgement of the model of social identity-brand equity with relevance to exploring the perceptions of the brand, based on the analysis performed by Underwood et al. (2001).

Boyle and Magnusson (2007) also based their analysis on the SIBE model to explore the connection between firm performance and social media use. A further theoretical implication of the current study is the affirmation of the effect of the use of social media technology on firms' sales and financial performance. This affirmation validates the approach and confirms the findings from prior studies (Gera and Gu, 2004; Paniagua and Sapena, 2014; Hakala and Kohtamäki, 2011).

The current study incorporates the term ‘market capabilities’, as utilized by Herskovitz and Crystal (2010), to define the effects on the performance of the firm, which may involve narrative elements to define the presence of media.

Gil de Zúñiga et al. (2012) discuss the parallels between the business marketplace and the social field. The current study affirms that social entities within a competitive environment offer various perceptions of a brand. This means that SMEs are not perceived as being the same among all businesses, and therefore are potentially valued because of their likeability, along with other observable factors. Likewise, Watkins (2014) explored the domain of sports to investigate factors that impact organizations’ performance. Both Paniagua and Sapena (2014) and Hakala and Kohtamäki (2011) substantiated the hypothesis in the current study, which predicts that likeability will be associated with the positive tone of messages and connections. The results presented in the current analysis support the findings of these studies and the study also offers pathways for future scholars to explore observable variables pertaining to the perceptions of the brand.

In several different media environments, brands earn positions of consumer value because of the perception of their likeability (Nguyen et al., 2015), and positions with respect to market value through brand awareness (Burnaz & Bilgin, 2011) and staying power. In the context of the business marketplace, brand equity describes the competitive position that the brand garners with respect to the external stakeholders of the organization (Parrott et al., 2015). In addition to this, the concept of social capital helps to explain the environment of social media, which has merged socially competitive tendencies with respect to human interactions with ingenuity and brand amplification tactics that are present in the competitive business market (Nguyen et al., 2015).

Therefore, the research conducted in the present study operationalizes the conceptual synthesis of social capital and brand equity to create more scholarly pathways to investigate the phenomenon of branding, when the personas of the brand are subject of the analysis. As explained in this research, social media is a ripe and dynamic environment in which future analysis is encouraged to advance knowledge about social competition and social mobility in different contexts. In the current study, social media use is associated with customer orientation, marketing capabilities and brand equity to find out the potential impact on the performance of the organization. This study designs the factors of the brand persona’s inherently the behaviour socially and its interactions with social media users, who are often

fans. This approach qualifies as a conceptual operationalization of the synthesis, whereby future scholars could utilize the definitions and explanations offered herein to analyse the use of social media technology in the SME business environment, particularly with respect to firms' performance.

6.5.3. Practical implications for the academy:

The present study reveals that customer orientation and marketing capabilities have a positive impact when on firms' performance when combined with social media technology use, although this was not found to be the case for brand equity. The results of the research also extend the literature with respect to social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram, which are considered as mediums of communication, having news feeds in real-time, as well as platforms for branding (Andéhn et al., 2014). Twitter is also considered as a medium for communication, as it enables interactions that go beyond two-way communication, with several other functions such as sharing, liking, commenting, listing, trending, and favouriting (Wang and Kim, 2017). Whenever such functions are viewable and engaged by the external public beyond the scope of two-way interaction between the user and provider, the media becomes increasingly social, as well as shareable and potentially amplified (Wang and Kim, 2017). The current study's inclusion of social media usage as part of the stimulus shown to the respondents reflects the literature, acknowledging that small and medium businesses make use of social media platforms (Hasaan et al., 2016). The results also further validate the presence of brands on social media platforms.

With respect to reviewing the core findings, the current study has found a major and main impact of marketing capabilities on firms' performance. The findings also affirm the literature suggesting that messages with a positive tone will create greater brand resonance among consumers (Kim et al, 2016). In other words, it can be said that branded content that has a clear tone may influence customers' buying behaviour and have noticeable effects in terms of changing attitudinal aspects such as opinions (Kim et al., 2016).

The current research also revealed that the use of web technology and cyberspace has become a general or common practice in all businesses (Zhang et al., 2013). Organizations today are more empowered to contact their clients anytime or anywhere using the internet (Chen et al., 2011).

On the other hand, social media as a channel of communication help firms to accomplish a range of objectives, including PR, marketing, branding, advertising, human resources,

customer services and problem-solving (Nisar and Whitehead, 2016). Accordingly, social media have been considered as effective platforms to allow enterprises to connect with many potential customers to spread information about their businesses (Schaupp and Belanger, 2014). The development of online communities has expanded the interconnectivity between consumers and businesses and enabled rapid communications internationally (Aichner and Jacob, 2015). In addition to this, social media can have an impact on firms' brand position, customer loyalty, brand awareness and customers' purchasing decisions (Nisar and Whitehead, 2016).

Firms' adoption of social media creates a greater network among customers, businesses and suppliers (Siamagka et al., 2015). According to the network approach, firms are taking advantage of networking activities that lead to superior performance. Several different studies in the past have emphasized the advantages of networking for firms (Trainor et al., 2014). However, less attention has been paid to the values of online networking for the performance of SMEs (Wamba and Carter, 2016). SMEs are the economic engine for the majority of the countries, but past studies have focused mainly on the adoption (Durkin et al., 2014; Wamba and Carter, 2016) and the barriers and benefits of social media in the context of SMEs.

Social media fundamentally affect SMEs. According to Ahmed et al. (2014), social media provide free tools for market research, as they focus on customers' evaluation and comments on different social networking sites to give managers an idea about their businesses' overall performance.

6.6. Research limitations

The study is confined to SMEs and requires replication, but the focus must be on specific industries. The importance of social media may be different in different contexts, industries and countries. The current research is only fitting for marketplace discovery in the near term. There were very few potential consumers engaged with networking sites and prominent platforms such as Instagram. In the future, social media might have as much dynamic ability as it had in the previous decade. The world's population is increasingly becoming engaged with online communities and fans and fanbases continue to grow. Therefore, it will not be wrong to say that current studies are limited with respect to the time frame, which prescribes renewed inquiry alongside the inevitable evolution and growth of social media.

To conduct parsimonious as well as methodologically sound research, the current study has an intentionally wider focus, considering the impact of social media technology use on the

performance of SMEs in all aspects by looking into social media channels such as Facebook and Instagram. However, there are several different environments of social media with distinct communities of users, which may yield different user reactions (Adegbuyi *et al.*, 2015). This variance may render the current findings limited in their generalizability across the broader universe of social media. Nevertheless, the current research offers an approach which is operationalizable to examine unexplored environments. This is perhaps the most useful contribution to the analysis. The blueprint of the current study may require adjustments when factoring in the effects of social media use. This would require a simulation of the use of social media, rather than a study using interview measures.

Hypothesis 1 of the research focuses mainly on the impact of social media technology use on firms' performance, taking into consideration the wider platform of SMEs, and is limited to specific industries. The research has not taken into consideration all aspects of performance. The results might have been different if the use of social media technology had been limited to specific platforms and if performance had been measured in terms of financial aspects and revenue. If specific industries had been measured, this would provide different results, as the use of social media and its effectiveness in different sectors increases or decreases the performance of the organization. In addition to this, different social media platforms have different audiences. Older people tend to make more use of Facebook, whereas the young generation is making more use of Instagram and Snapchat. Therefore, the issue of whether the platform selected is right for the product or the service, and whether the audience on the platform is the right fit for the target market, will depend on the organization and its sector.

Hypothesis 2 of the research focuses on the impact of social media technology use on customer orientation, marketing capabilities and brand equity of SME. Again, this has been examined using a wide lens with respect to all the SMEs. There are certain dimensions within customer orientation, but the present has focused on customer orientation in general and the specific nature of customer orientation has not been evaluated with respect to firms' performance. The impact of brand equity on firms' performance was not found to be positive in this research, but since the study was carried out in on the general context of all SMEs, it could be further specified with respect to industry or sector and different results might arise.

Despite the significant results as well as notable implications, this study also has some limitations. First, it used a cross-sectional design, which sometimes restricts the drawing of results from causal explanations. In this regard, it might be worthwhile for future scholars to

carry out a longitudinal study. The present study only examined the impact of social media technology use on the performance of firms in general for SMEs of Pakistan, but future researchers might try to test the impact of other marketing strategies for the sustainable performance of the SMEs and could also examine the intervening role of the associations in general.

6.7. Future Research Recommendations

Future studies should test the results of the current study in other sectors. In addition, social media might have a different impact on different benefits for businesses. Studying the effect of social media on brand equity based on consumers and on finance, as well as the lifetime value of customers, would potentially be fruitful avenues to conduct further research. Moreover, it is necessary to investigate customer relationship management (CRM) and advertising alongside the effect of social media use on organizations' performance.

This study should be replicated with the inclusion of additional variables. Therefore, for future research, it is recommended that the factors of the ever-changing universe of social media be considered (Ainin *et al.*, 2015). Such research would uncover potentially fruitful and interesting new information.

Future studies should aim to achieve realistic simulation or engagement with social media. In the current study, the responses were limited to questionnaire answers. It is advised that future researchers conduct an experiment that presents social media activity through realistic simulation of social media. Such an approach would closely resemble the typical behaviour of engagement. The stimulation approach incorporates more authentic outgroup and ingroup experiences in social media.

It is also recommended that future researchers individually evaluate the performance with respect to a firm, in the form of sales performance, revenue, equity or increase in the customer base. For further research to be performed, only the customer orientation and its impact on the performance of the firm could be evaluated alone, with a focus on a specific sector or industry.

Prior research has found that brand equity has a positive impact on firms' performance. Therefore, it requires further investigation to evaluate the role of brand equity between the use of social media on the performance of the firm. Lastly, marketing capabilities, in general, have shown a positive impact on the performance of the firm, so it is necessary to further evaluate

whether marketing capabilities via social media use create a significant change in firms' financial performance.

Hypothesis 3 of the research focuses on the impact of customer orientation, marketing capabilities, and brand equity on the performance of SMEs. The results, other than brand equity, were found to have a positive impact on firms' performance, but brand equity showed a negative impact on firms' performance in this research. It is thus recommended that research should be carried out with a larger sample and that probability sampling should be used instead of non-probability convenience-based sampling. The Covid-19 pandemic meant that it was not possible to contact more SMEs to gather their opinions. Therefore, it is recommended that future research should be performed with a specific industry or sector, and with a larger sample that is selected based on probability sampling instead of non-probability convenience-based sampling.

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APPENDICES

Appendix-A: Survey Questionnaire

1/3/2021

SMMA and Profitability

SMMA and Profitability

This academic research study is being conducted for evaluating the role of social media marketing activities on the profitability of the small and medium enterprises in Pakistan. This research focuses on gathering the owner's perspective and therefore, your valuable time is requested to fill the questionnaire. It will take 10 to 15 minutes to fill out this questionnaire.

*** Required**

1. Your Gender *

Mark only one oval.

- Female
 Male
 Prefer not to say

2. Your Age *

Mark only one oval.

- 20 to 35 years
 36 to 45 years
 46 to 55 years
 Above 55 years

Social Media Technology Use

From Question 1 to 6, Kindly rate How social media technology use helped in your organization's growth? (in your opinion)

3. 1) Photo / Video sharing (i.e. Flickr, You Tube, Ustream) *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

4. 2) News/live feeds (i.e. RSS, Facebook) *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

5. 3) Blogging / Micro-bogging (i.e. Blogger, Wordpress, / Twitter , Facebook) *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

6. 4) Instant messaging (i.e. Google /Facebook /Yahoo / MSN messengers) *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

7. 5) Groups (i.e. Facebook group , WhatsApp group etc) *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

8. 6) Social and professional network presence (e.g. FaceBook, LinkedIn, Twitter) *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

Company Performance

From Questions 7 to 13, please rate your company performance in various areas / sections (in your opinion)

9. 7) Able to identify a simple brand meaning *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

10. 8) Using branding as an operational tool *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

11. 9) Treating the brand as assets *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

12. 10) Supporting brand through staff *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

13. 11) Developing new ideas to help customers *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

14. 12) Able to fast track new offerings to customers *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

15. 13) Able to manage processes to keep costs down *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

Customer Support Performance

From Question 14 to 18, please rate your company's customer support performance (in your opinion)

16. 14) Satisfying customer needs is the central purpose of our business. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

17. 15) A customer focus is reflected in our business planning *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

18. 16) We anticipate and respond to customers' evolving needs and wants *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

19. 17) We emphasize the evaluation of formal and informal customer complaints *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

20. 18) We follow up with customers for quality/service feedback *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

Financial Performance

From Question 19 to 22, please rate your company's financial performance (in your opinion)

21. 19) Increase in market share over the past 3 years *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

22. 20) Increase in annual turnover over the past 3 years *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

23. 21) Achieving firm profit goals over the past 3 years *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

24. 22) Having a better return on investment over the past 3 years *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

Brand Performance

From Question 23 to 25, please rate your company's brand performance (in your opinion)

25. 23) Our brand is better known than our most important competitor's. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

26. 24) The quality of our brand as perceived by our customers is higher than our competitor's *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

27. 25) High proportion of the products under our brand umbrella are leaders in their markets *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Thank You for your precious Time

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Google Forms

Appendix-B: Responses to Questionnaire Statements

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	129	57.6	57.6	57.6
	Female	93	41.5	41.5	99.1
	Prefer not to Say	2	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20 to 35 years	43	19.2	19.2	19.2
	36 to 45 years	66	29.5	29.5	48.7
	46 to 55 years	83	37.1	37.1	85.7
	Above 55 years	32	14.3	14.3	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Photo / Video sharing (i.e., Flickr, You Tube, Ustream)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	18	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	29	12.9	12.9	21.0
	Neutral	20	8.9	8.9	29.9
	Agree	12	5.4	5.4	35.3
	Strongly Agree	145	64.7	64.7	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

News/live feeds (i.e., RSS, Facebook)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	3.6	3.6	3.6
	Disagree	18	8.0	8.0	11.6
	Neutral	25	11.2	11.2	22.8
	Agree	35	15.6	15.6	38.4

Strongly Agree	138	61.6	61.6	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Blogging / Micro-blogging (i.e. Blogger, WordPress, / Twitter, Facebook)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	5	2.2	2.2	2.2
Disagree	15	6.7	6.7	8.9
Neutral	46	20.5	20.5	29.5
Agree	57	25.4	25.4	54.9
Strongly Agree	101	45.1	45.1	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Instant messaging (i.e., Google /Facebook /Yahoo / MSN messengers)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	6	2.7	2.7	2.7
Disagree	14	6.3	6.3	8.9
Neutral	11	4.9	4.9	13.8
Agree	37	16.5	16.5	30.4
Strongly Agree	156	69.6	69.6	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Groups (i.e., Facebook group, WhatsApp group etc.)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	10	4.5	4.5	4.5
Disagree	19	8.5	8.5	12.9
Neutral	21	9.4	9.4	22.3
Agree	35	15.6	15.6	37.9
Strongly Agree	139	62.1	62.1	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Social and professional network presence (e.g., Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	1.3	1.3	1.3
	Disagree	8	3.6	3.6	4.9
	Neutral	4	1.8	1.8	6.7
	Agree	23	10.3	10.3	17.0
	Strongly Agree	186	83.0	83.0	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Able to identify a simple brand meaning

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
	Disagree	2	.9	.9	1.3
	Neutral	20	8.9	8.9	10.3
	Agree	95	42.4	42.4	52.7
	Strongly Agree	106	47.3	47.3	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Using branding as an operational tool

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	20	8.9	8.9	8.9
	Agree	110	49.1	49.1	58.0
	Strongly Agree	94	42.0	42.0	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Treating the brand as assets

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	12	5.4	5.4	5.4
	Agree	88	39.3	39.3	44.6
	Strongly Agree	124	55.4	55.4	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Supporting brand through staff

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
	Disagree	65	29.0	29.0	29.5
	Neutral	112	50.0	50.0	79.5
	Agree	34	15.2	15.2	94.6
	Strongly Agree	12	5.4	5.4	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Developing new ideas to help customers

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
	Disagree	1	.4	.4	.9
	Neutral	10	4.5	4.5	5.4
	Agree	134	59.8	59.8	65.2
	Strongly Agree	78	34.8	34.8	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Able to fast track new offerings to customers

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
	Neutral	9	4.0	4.0	4.5
	Agree	137	61.2	61.2	65.6
	Strongly Agree	77	34.4	34.4	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Able to manage processes to keep costs down

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
	Disagree	2	.9	.9	1.3

Neutral	48	21.4	21.4	22.8
Agree	124	55.4	55.4	78.1
Strongly Agree	49	21.9	21.9	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Satisfying customer needs is the central purpose of our business.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
Disagree	2	.9	.9	1.3
Neutral	7	3.1	3.1	4.5
Agree	94	42.0	42.0	46.4
Strongly Agree	120	53.6	53.6	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

A customer focus is reflected in our business planning

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
Disagree	1	.4	.4	.9
Neutral	8	3.6	3.6	4.5
Agree	82	36.6	36.6	41.1
Strongly Agree	132	58.9	58.9	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

We anticipate and respond to customers' evolving needs and wants

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
Disagree	2	.9	.9	1.3
Neutral	9	4.0	4.0	5.4
Agree	97	43.3	43.3	48.7
Strongly Agree	115	51.3	51.3	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

We emphasize the evaluation of formal and informal customer complaints

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
	Disagree	2	.9	.9	1.3
	Neutral	6	2.7	2.7	4.0
	Agree	96	42.9	42.9	46.9
	Strongly Agree	119	53.1	53.1	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

We follow up with customers for quality/service feedback

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
	Disagree	2	.9	.9	1.3
	Neutral	5	2.2	2.2	3.6
	Agree	47	21.0	21.0	24.6
	Strongly Agree	169	75.4	75.4	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Increase in market share over the past 3 years

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	.4	.4	.4
	Disagree	5	2.2	2.2	2.7
	Neutral	64	28.6	28.6	31.3
	Agree	123	54.9	54.9	86.2
	Strongly Agree	31	13.8	13.8	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Increase in annual turnover over the past 3 years

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	2	.9	.9	.9

Disagree	1	.4	.4	1.3
Neutral	36	16.1	16.1	17.4
Agree	146	65.2	65.2	82.6
Strongly Agree	39	17.4	17.4	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Achieving firm profit goals over the past 3 years

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	3	1.3	1.3	1.3
Disagree	1	.4	.4	1.8
Neutral	56	25.0	25.0	26.8
Agree	127	56.7	56.7	83.5
Strongly Agree	37	16.5	16.5	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Having a better return on investment over the past 3 years

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	2	.9	.9	.9
Disagree	1	.4	.4	1.3
Neutral	37	16.5	16.5	17.9
Agree	146	65.2	65.2	83.0
Strongly Agree	38	17.0	17.0	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Our brand is better known than our most important competitor's.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	5	2.2	2.2	2.2
Disagree	13	5.8	5.8	8.0
Neutral	113	50.4	50.4	58.5
Agree	75	33.5	33.5	92.0
Strongly Agree	18	8.0	8.0	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

The quality of our brand as perceived by our customers is higher than our competitor's

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	1.8	1.8	1.8
	Disagree	13	5.8	5.8	7.6
	Neutral	108	48.2	48.2	55.8
	Agree	80	35.7	35.7	91.5
	Strongly Agree	19	8.5	8.5	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

High proportion of the products under our brand umbrella are leaders in their markets

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	11	4.9	4.9	4.9
	Disagree	41	18.3	18.3	23.2
	Neutral	99	44.2	44.2	67.4
	Agree	53	23.7	23.7	91.1
	Strongly Agree	20	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Social Media Technology Use

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	2	.9	.9	.9
	3	17	7.6	7.6	8.5
	4	97	43.3	43.3	51.8
	5	108	48.2	48.2	100.0
	Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Appendix C: Regression Results

SMTU → FP

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.270 ^a	.073	.069	.623

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.769	1	6.769	17.428	.000 ^b
	Residual	86.227	222	.388		
	Total	92.996	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.913	.263		11.089	.000
	Social Media Technology Use	.247	.059	.270	4.175	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

SMTU → BE

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.065 ^a	.004	.000	.624

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.370	1	.370	.950	.331 ^b
	Residual	86.469	222	.390		
	Total	86.839	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Brand Equity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.095	.263		11.766	.000
	Social Media Technology Use	.058	.059	.065	.975	.331

a. Dependent Variable: Brand Equity

BE → FP

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.393 ^a	.155	.151	.595

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Equity

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.389	1	14.389	40.636	.000 ^b
	Residual	78.607	222	.354		
	Total	92.996	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Equity

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.633	.217		12.106	.000
	Brand Equity	.407	.064	.393	6.375	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

SMTU → MC

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.131 ^a	.017	.013	.477

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.884	1	.884	3.881	.050 ^b
	Residual	50.545	222	.228		
	Total	51.429	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Marketing Capabilities

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.716	.201		18.477	.000
	Social Media Technology Use	.089	.045	.131	1.970	.050

a. Dependent Variable: Marketing Capabilities

MC → FP

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.392 ^a	.154	.150	.595

a. Predictors: (Constant), Marketing Capabilities

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.288	1	14.288	40.299	.000 ^b
	Residual	78.708	222	.355		
	Total	92.996	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Marketing Capabilities

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
		1	(Constant)	1.831		
	Marketing Capabilities	.527	.083	.392	6.348	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

STMU → MC → FP

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.450 ^a	.202	.195	.579

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use, Marketing Capabilities

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	18.802	2	9.401	28.002	.000 ^b
	Residual	74.194	221	.336		
	Total	92.996	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use, Marketing Capabilities

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.100	.389		2.827	.005
	Marketing Capabilities	.488	.081	.363	5.987	.000
	Social Media Technology Use	.204	.056	.222	3.667	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

STMU → CO

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.279 ^a	.078	.074	.576

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.209	1	6.209	18.722	.000 ^b
	Residual	73.630	222	.332		
	Total	79.839	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Orientation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Technology Use

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.490	.243		14.377	.000
	Social Media Technology Use	.237	.055	.279	4.327	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Orientation

CO → FP

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.377 ^a	.142	.139	.599

a. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Orientation

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.252	1	13.252	36.891	.000 ^b
	Residual	79.744	222	.359		
	Total	92.996	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Orientation

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
		1	(Constant)	2.151		
	Customer Orientation	.407	.067	.377	6.074	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

STMU → CO → FP

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.415 ^a	.172	.164	.590

a. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Orientation, Social Media Technology Use

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	15.981	2	7.990	22.929	.000 ^b
	Residual	77.015	221	.348		
	Total	92.996	223			

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Orientation, Social Media Technology Use

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.678	.346		4.854	.000
	Social Media Technology Use	.163	.058	.178	2.799	.006
	Customer Orientation	.354	.069	.328	5.141	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance